

Deliverable 1.1

Demystify Digital Deliberative Processes

WP 1 Demystify digital Deliberation

T1.1 Systematic Literature Review on AI, Argumentation and Deliberation

T1.2 Technology foresight on wide adoption of using AI in deliberations

T1.3 Stakeholders needs & considerations on using AI in deliberations

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<p>Abstract: Deliverable 1.1 synthesises a systematic literature review, Delphi-based foresight, and multi-site needs assessment to map the landscape of deliberation in the digital age. It distils normative foundations, platform affordances, AI enhancements, evaluation metrics, and future trajectories, while capturing stakeholder use cases and a preliminary product backlog. Together these insights form a unified conceptual and strategic springboard guiding user-centred, agile development of AI-supported deliberative technologies throughout AI4Deliberation.</p>	
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In the preparation of the text for this deliverable, AI was used for proofreading, editing and translation purposes.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a basic foundation for future activities of the AI4Deliberation project, based on activities within WP1 - Demystify digital Deliberations tasks. By providing a comprehensive understanding of deliberation processes and their translation into the digital context, a starting point can be created that clarifies how AI-enabled tools can be meaningfully and sustainably integrated into these deliberation processes. In particular:

- **Task 1.1** delivers a systematic literature review, examining the normative foundations of deliberation, the affordances and challenges of digital platforms, current tools on the market, and an assessment of potential use cases for AI to enhance processes. It also explores evaluation methods, the potential role of Argument Mining, institutional conditions, and best practices for integrating such technologies.
- **Task 1.2** conducts a forward-looking technology foresight exercise using the Delphi method, identifying plausible future scenarios and socio-political shifts that may shape the development and impact of digital deliberation technologies.
- **Task 1.3** involves a comprehensive needs assessment based on surveys and interviews with stakeholders across diverse pilot contexts, producing key user insights, use cases, and a preliminary product backlog to guide a user-centered agile development.

The synthesis of these three interlinked tasks of WP1, provides a strong basis for the development of corresponding AI tools, as we can be sure that they represent innovations, that they are strongly oriented towards the normative design principles of deliberative processes, that they can be set up in a crisis-proof manner and that they are not dictated from the ivory tower, but rather take the design recommendations of potential users and practitioners seriously.

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Acronyms and Abbreviation

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
ADUs	Argumentative Discourse Units
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDUA	AI Device Use Acceptance (model)
ASI	Artificial Super Intelligence
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CDCP	Consumer Debt Collection Practices (corpus)
CFG	Context-Free Grammar
CPSV-AP	Core Public Service Vocabulary Application Profile
D	Deliverable
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue vocabulary Application Profile
DDI	Digital Democratic Innovation
DGDL	Dialogue Game Description Language
DPET	Decision Focused Public Engagement Table
DQI	Discourse Quality Index
DRI	Deliberative Reason Index
EU	European Union
EDITS	Edit Distance Textual Entailment Suite
EIF	European Interoperability Framework (likely)
ePAM	eParticipation Acceptance Model
ESHCC	Empathy Scale for Human-Computer Communication
F2F	Face-to-Face

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Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
GAM	e-Government Adoption Model
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IS	Information System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
LLMs	Large Language Models
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PEST	Political, Economic, Social, Technological (analysis)
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
REST	Representational State Transfer
RTE	Recognizing Textual Entailment (challenge)
SEAB	Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board
STEEPV	Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, Political, Values (analysis)
SUS	System Usability Scale
T	Task
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TE	Textual Entailment
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
VAAs	Voting Advice Applications
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable AI

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Partners List Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
UNIS	UNI SYSTEMS SYSTMATA PLIROFORIKIS MONOPROSOPI ANONYMI EMPORIKI ETAIRIA - UNI SYSTEMS INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SYSTEMS COMMERCIAL S.M.S.A.
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS
UBAM	OTTO-FRIEDRICH-UNIVERSITAET BAMBERG
KT	KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED
UNIVDUN	UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE
IK	INSTITUT ZA KRIMINOLOGIJO PRI PRAVNI FAKULTETI V LJUBLJANI
BRANE	Dembrane B.V.
TG	THOUGHTGRAPH LTD
GFOSS	ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA
AAIT	ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS
CBAM	Stadt Bamberg
UZH	UNIVERSITY OF ZÜRICH

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 1.1 “Demystify Digital Deliberative Processes” presents the results of the WP1 - Demystify digital Deliberations. The objectives of WP1 were: O1.1 To analyse and synthesise the scientific literature and practice in the cross-section of the following fields: deliberation processes and platforms, AI and LLMs (including video LLMs), argumentation mining, evaluation models, O1.2 To map the future of multimodal AI deliberations using scenarios (Technology Foresight), and O1.3 To elicit stakeholders needs and considerations. By completing three interlinked tasks (T1.1, T1.2, and T1.3), this deliverable collectively aims to demystify deliberation, anticipate technological trajectories, and root our innovation process in real-world stakeholder needs.

The first part of this deliverable presents a systematic literature review that critically assesses the current state of deliberation, with a particular focus on its translation into digital environments. This includes an exploration of the normative foundations of deliberation, the affordances and drawbacks of digital deliberation platforms, and a comprehensive review of existing platforms in use today. It also surveys potential AI functionalities that could enhance deliberative processes, from moderation to summarization, as well as different settings and modes in which deliberation takes place. Evaluation methods specific to digital deliberation, the emerging role of Argument Mining, the institutional prerequisites for sustained use, and the identification of best practices are all addressed in detail. This review thus forms an essential knowledge base for the design and implementation of deliberative technologies within the project.

To complement the retrospective and present-oriented perspective of the literature review, T1.2 engages in a forward-looking analysis through a structured technology foresight exercise. Based on the Delphi method, this task explores a range of plausible future scenarios and uncertainties that might influence the evolution of digital deliberation technologies and their sociopolitical contexts. The foresight process ensures that the project's design and strategic orientation remain robust in the face of change, enabling us to anticipate risks and opportunities with greater clarity.

Finally, this report concludes with an in-depth needs assessment carried out through surveys and interviews conducted by partners across diverse settings. This task identifies the practical requirements of future users, maps out relevant use cases, and develops epics and user stories that capture the expectations, challenges, and priorities of key stakeholders. The output includes a preliminary product backlog, setting the stage for user-centered design and agile development processes in subsequent work packages.

Together, the insights from T1.1, T1.2, and T1.3 not only inform the design and development of the project's technological components but also establish a common conceptual and strategic framework. Deliverable 1.1, therefore, acts as a critical springboard, aligning theoretical foundations, technological foresight, and stakeholder input into a coherent vision for deliberative innovation in Europe.

2. Using Artificial Intelligence to strengthen deliberation in digital communication environments and dedicated deliberation platforms: A literature review

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2.1 Introduction: The Promise of Artificial Intelligence for Online Deliberation

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is swiftly transforming how democratic participation and public deliberation take place. In the face of increasingly complex societal issues, digital platforms are playing a crucial role in fostering inclusive conversations and supporting more participatory forms of decision-making. These platforms, particularly those enabled by AI, hold immense potential to enhance the quality, scale, and inclusivity of deliberative processes. However, this technological shift also poses questions about how AI integrates into democratic practices and whether it can uphold the normative ideals of deliberative democracy.

Drawing on an extensive survey of current scholarship, this report investigates AI's capacity to support online deliberation. It seeks to pinpoint how AI can strengthen democratic dialogue, clarify its limitations, and assess the resulting implications for design, policy, and professional practice.

The report uses the PRISMA approach to identify and account for relevant literature on the questions of relevance.

Figure 1: Overall PRISMA Flow Chart

For specific chapters, we used alternative approaches to PRISMA. We did so in cases where notes focused on large conceptual and specific technical issues. In these cases, our specialist authors built on their expertise and prior work. The work reviewed in these sections adds another 123 additional papers.

The KPIs set in the AI4Deliberation project were not only achieved in this report, but even exceeded:

Table 1: KPIs for Task 1.1

KPI	KPI reached
>= 200 Papers reviewed	320 Papers reviewed
>= 50 Platforms reviewed	50 Platforms reviewed
>= 50 AI features reviewed	92 AI features reviewed
>= 10 deliberation methods reviewed	20 deliberation methods reviewed

The report is structured into several interconnected chapters, each addressing key aspects of digital and AI-enabled deliberation:

What do we expect from digital deliberation? This chapter establishes a foundation by exploring the normative principles of deliberative democracy and identifying metrics for assessing deliberative success. It links these principles to the design features of digital deliberation environments, offering a normative lens for evaluating digital platforms.

Digital deliberation: Affordances and limitations. This chapter shines a light on the distinctive promises and pitfalls of digital deliberation. It investigates the capabilities digital platforms theoretically make available, how those capabilities are realized in practice, and how faithfully these new approaches reflect the ideals of deliberative democracy.

Deliberation in practice investigates how democratic innovations are applied in real-world contexts. By analyzing various deliberative formats, this chapter highlights the experimental and flexible nature of these initiatives and evaluates their alignment with foundational deliberative principles.

Digital solutions for democratic deliberation focuses on existing digital platforms, contrasting traditional approaches with AI-enabled solutions. The chapter identifies the functionalities and applications of these platforms, highlighting the transformative role AI can play in scaling and enhancing deliberation.

Artificial Intelligence features for democratic deliberation explore specific AI capabilities, such as natural language processing and argument mining, that address key challenges in deliberation. This chapter synthesizes current research on the affordances and risks associated with integrating AI into deliberative processes.

Spotlight: Argument mining provides a deep dive into the emerging field of argument mining, a critical tool for structuring and analyzing deliberative dialogues. This chapter emphasizes the importance of extracting reasoning and structuring arguments for fostering informed and meaningful deliberations.

How do we know if digital deliberation works? addresses evaluation methodologies for AI-enabled deliberation, focusing on quality assessment of AI outputs, deliberative experiences, and technological usability. This chapter establishes a framework for evaluating the impact and effectiveness of AI in deliberative contexts.

Institutionalizing AI-enabled deliberation examines the procedural, contextual, and institutional requirements for embedding AI-enabled deliberation into democratic governance. It underscores the interplay between technical and institutional artifacts necessary for meaningful and ethical deliberative processes.

Across its chapters, the report delivers a thorough analysis of both the present landscape and the emerging possibilities of AI-supported deliberation. Drawing on perspectives from multiple disciplines, it outlines a strategic guide for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers aiming to harness AI to strengthen democratic participation while upholding the core values of deliberative democracy.

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2.2 What do we expect from digital deliberation?

Digital technology provides new opportunities for democratic deliberation. While there is good reason to look critically at the consequences of commercial platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, or X for public discourse, there are many dedicated software solutions available, designed to provide structured spaces optimized for democratic deliberation and deliberative decision-making. These systems are used widely by different types of actors to allow people to come together to share ideas, deliberate on issues, and make collective decisions (Shortall et al., 2022). To better understand and design the fitness of software systems for digital deliberation, we first need to identify crucial features and normative ideals of deliberation and deliberative discourse.

In this chapter, we identify core features that contribute to successful digital deliberation. We first turn to democratic theory to identify core normative principles for democratic deliberation. We then provide an overview of how to identify and measure deliberative success, including specific metrics to assess whether deliberative formats lead to better understanding, diverse participation, or impactful outcomes. We turn to how these principles have been translated into design principles and features in digital deliberation environments. We close by discussing metrics specific to measuring discourse quality in digital deliberation environments.

Approach

We provide a systematic overview of how the literature treats questions of normative principles of deliberation and their translation into the design and evaluation of digital deliberation environments. We followed a structured search and review approach:

We conducted searches for a set of search terms in selected databases:

Databases:

- *Google Scholar*,
- *Web of Science*,
- *ACM Digital Library*, and
- *IEEE Explorer*.

Search terms:

- digital deliberation,
- deliberation platforms,
- online deliberation, and
- AI deliberation.

For each search term, we ranked results by citation count and reviewed the top 100 studies returned for relevance.¹ In a second step, we reviewed the references of studies identified as relevant. We checked the sources from these lists that were not identified through our prior database searches and included those relevant. We document this process according to PRISMA standards (Moher et al., 2009; Webster & Watson, 2002).

Figure 2: PRISMA Documentation for Chapters 2 and 3

From each database, we selected to review the top-100 studies (in case more than 100 results were returned). In summary, this process yielded 705 records (including records identified through relevant literature reviews, surveys and books).

¹ We deviated from this protocol only for results from *ACM Digital Library*. After the 77th result for the keyword AI Deliberation, we encountered only unrelated bulk content and duplicates of already identified sources. Accordingly, we abandoned the systematic approach in this case. A quick verification confirmed that continuing the systematic process would not have yielded any further relevant results.

In addition to these records, we also consider 3 pre-identified papers familiar to the authors based on their expertise. After removing records before screening and excluding ineligible records, 64 papers were selected to be included in the chapter.

2.2.1 Normative foundations of deliberation

Consensus as the main objective is often regarded as the overriding goal of deliberation processes (Bravo et al., 2019). However, Curato et al. (2017) argue that meta-consensus, i.e., the overwhelming acceptance of the resulting consensus decision, is more important for legitimizing the outcome. The emergence of this, however, requires a high-quality deliberation process. It is therefore important to define the underlying normative principles at the micro level of the processes in order to be able to define the high quality of a deliberative framework.

From the literature, **rationality** emerges as the most important condition for democratic deliberation. This raises the question of how rationality in discourse is achieved. Authors widely agree that for discourse to be rational, participants should back up their arguments with **evidence-based, well-reasoned justifications** (Bravo et al., 2019; Chugunov et al., 2016; T. Davies & Chandler, 2012; Esau et al., 2017, 2021; Graham, 2010; Graham & Witschge, 2003; Halpern & Gibbs, 2013; Landwehr, 2014; E. Manosevitch et al., 2014; Min, 2007; Price, 2006; Volkovskii et al., 2022; Yeo et al., 2024). Beyond the commitment to evidence-based, reasoned argument, different authors emphasize different aspects of rational discourse: This includes **access to balanced information** (Coleman & Gøtze, 2003; Ercan et al., 2019), **constructive exchange** between participants (Esau et al., 2017), the **support of arguments through evidence and reason** (Freelon, 2013; Janssen & Kies, 2005; Strandberg & Grönlund, 2012; Volkovskii et al., 2022), **sincerity** of argument (Graham & Witschge, 2003; Janssen & Kies, 2005; Strandberg & Grönlund, 2012), the **absence of emotional, manipulative and coercive speech** (Buchstein, 1997; Coleman & Gøtze, 2003; Gonzalez-Bailon et al., 2010; Witschge, 2004) and the **mitigation of power-imbalances** between participants as a precondition for free expression (Buchstein, 1997; Chugunov et al., 2016; Esau et al., 2017; Graham & Witschge, 2003; Janssen & Kies, 2005; Przybylska et al., 2023).

Another important normative foundation for democratic deliberation is **reflexivity**, the critical interrogation of arguments used in discourse (Christensen, 2021; Del Valle et al., 2020; Gastil & Felicetti, 2025; Graham, 2010; Halpern & Gibbs, 2013; Janssen & Kies, 2005; Yeo et al., 2024; You et al., 2015). Ungsuchaval et al. (2024) emphasize the following contributing factors to reflexivity: **active attention, asking questions** of understanding and other **behaviors that create a sense of a good conversational environment**. Janssen & Kies (Janssen & Kies, 2005) emphasize the importance of enabling participants to adopt **different perspectives or roles**. The role of such multidirectional and interactive communication is also highlighted by Christensen (2021). These prerequisites also feature within another normative condition for deliberative discourse, **reciprocity**.

This covers discussions based on **mutual respect** (Christensen, 2021; Del Valle et al., 2020; Hwang et al., 2014; Volkovskii et al., 2022; You et al., 2015) and **equality** (Bravo et al., 2019;

Ercan et al., 2019; Esau et al., 2017; Graham & Witschge, 2003; Grönlund et al., 2009; E. Manosevitch et al., 2014; Moss & Coleman, 2014; Price, 2006).

Two additional, if sometimes interchangeably used, normative concepts for deliberation are **inclusivity** and **diversity**. Inclusivity refers to the **openness** of the deliberation process to people from various backgrounds (e.g., gender, health status, socio-economic status). Diversity, in turn, refers to the **plurality of opinions**. Both aspects are essential to ensure that the group of participants in a deliberative format represents a sample of society as a whole, taking special efforts to include participants from groups often underrepresented in political or deliberative participation. This is ultimately necessary for the legitimacy of the outcomes (Lafont, 2015; Landemore, 2024; Mikhaylovskaya, 2024).

Together, these aspects form the normative ideal of rational-critical discourse:

Table 2: Normative Conditions of Deliberation

Normative Condition	Aspects
Rationality	Evidence-based and reasoned argument
	Access to balanced information
	Constructive exchange
	Sincerity
	Absence of emotional, manipulative and coercive speech
	Mitigation of power imbalance
Reflexivity	Active attention
	Asking questions
	Good conversation environment
	Different Perspectives
	Roleplay
Reciprocity	Mutual respect
	Equality
Inclusivity	Openness to participants from different backgrounds
Diversity	Plurality of represented opinions

2.2.2 Measuring deliberation

Measuring deliberative quality has not been consistently addressed in the literature. Researchers have employed a wide range of impact metrics, and different theoretical constructs often use the same terminology, while entirely distinct instruments claim to measure the same impact. In deliberative contexts, quality can be understood as having at least two dimensions across different scales.

The first dimension pertains to the **quality of the deliberative process**, defined by normative standards that ensure deliberation occurs in its most effective form. The second dimension relates to the impact of deliberation, which can be observed at the individual or group level, or even on a broader, macro scale. Notably, deliberation can be evaluated both in terms of its *procedural characteristics* and its *outcomes*.

On the procedural side, deliberative quality is determined by how well the process adheres to key principles such as inclusiveness, equality, reason-giving, and authenticity. This involves examining the content and structure of deliberative interactions or engaging directly with participants. Researchers often code discourse contributions to assess attributes such as rationality, reciprocity, and reflexivity. For example, studies have analyzed the **quality, constructiveness, or type of argument or justification** (T. Davies & Chandler, 2012; Esau et al., 2017, 2021; Halpern & Gibbs, 2013). Other indicators include the **relevance of arguments** (Esau et al., 2021), the presence of mutual respect—often inferred from levels of **politeness** or **civility** (Esau et al., 2017; Halpern & Gibbs, 2013)—and the extent to which contributions **reference previous statements** (Esau et al., 2017; Graham & Witschge, 2003; Stromer-Galley, 2007). One comprehensive approach that integrates these metrics is the *Discourse Quality Index (DQI)* (Steiner et al., 2005).

However, deliberation is not solely about the process; it is valued for its potential to produce **better decision-making**. The outcomes of deliberation include not only epistemic gains — such as improved accuracy, truth, and factual knowledge (or epistemic superiority, as framed by Estlund & Landemore, 2018) — but also enhanced participant capacity for learning and reasoning. This encompasses not only rationality but also the reasonableness of the decision itself. Reasonableness emphasizes the quality of the reasoning process and the integration of diverse perspectives, a concept captured by the *Deliberative Reason Index (DRI)* (Niemeyer & Veri, 2022).

Based on these considerations, we can distinguish two types of measurable quality criteria:

- (1) **Procedural Measures:** These focus on the normative components that drive the deliberative process, such as rationality, reciprocity, inclusivity, diversity, and mutual respect. These aspects are typically assessed using tools like the DQI, which evaluate how participants engage in deliberative reasoning and interact with one another, often through content analysis of discourses and exchanges.
- (2) **Output Measures:** These assess the outcomes of deliberation. They include not only epistemic outcomes, such as opinion change and factual knowledge gain—but also

the reasonableness of the decision, reflecting the quality of the reasoning process and the effective integration of diverse perspectives, which can be captured by DRI.

By distinguishing between procedural and output measures, we can more comprehensively evaluate the multifaceted nature of deliberative quality, ensuring that both the process and its outcomes are thoroughly assessed.

Table 3: Quality Metrics of Deliberation

Target Concept	Signal	Approach
Procedural quality		
Rationality	Argument quality	Content analysis
	Argument type	Content analysis
	Argument justification	Content analysis
	Argument relevance	Content analysis
Reciprocity	Constructive exchange	Content analysis
	Politeness	Content analysis
	Civility	Content analysis
	Interconnected flow of argument	Content analysis
Inclusivity	Demographic characteristics	Survey (observational)

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Target Concept	Signal	Approach
Diversity	Attitudes represented	Survey (observational)
Mutual respect	Dialogical sentiments	Survey (observational)
Output quality		
Reflexivity	Opinion change	Survey (experimental)
	Knowledge gain	Survey (experimental)
Reasonableness	Deliberative reasoning	Survey (experimental)

Surveys with observational and experimental designs provide a promising addition to measuring the quality of deliberative discourse. Observational surveys can identify distributions of **demographic and attitudinal characteristics** within those invited to deliberative formats, those actually participating, and the general population (Neblo & et al., 2010; Schlosberg et al., 2008). This speaks to the **inclusivity** and **diversity** of deliberative formats. Since observational surveys depend on participants' self-assessments, they are limited in reliably identifying discourse features, such as rationality, reflexivity, and reciprocity (Min, 2007).

Experimental designs can examine the **effects of deliberative formats or specific elements** by selectively assigning respondents to treatment and control groups. Treatment groups experience deliberation or are assigned specific features within deliberation. By comparing responses of those exposed to the treatment and those not, researchers can identify the effects of deliberative formats and features (Min, 2007; Rhee & Kim, 2009). This includes **opinion change**, **knowledge gain** (Grönlund et al., 2009; Min, 2007) and **deliberative**

reasoning (Niemeyer, Veri, Dryzek, & Bächtiger, 2024). These variables have been used to both speak to the reflexivity and “success” of deliberation.

2.2.3 Designing for deliberation

To translate these normative ideals into actionable strategies, the next section systematically reviews the existing literature on design principles that operationalize the core values of democratic deliberation.

Table 4: Design Principles of Online Deliberation Spaces

Design Principle	Target Concept	Signal
Text-based spaces		
Asynchronous Communication	Rationality	Argument justification
		Argument quality
	Reflexivity	Knowledge Gain
	Inclusivity	Demographic characteristics
Moderation	Rationality	Argument relevance
	Reciprocity	constructive exchange
		Politeness
		Civility
Anonymity	Rationality	Sincerity
		Mitigation of Power Imbalance
	Diversity	Attitudes represented
Informed Nature (including provision, summarization and depiction of information)	Rationality	Argument quality
		Argument type
		Argument justification
		Argument relevance

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Design Principle	Target Concept	Signal
	Reflexivity	Knowledge Gain
Structured Agenda	Rationality	Argument relevance
Engagement	Diversity	Attitudes represented

One of the most widely recognized design principles in the literature is the use of **text-based spaces to enable asynchronous communication** (Aragón et al., 2017; Bravo et al., 2019; Coleman & Moss, 2012; T. Davies & Chandler, 2012; Esau et al., 2017; Halpern & Gibbs, 2013; Janssen & Kies, 2005; Moss & Coleman, 2014; Price, 2006; Rose & Sæbø, 2010; Semaan et al., 2015; Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024; Wright & Street, 2007; Yeo et al., 2024). Only a small portion of scholars argue for synchronous (live) communication, as it is said to lead to a more deliberative and social conversational environment (Ungsuchaval et al., 2024) and to prevent distortions in power dynamics (Showers et al., 2015).

Another feature that is often discussed is the **moderation** of the online space. Some authors debate the trade-off between the freedom of the online space and the establishment of social norms and a structured discussion process (Coleman & Götze, 2003; Graham, 2010; Przybylska et al., 2023).

However, the majority advocate for the necessity of moderation (Aragón et al., 2017; Bravo et al., 2019; Buchstein, 1997; Christensen, 2021; Coleman & Moss, 2012; De Liddo & Strube, 2021; Esau et al., 2017; Gastil & Richards, 2016; Gonzalez-Bailon et al., 2010; Janssen & Kies, 2005; Moss & Coleman, 2014; Przybylska et al., 2023; Rhee & Kim, 2009; Wright, 2012; Wright & Street, 2007).

In this context, some authors emphasize that moderators should adopt less of a purely controlling role and instead take on a facilitating role fulfilling different functions, hereby the moderation role is referred to as intermediary (T. Davies & Chandler, 2012; Edwards, 2002; Graham & Witschge, 2003; Landwehr, 2014; Witschge, 2004).

Another debated topic in the literature is the question of **anonymity**. While some researchers advocate for anonymity due to the increased honesty it fosters among participants (Price, 2006; Rose & Sæbø, 2010), others argue that it undermines adherence to interpersonal norms and respectful interactions, that the identifiability of commenters had a stimulating effect on the discussion, or more practical, to avoid the necessity of moderation (Bravo et al., 2019; Coleman & Götze, 2003; De Cindio & Stortone, 2013; Halpern & Gibbs, 2013; Janssen & Kies, 2005). A few take a more balanced stance on this issue (Aragón et al., 2017; Coleman & Moss, 2012; E. Manosevitch et al., 2014; Rhee & Kim, 2009). Some suggest that there could be options for (optionally temporary) pseudonymization towards other users, while requiring authentication with the platform itself (Christensen, 2021; Moore et al., 2021; Semaan et al., 2015).

Additionally, the literature describes design principles aimed at supporting the **informed nature** of the deliberation process. Most of these focus on the mere **provision** of information (Bravo et al., 2019; Christensen, 2021; Esau et al., 2017; Schlosberg et al., 2008). Some emphasize the importance of balance (Coleman & Gøtze, 2003; Gastil & Felicetti, 2025), while others highlight the aggregation and structured presentation of this information (Robertson, 2006; Semaan et al., 2015; Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024). The importance of **visualizing** this information or the discourse in the form of concept or argument maps is also often emphasized in the literature (Chugunov et al., 2016; Coleman & Moss, 2012; De Liddo & Strube, 2021; Towne & Herbsleb, 2012).

Along similar lines are those who advocate for visual and cognitive cues to remind participants of the normative principles of deliberation (E. Manosevitch et al., 2014; I. Manosevitch, 2014; Yeo et al., 2024). Some also advocate for the **filtering or summarization** of information, while avoiding censorship (Buchstein, 1997; Coleman & Gøtze, 2003).

Regarding the classic procedural elements of deliberation processes, it is often emphasized that they should be based on a **structured agenda and well defined topics** (De Cindio & Stortone, 2013; Esau et al., 2017; Moss & Coleman, 2014; Price, 2006). Hereby, Coleman & Gøtze (2003) emphasize the necessity to divide the discussions by topic into different channels, while Towne & Herdsleb (2012) emphasize that redundancy of threads should be avoided.

Threads on ideas should also follow a hierarchical structure, allowing responses to the original idea contributor (Aragón et al., 2017; Phang et al., 2014; Wen & Wei, 2018).

Przybylska et al. (2023) additionally suggest providing some predefined scenarios to discuss. Only a few dissenting voices advocate for a bottom-up approach, where the deliberators themselves take over agenda setting to improve their feeling of ownership (Rose & Sæbø, 2010).

Recent literature also points to the positive effects of gamification modules, including reward or level-up systems, increasing the attractiveness of platform participation (Gastil & Richards, 2016; Kim et al., 2022; I. Manosevitch, 2014). To ensure long-term **engagement** and sustain the positive effects of deliberation processes on participants' political participation, some researchers suggest incorporating feedback loops that demonstrate how the results generated on the platform can influence public political decision-making (Bravo et al., 2019; Gastil & Richards, 2016; Phang et al., 2014). Semaan et al. (2015) provide a similar rationale, arguing that feedback mechanisms on the impact of individual posts would also be useful.

The discussion of design principles heavily focuses on rationality, such as supporting discourse with information, promoting sincerity (e.g. identification), or ensuring process transparency. Features that directly support representativeness, such as diversity and equality among users in deliberation processes, or those that foster reflexivity are significantly underemphasized in the literature.

2.2.4 Measuring digital deliberation

Digital deliberation provides the same measurement and evaluative opportunities as other forms of deliberation (De Cindio & Stortone, 2013; Esau et al., 2017; Graham & Witschge, 2003; Wright & Street, 2007). But the controlled nature of digitally mediated deliberation offers further opportunities as well. This includes the detailed analysis of text data (Grimmer et al., 2022) and digital trace data (Howison et al., 2011), which provide new windows to content, interactions, and structures within deliberative formats. For example, in digital deliberation environments, **rationality** is often represented by message length, as longer messages are assumed to reflect better reasoning (Halpern & Gibbs, 2013). Similarly, **coherence** and **continuity** within discussion threads can be captured very effectively (Graham & Witschge, 2003).

Text-based communication logs allow for the assessment of **equality** by examining the quantity of users' contributions e.g., the number of comments each user makes, and the calculated **proportion of dominance** in the discussion (T. Davies & Chandler, 2012; Phang et al., 2014; Rhee & Kim, 2009). These can then be analyzed using metrics like the **GINI coefficient** (Bravo et al., 2019). The high degree of coverage within digital trace data also allows us to better trace the argument portfolio of each participant and therefore the **plurality of positions**, which makes **diversity** by far more measurable than in face-to-face deliberation settings (Bravo et al., 2019).

The same logic applies to the **validity of claims**, since it allows us to assess the total numbers, percentages and distributions of claims validated through agreement or disagreement (Chugunov et al., 2016).

Additionally, this opens up the possibility for **automating metric evaluation** using tools such as DelibAnalysis (Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024).

Furthermore, tracking **participation metrics** is simplified by comparing metrics such as the number of registrations against the number of unique visitors (De Cindio & Stortone, 2013; Esau et al., 2017).

Lastly, digital deliberation environments enable network metrics based on the characteristics of interactions between users and the assignment of metadata to network ties. For example, tie width might reflect representativeness (diversity, equality), while depth might capture the argumentative quality through levels of interaction, the length of posts, or the number of nested replies (Aragón et al., 2017; Bravo et al., 2019; Gonzalez-Bailon et al., 2010).

In sum, digital deliberation environments facilitate the collection of quantitative metrics. However, as in other deliberation formats, some core normative requirements of deliberation, such as reflexivity, are still difficult to capture by relying on purely quantitative approaches.

2.2.5 Conclusion

This discussion shows that dedicated software solutions offer promising spaces for digitally mediated deliberation. However, they do not necessarily connect and correspond with all core normative features of democratic deliberation. These gaps are important to keep in mind in designing and evaluating environments for digital deliberation. This requires the conscious design of metrics that can capture not just dimensions of rationality in arguments but also the diversity of contributors, the level of mutual respect, and deeper cognitive processes such as reflexivity. While normative discussions on design principles, including asynchronous versus synchronous communication, moderation, anonymity, and structured agendas, are notably insightful, they rarely comprehensively address representativeness or reflexivity. This gap underscores the need to integrate normative imperatives into platform features that foster inclusivity, diversity, equality, and deeper cognitive engagement among participants. The emergence of new measurement tools and digital trace data offers fresh avenues for analyzing deliberative processes, yet critical dimensions like reflexivity and internal transformation remain elusive.

Taken together, these insights set the stage for exploring how future innovations, including AI-driven approaches, might refine both the metrics and the design frameworks underlying online deliberation.

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2.3 Digital deliberation: Affordances and limitations

Digital deliberation has introduced transformative opportunities for public discourse, reshaping how individuals and groups engage in collective reasoning and decision-making. As societies increasingly turn to digital spaces for dialogue, it becomes essential to explore both their affordances and limitations. Here, we examine how digital deliberation addresses specific issues inherent in traditional deliberation, alongside its theoretical and practical contributions to the deliberative process.

Key questions guide this investigation. First, what specific problems within the concept of deliberation can digital platforms address? Second, what theoretical affordances do these platforms provide? Third, how are these theoretical affordances implemented in practice? Exploring actual platform designs and functionalities sheds light on their real-world contributions.

Moreover, we evaluate whether the affordances of digital deliberation are systematically assessed for their impact on deliberative quality. Such evaluation is crucial to understanding how well these platforms fulfil their democratic potential. Finally, the chapter critically addresses limitations of digital deliberation when seen in the context of normative ideals of democratic deliberation introduced above.

2.3.1 Approach

To comprehensively address these questions, we follow the same approach as in the previous chapter. For details and documentation, see above.

2.3.2 Affordances of digital deliberation and the limits of traditional deliberation formats

The shift to digital deliberation responds to key problems that have historically limited the effectiveness of traditional deliberative practices. **Scalability** is a major concern in traditional settings, constrained by physical spaces and logistical barriers. Digital communication overcomes accessibility barriers by enabling large-scale participation, accommodating voices from diverse geographic and demographic contexts (e.g. Coleman & Gøtze, 2003; Wright & Street, 2007). It is neither feasible for organizers to connect more than a sample of a few hundred people at a time in face-to-face settings, nor is it realistic for the general population to dedicate sufficient time and financial resources in their private lives to regularly travel or attend scheduled face-to-face sessions, leaving alone additional mobility challenges. Therefore, we can treat this issue not only as a logistical but also as an economic obstacle to traditional deliberation processes (Buchstein, 1997; Moss & Coleman, 2014; Price, 2006). Scholars such as Coleman & Gøtze (2003) and Grönlund et al.

Grönlund et al. (2009) highlight that the online nature of digital deliberation enables the emergence of a scale-free network and thus removes geographic barriers, making deliberation accessible to a broader audience (Buchstein, 1997; Wisniewski, 2013).

Another affordance of these platforms is the opportunity for **asynchronous communication** which helps to lower opportunity costs for participation emerging from time restrictions, as every citizen can participate according to their own time resources without being bound to scheduled sessions (e.g. Ercan et al., 2019; Halpern & Gibbs, 2013; Wright & Street, 2007).

Regarding the economic barriers of traditional deliberation processes, the literature also indicates that the design of most platforms is suited to empowering participants in many-to-many communication. The ability to create informational content and express one's opinion, which can simultaneously reach an almost unlimited number of recipients, significantly **reduces the economic cost** for each participant in voicing their opinion (Stockmann et al., 2020; You et al., 2015). This, in turn, lowers the barrier to participation and contributes to the scalability of the process.

Together with the mostly text-based communication modalities on platforms, advanced tools, including hierarchical threads and argument visualizations, prevent discussions from becoming unmanageable, ensuring that deliberation remains coherent as participation scales up (Towne & Herbsleb, 2012). In contrast to face-to-face deliberation, participants are thus able to form a more **comprehensive understanding** of the discussion rather than focusing solely on individual arguments. De Liddo and Strube (2021) further argue that online platforms that display aggregated content enable deliberators to achieve better sense-making, as this approach can reduce cognitive overload.

The creation of scaling opportunities simultaneously addresses another issue of traditional deliberation processes: **representativeness**. Landemore (Landemore, 2024) argues that samples, not least due to self-selection bias, fail to adequately represent the diversity of opinions in society. In defining this problem, she references, among others, Lafont's (2015) statement: "No Democratization without Mass Deliberation." This issue is also widely discussed in the literature (Bravo et al., 2019; Ercan et al., 2019; Gastil & Richards, 2016; Min, 2007).

The resulting increased **diversity of platform users** not only strengthens the legitimacy of outcomes but also enhances deliberative quality by exposing each participant to a broader range of perspectives. Engaging critically with the full spectrum of opinions not only helps to prevent the risk of groupthink in small groups but also to improve the fairness of competition of opinions (Moss & Coleman, 2014; Phang et al., 2014; Price, 2006; Wisniewski, 2013). Authors such as Semaan et al. (2015) and Coleman & Götze (2003) emphasize that platforms specifically designed for deliberative processes aim to expose users, either unstructured or equally, to a variety of viewpoints. This also helps prevent the formation of echo chambers, as observed on traditional social media platforms (Gonzalez-Bailon et al., 2010; Phang et al., 2014).

Another problem of traditional deliberation processes is the persistent perception of **social hierarchies** in face-to-face interactions, which prevents all participants from feeling a sense of equality. This can lead to some participants not expressing their opinions as openly as they might otherwise (Halpern & Gibbs, 2013; Price, 2006; Showers et al., 2015).

An affordance of online deliberation platforms is that through anonymization and pseudonymization, background variables are concealed. This ensures that these variables are not apparent in the evaluation of contributions or self-assessment, as comparisons with others are eliminated (Price, 2006). Another affordance that helps reduce social hierarchies in digital deliberation processes arises from the design feature of asynchronous communication. Since all participants can work at their own pace, due to the text-based communication logic, they are able to formulate their thoughts reflexively and fully without being constrained by preset speaking times (Min, 2007).

Further, some authors claim that the spaces for free exchange of ideas in public discourse are diminishing (Graham & Witschge, 2003; Przybylska et al., 2023). This would raise the necessity of intentionally designing and providing dedicated spaces for digital deliberation (Graham & Witschge, 2003).

The majority of the literature agrees that the overarching affordance of digital deliberation is the construction of a newly emerging socio-technical public sphere (Esau et al., 2021; Gastil & Richards, 2016; Rose & Sæbø, 2010; Semaan et al., 2015; Stockmann et al., 2020; Wright, 2012; Rasmussen, 2009; Strandberg & Grönlund, 2012; You et al., 2015; Phang et al., 2014; Graham, 2010). With these offerings comes the opportunity of conceptually situating them between the traditional concepts of the formal and informal public sphere (Landemore, 2024). This positioning facilitates the **softening of topical boundaries, enabling greater engagement across themes** (Grönlund et al., 2009). In contrast, traditional deliberation settings rely on rigid formal discourse structures due to the aforementioned economic constraints. It is not explicitly mentioned, but this could also have an impact on long-term engagement. Platforms also provide a good opportunity through their structures to inform participants, via feedback loops, about the impact of deliberation processes on actual policy outcomes. This, along with other technical features such as gamification elements, can help ensure that participants remain involved in the deliberation process for longer periods (Gastil & Richards, 2016).

Table 5: Affordances of Digital Deliberation Platforms

Affordance	Papers Addressing the Affordance
Many-to-Many Communication	Halpern & Gibbs (2013); Wright & Street (2007); Buchstein (1997); Ercan et al. (2019); Rose & Sæbo (2010); Stockmann et al. (2020); Rasmussen (2014); Phang et al. (2014); Christensen (2021); Freelon (2015); Wen & Wie (2018).
Construction of a Socio-Technical Public Sphere	Wright (2012); Rose & Sæbo (2010); Semaan et al. (2015); Esau et al. (2020); Gastil & Richards (2017); Stockmann et al. (2020); Rasmussen (2014); Strandberg & Grönlund (2014); You et al. (2015); Phang et al. (2014); Graham (2010).

Affordance	Papers Addressing the Affordance
Promote Reflexivity	Coleman & Moss (2012); Yeo et al. (2024); De Liddo & Strube (2021); Phang et al. (2014).
Enhanced Accessibility	Schlosberg et al. (2008); Stockmann et al. (2020); Christensen (2021); Hwang et al. (2014).
Promote Legitimacy of Public Decisions	Manosevitch et al. (2014); Gastil (2021); Gastil & Richards (2017).
Grass-Root Communication and Information Access	Buchstein (1997); Rose & Saebo (2010); Wisniewski (n.d.); Wen & Wie (2018).
Introduction to New Perspectives (Fairness)	Moss & Coleman (2014); Price (2006); Wisniewski (n.d.); Phang et al. (2014).
Reduce Echo Chambers	Gonzalez-Bailon (2010); Phang et al. (2014).
Create Structured Discussion Spaces	Gonzalez-Bailon (2010).
Promote Civic Identity and Engagement	Semaan et al. (2015); Manosevitch (2014); Janssen & Kies (2005).
Support for Summarization and Sensemaking	De Liddo & Strube (2021).
Blurring of Topical Borders	Grönlund et al. (2009).
Scale-Free Communication	Buchstein (1997); Wisniewski (n.d.).
Improved Responsiveness of Policies	Gastil & Richards (2017).
Shift from Passive to Active Participation	Chugunov et al. (2016).

2.3.3 Limitations to digital deliberation

Scalability might not only be an affordance of digital deliberation, it might also be a limitation. For example, Coleman & Gøtze (2003) identify the **Problem of Scale** as a potential drawback of digital deliberation. They argue that the quality of deliberation decreases as the size of the deliberative community grows. Shortall et al. (2022) attribute this phenomenon to various causes like a lack of social norms and cues or of perceived abilities, information overload and unjust power distortions.

Some authors support this reasoning and argue that hate speech and a decline in interpersonal norms arise due to a **lack of social cues**, which is exacerbated by **anonymity** in digital communication environments (Coleman, 2005; Hwang et al., 2014; E. Manosevitch et al., 2014).

Others argue that digital deliberation can lead to **information overload**, since the opportunity for every participant to create and publish content can render discussions opaque. Each person has only a limited cognitive and temporal capacity, which becomes exhausted after consuming a certain number of arguments. Therefore, the sheer volume of information in a scaled deliberation process could lead to a kind of information overload (Buchstein, 1997; Semaan et al., 2015; Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024). Another frequently mentioned drawback is the **accessibility of platforms**, as they tend to attract only technophile individuals, while technophobic individuals refrain from participating. This self-selection bias not only reduces the number of participants but also distorts public opinion (Coleman & Gøtze, 2003; Grönlund et al., 2009; Rose & Sæbø, 2010; Strandberg & Grönlund, 2012).

Some scholars further argue that scaling efforts might fail due to limited political interest, resulting in low participant numbers (Coleman & Gøtze, 2003; J. Davies et al., 2021; Strandberg & Grönlund, 2012).

Wisniewski (2013) underscores this point by highlighting that there is no linear relationship between the accessibility of a platform and actual participation.

Additionally, the question of **platform operators** remains unresolved, as they may bring commercial interests into the process. The management of data from democratic processes by companies driven by economic interests poses a serious threat to the legitimacy of the outcomes. This danger, though significant, appears underrepresented in the literature, being mentioned explicitly only by Buchstein (1997), who also creates awareness for the problem of traceability, and abstractly addressed by Coleman (2005), who posits that "technology is never neutral." Davies et al. (2021) also emphasize that the ideas generated on these platforms are often lacking in complexity and depth, making them not necessarily suitable for use by political decision-makers.

Since the **legitimacy** of the outcomes of these isolated discussions remains limited, their impact on shaping real-world policy decisions is also restricted (J. Davies et al., 2021; Gastil & Richards, 2016; Grönlund et al., 2009). This poses a significant danger in the context of deliberation, as many positive effects associated with successful deliberation processes, such as increased political engagement (Strandberg & Grönlund, 2014), may be nullified by the disappointment of participants (Coleman & Gøtze, 2003).

Building on the template of conventional social media platforms, some authors argue that online deliberation carries the potential risk of balkanization or polarization due to the formation of **echo chambers** (Buchstein, 1997; De Liddo & Strube, 2021; Grönlund et al., 2009; Hwang et al., 2014; Strandberg & Grönlund, 2014; Wisniewski, 2013).

Early efforts in digital deliberation also encountered technical issues, such as server outages (Grönlund et al., 2009; Strandberg & Grönlund, 2014). However, the more recent literature does not elaborate further on these challenges, suggesting that with the advancement of the internet and server capacities, such problems no longer persist.

Table 6: Problems of Offline Deliberation Addressed by Digital Deliberation

Problem Addressed	Papers Addressing the Problem
Scalability	Coleman & Gotze (2001); Wright & Street (2007); Rose & Saebo (2010); Grönlund et al. (2009); Moss & Coleman (2014); Manosevitch et al. (2014); Semaan et al. (2015); Strandberg & Grönlund (2014); Phang et al. (2014); Gastil & Felicetti (2024); Siachos & Karacapilidis (2024); Towne & Herbsleb (2012).
Accessibility	Coleman & Gotze (2001); Buchstein (1997); Witschge (2004); Ercan et al. (2019); Moss & Coleman (2014); Manosevitch et al. (2014); Semaan et al. (2015); Aragón et al. (2017); Hwang et al. (2014); Gastil (2021).
Economical Barriers	Wright & Street (2007); Buchstein (1997); Price (2006); Gonzalez-Bailon (2010); Davies & Chandler (2011); Schlosberg et al. (2008); Grönlund et al. (2009); Moss & Coleman (2014); Manosevitch et al. (2014); Stockmann et al. (2020); Towne & Herbsleb (2012); Chris Wisniewski (n.d.).
Hierarchies/Power Distortions	Price (2006); Halpern & Gibbs (2013); Showers et al. (2015).
Representativeness	Min (2007); Ercan et al. (2019); Bravo et al. (2019); Gastil & Richards (2017); Lafont (2015); Landemore (2024)
Broadening Participation	Wright (2012); Rasmussen (2014); Gastil (2021).
Declining Spaces for Public Deliberation	Graham & Witschge (2003); Przybylska et al. (2023).
Long-Term Engagement	Gastil & Richards (2017); Semaan et al. (2015); Bravo et al. (2019); Phang et al. (2022).

2.3.4 Conclusion

Digital deliberation offers valuable opportunities to enhance traditional deliberative formats by addressing challenges like scalability, accessibility, and representativeness. Features such as asynchronous communication, anonymity, and content aggregation enable broader participation and reduce economic, geographic, and social barriers. These platforms foster diverse engagement within a socio-technical public sphere, but issues like information overload, echo chambers, technophobia, and commercial interests remain significant drawbacks.

To realize their potential, careful attention is needed to platform design, accessibility, and mitigation of challenges like polarization and declining deliberative quality. Additionally, integrating platform outputs into policymaking and ensuring transparency in platform governance are critical to maximizing their democratic impact.

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2.4 Deliberation in practice?

This chapter looks at deliberative formats in practice. It identifies more than 20 deliberative process formats from real-world cases. The following discussion is structured around the four core deliberative principles and the design features that help uphold them. When examining the formats of democratic innovations, particularly those centered on deliberative processes, two key challenges emerge:

1. Deliberative democratic innovations often rely on unstandardized approaches because mini-publics are highly context-specific, with their design and operation tailored to their purpose, the issues at hand, and the sociopolitical environment in which they are implemented (Curato et al., 2021); and
2. Standardized definitions as proposed by (Elstub & Escobar, 2019) are often subject to conceptual stretching that is often linked to a theoretical level without real-world applications (Veri, 2023). Yet, deliberative democratic innovations are also intended as the political projects of deliberative democratic theory (Alnemr et al., 2020), their processes are frequently deconstructed in light of theory-based core principles rather than adhering to standardized formats. Consequently, they tend to be experimental and highly flexible, adapting to specific contexts and resulting in significant internal variation in their core features.

To face these hurdles, the review was based on a principle based literature review, which implies to organize the research on deliberative formats around foundational principles that define the concept of deliberative concept. In this respect, such deliberative principles were first defined accordingly to the literature on deliberative democracy and subsequently a thematic analysis based on such principles was run by using a bottom-up approach, by using Participedia and focusing on what Veri's (2023) mapping study on democratic innovations identified as a cluster of deliberative democratic formats.

2.4.1 Deliberation FORMATS

In the subsequent section, we identify the key deliberative principles that underpin democratic engagement. Then, we outline the design features necessary to uphold these principles across various democratic innovation formats. Using data from Participedia, we analyze 20 carefully selected formats—categorized as either face-to-face (F2F) or online/mediated—and examine how each format addresses or struggles to meet the deliberative principles discussed previously. Subsequently, we evaluate the benefits of these formats in fostering deliberation and democratic participation and explore their limitations and challenges. Finally, we review the available empirical evidence to assess the practical application and impact of these formats.

2.4.2 Deliberative Principles

Following classic deliberative democracy theory scholarship (Chambers, 2003; J. Cohen, 1997; J. Dryzek, 2007), four principles recur:

- **Inclusiveness:** Ensuring the participation of diverse groups of citizens by accounting for cognitive differences, opinion diversity, and socio-demographic variations (Carson & Martin, 1999; J. Dryzek, 2007; Fishkin, 2009).
- **Equality:** Providing equal opportunities for all participants to express their reasons, contribute to agenda-setting, and influence outcomes (Mansbridge, 1999; Thompson, 2008).
- **Reason-Giving:** Facilitating the production of reasoned and informed opinions through deliberative processes (Fishkin, 1997; Niemeyer, Veri, Dryzek, & Baechtiger, 2024).
- **Authenticity and Mutual Respect:** Promoting open, sincere, and reciprocal engagement with a commitment to mutual listening (Warren & Mansbridge, 2013).

While other principles come into place, like the idea of **equity** which points to the inclusion of underrepresented communities (Curato et al., 2021), those principles are also considered the four core elements generally discussed by the literature on deliberative formats (Curato et al., 2021).

2.4.3 Process attributes that uphold deliberative principles

Scholars (Curato et al., 2021; Fung, 2003; Gastil, 2008; Smith, 2009) identify core design features that reinforce these principles:

- **Random/Stratified Selection:** Enhances inclusiveness, mitigates elite capture, and fosters discursive diversity (J. Dryzek & Niemeyer, 2008; Fishkin, 2009; Neblo & et al., 2010). Random selection should incorporate proxies of plurality — such as demographic, discursive, and developmental diversity — based on prior deliberative experiences to ensure effective representation (J. S. Dryzek & Niemeyer, 2024), but also to guarantee equality in participation as everybody has an equal chance to be selected and participate. Selection methods are also a core feature to guarantee equity and inclusivity, or that give everybody the chance to be represented, with special focus on marginalized communities or groups of people (Curato et al., 2021).
- **Expert/Balanced Briefing:** Promotes reason-giving by providing participants with factual and diverse perspectives, ensuring informed deliberation (Fishkin, 1997).
- **Group-Building Activities:** Enables participants to establish internal norms and deliberation rules, which in turn stimulate reasoning and foster productive engagement (Niemeyer, Veri, Dryzek, & Baechtiger, 2024).

- **Skilled Facilitation:** Ensures equality by allowing everyone to speak and fosters authenticity by encouraging respectful dialogue and preventing strategic domination (Parkinson, 2003).
- **Transparent/Repeated Sessions:** Builds trust among participants, clarifies procedures, and supports deeper reflection and sustained engagement (Chambers, 2003; Niemeyer, Veri, Dryzek, & Baechtiger, 2024; Warren & Pearse, 2008).
- **Duration:** While this is not a format feature, it is considered as a core element to guarantee cognitive inclusion and equal opportunities to learn complex topics (Curato et al., 2021).

2.4.4 List of Formats, Divided by Face-to-Face vs. Online

In his mapping study, Veri (2023) identifies four clusters of democratic innovations categorized by participation types. Two of these clusters point to active modes of participation, meaning that participants are interactively engaging in reasoned exchanges. These approaches align with normative ideals of fostering deliberation, inclusivity and public reasoning (Veri, 2023). In this respect, the empirical analysis identifies central and peripheral cases considering three specific dimensions: a) a procedural deliberative dimension, b) a participant number dimension, c) a deliberative decision output dimension. The final list was defined considering the procedural and participant number dimension.

Table 7: Deliberative Formats

Format	Overview	Features	Output	Subtypes	References
Citizens' Assembly	Randomly selected citizens deliberating on policy/constitutional questions (often multiple weekends) (~10-500 participants). F2F and/or Online	Facilitated, stratified random selection, structured deliberation, group building, Experts' presence, Multiple-days	Policy Recommendations	Also, general term for 'Mini-public'	Warren & Pearse 2008, Niemeyer et al. 2024, Smith 2009, Farrell et al. 2019

Format	Overview	Features	Output	Subtypes	References
Deliberative Poll	Survey a random sample (500-1000), bring them face-to-face to deliberate, then re-survey to measure opinion change. F2F and/or Online	Facilitated, stratified random selection, structured deliberation, experts' presence, large participation	Informed opinion	Deliberation Day, Delphi, Survey Deliberation Methods	Fishkin 2009, Arnesen et al 2024
Citizens' Juries	Small group (~12-25) meets for several days, weighing expert evidence, issuing a "verdict" based on a specific question to answer, F2F and/or Online	Facilitated, stratified selection, structured deliberation, group building, experts' presence, multiple day	Policy verdict	Citizens' Initiative Review, Planning Cell	Smith 2009, Smith & Wales 2000, Gastil & Knobloch 2019
(Participatory) consensus conferences	Lay panel (10-25) publicly questions experts on scientific/technical issues, then produces a consensus statement. F2F and/or Online	Facilitated, stratified random selection, structured deliberation, experts' presence	Consensus statement	Participatory consensus conference, Consensus Forum, Citizens' Conferences	Joss & Durant 1995, Sanders 1997

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Format	Overview	Features	Output	Subtypes	References
Planning Cells	Multiple small "cells" (~25 each) deliberate a public issue simultaneously; results synthesized, affected and unaffected people. F2F and/or Online	Facilitated, stratified selection, structured deliberation, expert presence	Synthesized recommendations	Citizens' Council, Citizens' Assembly, citizens' references panels	Dienel 2005
21 st Century Town Meeting	Large-scale events with hundreds/thousands of participants using technology (e.g., keypad voting). F2F and/or Online	Facilitated, stratified selection, expert presence	Aggregation action priorities	New England Town Meeting, AmericaSpeaks, Audience Response Systems	Lukensmeyer & Brigham 2002
World Café	Informal, café-style rotation of small-group discussions around core questions. F2F	Voluntary, informal relationship	Idea generation	Conversation Café, Socratic Cafe, Kichen Table Conversation	Brown 2010
Participatory Budgeting	Citizens discuss and vote on the allocation of public funds, typically at municipal or district levels, F2F and/or Online	Voluntary, election appointment	Budgetary allocations	Yanjin Model, Citizens Budget	Sintomer et al. 2008

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Format	Overview	Features	Output	Subtypes	References
Citizens Summit	Large-scale citizen summit (e.g., in Belgium), randomly inviting up to 1000 citizens for one or two days	Facilitated, stratified selection or voluntary, large-scale	Summaries of public preferences and priorities	G1000	Caluwaerts & Reuchamps 2015).
Deliberative Forum	A broad term for structured face-to-face or hybrid gatherings	Not necessarily facilitated, stratified selection, informal	Varied (recommendations, reports, ideas)	Also general term for 'mini-public'	Gastil 2008
Delphi Method	Iterative surveys/questionnaires—often with experts—feedback loops converge on consensus, F2F and/or Online	Not necessarily facilitated, stratified selection, informal	Consensus reports or ideas	Deliberative Pooling	Glass et al. 2022
Decision Focused Public Engagement Table (DPET)	Structured public discussions around specific decision-making challenges to facilitate targeted engagement (US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention) (~100 participants & 20-30	Facilitated, voluntary		Deliberative forums, consensus conferences	Bernier 2014

Format	Overview	Features	Output	Subtypes	References
	stakeholders) F2F				
Digital Democratic Innovation	DDI as VAAs help voters match their preferences with candidates or policies using questionnaires. Several types and can be citizen built as for Demokratiefabrik	Not facilitated, voluntary, structured participation	Personalized voter-policy marches	Demokratie fabrik.	Schultze, 2014, Gianola et al. 2024
Agora Ekklesia	Agora Ekklesia is a decision-making process designed to fulfil fundamental human needs within an assembly setting (~ 50-100)	Not necessarily facilitated, voluntary	Actionable resolutions	Public town halls and citizen assemblies.	Max-Neef, 1991
BarCamp	BarCamp is an international, participant-driven conference network focused on technology and the web, characterized by its open, collaborative, and user-generated format. (50-200 per event)	Self-organization and peer-led sessions, not facilitated, voluntary, informal	Shared knowledge, collaborative ideas	Hackathons and FoodCamps	Dennerline et al. 2013, Wiggins, 2007

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Format	Overview	Features	Output	Subtypes	References
Participatory Reflection and Action	Inclusive approach that collaborates with poor and marginalized communities, enabling them to utilize their knowledge, experience, and capabilities to analyze and address their own realities	Facilitated, voluntary	Locally relevant solutions	Participatory rural appraisal and action research	Fraser et al., 2016
Future Workshops	The process fosters democratic problem-solving by empowering marginalized or oppressed groups. It unfolds in three stages: critique, fantasize, and implementation. (20-50 per workshop)	Facilitated, appointed/elected, structured deliberative discussions	Action plans	Design thinking and strategic planning workshops	Schrot et al 2021, Jungk & Muellert, 1987
Online Deliberative Platforms	Digital platforms (asynchronous or synchronous) for geographically dispersed participants, high number of participants	Not necessarily facilitated, mainly voluntary stratified selection, informal and structured	Varied	Decidim, Polis. Rahvaalgatus.ee, VTaiwan, Helios	Coleman & Moss 2012

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Format	Overview	Features	Output	Subtypes	References
Online Citizens' Panel	Long-term online group convening repeatedly, possibly with rotating topics	Facilitated, stratified selection	Policy recommendations	Citizens panels	Davies & Chandler 2012
World Wide Views	Multi-site public consultation process designed to collect and report citizen opinions on critical issues, such as climate change.	Facilitated, stratified selection, structured formal deliberation	Global opinion reports		Goldsmith and Scheele 2016

2.4.5 Benefits of Deliberative Formats

Deliberative formats are anchored in core principles that seek to foster inclusiveness, equality, reasoned discussion, and authentic engagement. Most models weave together elements like random or stratified participant selection, expert input, team-building exercises, and professional facilitation to create democratic spaces that are not only fair but genuinely effective.

Inclusion and representation: Ensuring inclusion in deliberative practices typically relies on three key strategies: (i) participant selection, (ii) targeted local outreach, and (iii) scaling participation to accommodate larger groups.

i) The first approach emphasizes **inclusive selection methods**, often utilizing stratified random sampling. For instance, *Citizens' Assemblies* employ stratified random selection to reflect the demographic composition of society, ensuring that diverse perspectives are represented (Smith & Wales, 2000). This method amplifies the voices of underrepresented groups, creating a deliberative microcosm of the broader population.

By fostering inclusiveness, *Citizens' Assemblies* encourage balanced deliberation and equitable decision-making. Similarly, *Deliberative Polls* use random sampling to mitigate self-selection bias and achieve broad representation of societal viewpoints (Fishkin, 2009).

These polls invite participants from all walks of life, often providing incentives to encourage attendance and reduce participation barriers.

Expanding on this principle, *Planning Cells* involve multiple small groups working in parallel, synthesizing input from a wide range of participants to deepen inclusivity and engagement.

ii) The second approach focuses on **targeting local communities**, embedding democratic innovations as tools for community management. A prominent example is *Participatory Budgeting*, which actively promotes inclusiveness by prioritizing underrepresented areas and involving citizens in decisions about resource allocation. This approach ensures that marginalized voices are heard, allowing fiscal priorities to reflect diverse needs and fostering direct community engagement.

iii) The third approach involves **scaling deliberation** to larger formats to broaden inclusivity. Large-scale deliberative formats, such as the *21st Century Town Meeting* (Lukensmeyer & Bregham, 2002) and *Citizens' Summits*, rely on stratified random selection or open public invitations to engage participants from diverse demographic groups. These methods enhance the inclusivity of public consultations by enabling wide-ranging representation. Digital formats, including *E-Deliberation Platforms* and *Online Citizens' Panels*, further extend inclusiveness by leveraging technology to scale participation and overcome geographical barriers. By facilitating engagement regardless of physical constraints, these formats broaden participation and ensure accessibility for participants from diverse locations and backgrounds.

Through these approaches, deliberative practices integrate inclusiveness into participant selection, community engagement, and scalability, fostering richer, more equitable deliberations that reflect the diversity of society.

Reason-giving and Informed deliberation: In general, reason-giving is ensured through discourse-centric formats, where the exchange of reasons and dialogue take center stage in the deliberative process. While all the aforementioned democratic innovations emphasize these core elements, additional strategies are often employed to: i) Enhance the accuracy of reasons, which involves incorporating expert input, evidence-based resources, or fact-checking mechanisms to ensure that the arguments presented during deliberation are well-informed and grounded in reliable information. These strategies help participants build a shared understanding based on accurate and credible evidence. ii) Promote reason balance, which focuses on power-sharing in deliberative spaces to ensure that no single perspective or group dominates the discourse. Mechanisms such as skilled facilitation, equal speaking time, and structured dialogue frameworks are used to create a level playing field. These tools help balance the influence of participants, allowing for diverse viewpoints to be expressed and considered equitably.

i) In general, **reasons-accuracy** is balanced by expert briefings. Such briefings are a cornerstone of many formats, equipping participants with factual and diverse perspectives. *Citizens' Assemblies* and *Consensus Conferences* excel in this area, bringing in experts to present unbiased information, which participants use to deliberate complex issues.

ii) Deliberative processes often employ strategies to ensure **robust reason-giving**, supporting informed and balanced discussions. *Deliberative Polls* allow participants to refine their

opinions through structured interactions with subject matter experts. By integrating expert input into the deliberation process, participants are encouraged to engage critically with evidence, enhancing the quality and depth of their reasoning. The iterative nature of the *Delphi Method* further reinforces reason-giving by providing participants with repeated opportunities to review and justify their positions. Through a series of informed feedback loops, this process refines consensus while maintaining a focus on well-reasoned dialogue. *Future Workshops* emphasize creativity and critical thinking by encouraging participants to analyze current challenges, propose innovative solutions, and develop actionable plans.

In formats like *Citizens' Juries* and *Planning Cells*, small-group settings and skilled facilitation create an environment where participants can explore complex issues in depth. Group-building activities establish norms for respectful dialogue and foster trust and collaboration, which are essential for reason-giving. Facilitators play a key role in ensuring productive engagement and balanced contributions from all participants. By incorporating these mechanisms, deliberative formats cultivate a culture of reason-giving, ensuring that discussions remain informed, inclusive, and focused on generating actionable outcomes.

Equality and Balanced Participation: Equality and balanced participation are addressed through diverse and often mutually exclusive approaches, including i) skilled facilitation, ii) fostering a relaxed atmosphere, and iii) implementing structured processes.

i) **Skilled facilitation** is critical for ensuring equality in deliberative processes. Formats such as *Citizens' Assemblies*, *Citizens' Juries*, and *Deliberative Polls* depend on facilitators to create a level playing field where every participant has an equal opportunity to contribute. Facilitators actively manage discussions to prevent dominance, encourage quieter participants to share their views, and ensure balanced participation across diverse perspectives. Additionally, in formats like *Citizens' Juries* and *Consensus Conferences*, facilitation helps to create safe and respectful spaces where individuals can express their opinions openly and without fear of judgment. This emphasis on skilled facilitation supports authentic and inclusive dialogue, making sure that the deliberative process remains equitable and constructive.

ii) An **informal and welcoming atmosphere** plays a significant role in encouraging diverse input and preventing dominance.

World Café discussions exemplify this approach by fostering a casual setting where participants feel comfortable sharing their ideas freely.

iii) **Structured deliberative** processes ensure that equality and balanced participation are systematically embedded in the design. *Agora Ekklesia*, for example, incorporates private and group discussions that minimize external pressures, allowing participants to engage authentically. Transparent and repeated sessions, common in many deliberative formats, further enhance equality by clarifying procedures and providing participants with opportunities for deeper reflection and considered contributions.

Building Trust and Authenticity: Deliberative formats foster trust and authenticity through i) small and intimate atmospheres and ii) connections to tangible outcomes.

iv) Formats such as *Planning Cells* and *Citizens' Juries* build on **close interactions** in small groups to create trust and mutual respect among participants. Similarly, informal settings like World Café discussions and BarCamp events create relaxed environments that encourage open and creative engagement, allowing participants to feel comfortable expressing their perspectives authentically.

v) **Connection to Tangible Outcomes:** Formats like *Participatory Budgeting* and *Digital Democratic Innovations* enhance authenticity by linking deliberations directly to tangible, real-world decisions.

These approaches empower participants to see the immediate impact of their contributions, reinforcing the value of their involvement and strengthening trust in democratic institutions.

2.4.6 Common Drawbacks Across Formats

It is important to recognize the inherent tension between scaling deliberation to accommodate larger numbers of participants and maintaining the procedural elements — such as selection methods, facilitation, and group-building — that are essential for ensuring high-quality deliberation in standardized settings.

Representation vs. Depth: Large-scale deliberative events tend to be more inclusive, offering broader representation of diverse demographics. However, they often risk superficial engagement and limited trust-building. In contrast, smaller or repeated groups foster deeper trust and richer dialogue but may struggle to achieve representativeness (Smith, 2009), or produce spill-over effects beyond the meso level of the group (Van der Does & Jacquet, 2023).

Resource/Logistical Intensity: In-person deliberative processes can be resource-intensive, requiring significant investment in venues, facilitators, and participant logistics. Online methods, while potentially more scalable, require digital literacy, access to technology, and robust moderation to prevent dysfunction (Coleman & Moss, 2012). In addition, synchronous formats demand participants' availability at the same time, while asynchronous formats face challenges in maintaining momentum and continuity.

Facilitation Quality: Inadequate facilitation undermines equality, authenticity, and the overall quality of deliberation. Effective facilitation is particularly critical for ensuring balanced participation, managing power dynamics, and fostering constructive dialogue (Parkinson, 2003).

Structured deliberative process: The absence of a structured deliberative process, such as those used in *Citizens' Juries* or *Future Workshops*, increases the risk of deliberative pathologies. These include the spread of misinformation, emotional bias, and groupthink, which can compromise the legitimacy and outcomes of deliberation.

Dropout/Attrition: Sustained engagement is a challenge in both face-to-face and online settings. In-person formats that require participation over multiple weekends often

experience participant dropout, while online deliberations struggle with maintaining engagement due to competing priorities or lack of accountability.

Time Constraints: Many deliberative formats operate within short or one-off sessions, which limit opportunities for deeper reason-giving, relationship building, and iterative dialogue. These time constraints often lead to more surface-level engagement, reducing the transformative potential of deliberation (Mutz, 2006).

2.4.7 Empirical Testing vs. Other Evidence

- **Extensively Studied**
 - *Citizens' Assemblies, Deliberative Polls*, and some *Citizens' Juries* have robust comparative and case-study data (Farrell et al., 2019; Fishkin, 1997; Warren & Pearse, 2008)
 - *Participatory Budgeting* has broad international research, especially in Brazil and Europe (Sintomer et al., 2008).
 - *CIR* in Oregon shows measurable effects on voter knowledge (Gastil & Knobloch, 2019).
- **Moderately Studied**
 - *Consensus Conferences, Planning Cells*, and *large-scale events* (21st Century Town Meeting, G1000) have documented case studies but fewer standardized measures of deliberative quality (Caluwaerts & Reuchamps, 2015; Lukensmeyer & Bregham, 2002).
- **Less Uniform Evidence**
 - *Online Citizens' Panels, E-Deliberation*, have pilot data or smaller-scale evaluations; no consistent dataset across contexts (Coleman & Moss, 2012).
 - *World Café* are popular but rely on anecdotal or descriptive outcomes, with limited formal research (Brown, 2010).
- **Expert-Focused or Specialized**
 - *Delphi Method* is widely used in policy forecasting and corporate settings, but not always aligned with broad-based citizen deliberation (Glass & et al., 2022).

2.4.8 Conclusion

By matching specific design features (random/stratified selection, balanced materials, skilled facilitation, repeated or transparent sessions) to the four core principles (inclusiveness, equality, reason-giving, authenticity/mutual respect), these 20 formats strive to embody

deliberative ideals. Face-to-face methods often excel in deeper, trust-building discussion but can be resource-heavy and limited in scale.

Online or hybrid approaches potentially reach more participants but face digital divides and struggles with sustained engagement and reason-giving features. Little evidence on online processes exists in relation to the intrinsic deliberative quality of the process. Ultimately, the trade-offs between inclusiveness and depth, or between cost and authenticity, underscore the importance of carefully adapting each format to its context and objectives.

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2.5 Digital solutions for democratic deliberation

Digital platforms for deliberation have emerged as essential tools for participatory decision-making, enabling structured and inclusive dialogue at scale. These platforms provide mechanisms for individuals, groups, and organizations to discuss, debate, and make decisions collaboratively in digital spaces. With the increasing complexity of societal challenges and the need for diverse input, these tools bridge the gap between participation and decision-making, offering new avenues for democratic engagement.

A “deliberation platform” can be defined as a digital environment that facilitates collaborative decision-making or problem-solving processes amongst stakeholders. The purpose of this platform is to support deliberative practices, such as structured debates, voting mechanisms, data visualisation, real-time discussions, and analytics. The term ‘platform’ in this context is synonymous with ‘software systems’, focusing on project websites and specific systems that offer features such as interactivity with the visitor, access to relevant information on the topic, and tools to enhance user engagement. The emphasis on ‘platform’ highlights its role as a participatory environment as opposed to a static information repository, as it enables active involvement from stakeholders.

The evolution of these platforms reflects technological advances and shifts in societal expectations for inclusivity and transparency. Early platforms were often static and limited to basic forums or message boards. Today, platforms leverage sophisticated technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), to enable real-time discussions, visualize consensus, and support large-scale participation. These advancements allow for the integration of diverse voices while maintaining civility and focus in deliberations.

Digital deliberation platforms also vary widely in their objectives and designs. Some aim to foster open discussions and consensus-building, while others are tailored to decision-making within specific organizations or sectors. The versatility of these tools has made them invaluable in contexts ranging from governmental policy making and community planning to education and organizational governance.

In our research into the variety of platforms available for democratic deliberation, we identified a total of **51 platforms**, of which **12 explicitly discuss the use of AI** to enhance their functionality, while the remaining **39 rely on traditional approaches**. However, some platforms might incorporate AI without explicitly stating it, so we cannot be certain whether they utilize AI or not. For example, some platforms have a banned word filtering feature, which could potentially rely on AI for implementation. Similarly, other platforms may provide in-depth analysis, using AI for tasks like forecasting. For such platforms, it remains unclear if they leverage AI technologies.

Moreover, the global proliferation of digital communication technologies has fuelled the adoption of these platforms, especially in times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, when face-to-face interactions were limited (United Nations Division for Public Institutions and Digital Government, 2020).

Governments, nonprofits, and educational institutions have increasingly turned to these tools to engage stakeholders, collect input, and make informed decisions. As the demand for scalable and inclusive solutions grows, the role of AI in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of these platforms continues to expand.

This chapter explores existing platforms for deliberation—both AI-enabled and traditional—by analysing their design, functionalities, and user cases. By examining these tools, we aim to derive insights into their strengths, limitations, and implications for the development of future AI-enabled platforms that can meet the diverse needs of modern societies.

2.5.1 Approach

The logic behind our search and identification of platforms was based on using specific keywords, such as ‘deliberation’ and ‘democracy’, to locate relevant websites through search engines like Google Scholar and the EU platform.

Once we identified potential platforms, we analysed their features and purpose to determine whether they fit our predefined criteria, such as promoting deliberation and/or incorporating AI features.

As many platforms lack AI features, we also considered additional platforms that address deliberation and then examined the features in which they provide. In some cases, it was unclear whether AI was being used, as some platforms may include bots for monitoring language to prevent the use of discriminatory or offensive terms. After this analysis, a final selection was made based on the findings”

2.5.2 What software-systems are available for digital deliberation?

The landscape of digital deliberation platforms is vast and diverse, encompassing tools tailored to a variety of contexts and objectives. These platforms can broadly be categorized into three types:

- structured debate platforms,
- decision-making platforms, and
- large-scale discussion platforms.

Each category includes numerous examples, reflecting the rich variety of approaches to supporting deliberation.

Structured debate platforms such as *Kialo*,² *DebateGraph*,³ and *Consider.it*⁴ focus on organizing discussions into logical frameworks. Kialo structures debates into pro and con arguments, facilitating clarity and enabling users to explore different perspectives on complex issues. DebateGraph adds a visual layer, allowing participants to map arguments and understand the connections between ideas. Consider.it provides a collaborative interface to weigh the strengths of arguments, making it a valuable tool for analysing trade-offs and consensus-building.

Decision-making platforms such as *LiquidFeedback*,⁵ *Consul Democracy*,⁶ and *Adhocracy+*⁷ integrate deliberation with decision-making. LiquidFeedback, for instance, incorporates preference voting, enabling participants to express nuanced opinions beyond binary choices. Consul Democracy supports participatory budgeting and collaborative proposals, empowering citizens to influence policy-making directly. Similarly, Adhocracy+ enables organizations to manage stakeholder engagement through customizable workflows for idea collection and voting.

Large-scale discussion platforms include *Pol.is*,⁸ *Granicus*,⁹ and *CoUrbanize*,¹⁰ which emphasize inclusivity and scalability. Pol.is employs AI to cluster opinions and visualize consensus, making it particularly effective for synthesizing input from diverse audiences. Granicus provides tools for managing civic engagement initiatives, including public consultations and idea proposals. CoUrbanize, on the other hand, focuses on urban planning, connecting developers, municipalities, and residents to ensure that decision-making processes reflect community needs.

Additionally, platforms like *Your Priorities*,¹¹ and Granicus provide tools for **public consultations** and **participatory processes**. Open-source platforms such as *Decidim*¹² and *All Our Ideas*¹³ emphasize transparency and adaptability, allowing organizations to tailor the platforms to specific participatory goals. These examples illustrate the breadth of tools available to support deliberative practices across a wide range of applications.

A notable case study is the use of Pol.is by governments for **public policy discussions**. In Taiwan, Pol.is was used to engage citizens in deliberations on contentious issues such as ridesharing regulations. By clustering opinions and highlighting consensus points, the platform enabled policymakers to understand public sentiment and craft regulations that reflected the majority's preferences while addressing minority concerns.

² <https://www.kialo-edu.com/>

³ <https://debategraph.org>

⁴ <https://consider.it/>

⁵ <https://liquidfeedback.com/en/>

⁶ <https://consuldemocracy.org/>

⁷ <https://adhocracy.plus/>

⁸ <https://pol.is/home>

⁹ <https://granicus.com/>

¹⁰ <https://www.courbanize.com/>

¹¹ <https://www.yrpri.org/domain/3>

¹² <https://decidim.org/>

¹³ <https://all-our-ideas.citizens.is>

Similarly, LiquidFeedback has been employed by political parties, such as Germany's Pirate Party, to streamline **internal decision-making** processes. By integrating deliberation with voting, the platform facilitated transparent and democratic decision-making.

Another example is CoUrbanize, which has been widely used in **urban planning projects**. By integrating community feedback tools and interactive maps, CoUrbanize helps developers and municipalities collect real-time input from residents. This has allowed urban planning projects to address citizen concerns, improve transparency, and ensure alignment with community needs.

Table 8: Existing Digital Deliberation Platforms

Name	URL	Source
Stanford Online Deliberation Platform	https://deliberation.stanford.edu/tools-and-resources/online-deliberation-platform	(Fishkin et al., 2019; Gelauff et al., 2023, 2024)
Pol.is	https://pol.is/home	
Kialo	https://www.kialo-edu.com	(Mei et al., 2024)
LiquidFeedback	https://liquidfeedback.com/en	(Behrens et al., 2014; Grossi et al., 2024)
DebateGraph	https://debategraph.org	
Thinkscape	https://www.thinkscape.ai	
All Our Ideas	https://all-our-ideas.citizens.is	(Salganik & Levy, 2015)
Deliberative Democracy Lab	https://deliberation.stanford.edu/?utm_source=chatgpt.com	
The NUS Online Deliberation platform	https://civictechlab.org/projects/online-deliberation	(Perrault & Zhang, 2016)
Granicus	https://granicus.com	

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Name	URL	Source
Adhocracy+	https://adhocracy.plus	
Ask Parliament by Democracy Developers	https://www.democracydevelopers.org.au/app	
Assembl	https://www.bluenove.com/en/offers/assembl	
Consider.it	https://consider.it	
Consul Democracy	https://consuldemocracy.org	
ConsultVox	https://www.consultvox.co	
CoUrbanize	https://www.courbanize.com	
Democraciaos	https://democraciaos.org	
Decidim	https://decidim.org	(Barandiaran et al., 2024)
Decision21	https://www.decision21.com	
Dialogue	https://www.delib.net/dialogue	
Discuto	https://www.discuto.io/en	(Delib, 2024)
Ethelo	https://www.ethelo.com	
Fluicity	https://get.flui.city/en	
Loomio	https://www.loomio.com	
Make.org	https://make.org/GR	

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Name	URL	Source
OpenStad	https://openstad.org	
Purpoz	https://purpoz.com	
Your Priorities	https://www.yrpri.org/domain/3	
Parlay	https://parlayideas.com	
SocialAI	https://www.socialai.finance	
dembrane	https://www.dembrane.com/en-US	
76 Engage	https://76engage.com	(76 Engage, 2018)
Cap Collectif	https://www.cap-collectif.com	
Citizen OS	https://citizenos.com	
Civocracy	https://www.civocracy.com	
Cobudget	https://cobudget.com	
Cocoriko	https://www.cocoriko.org/en	
Delib	https://www.delib.net	
Efalia Engage	https://www.efalia.com/en/module-efalia-engage	
Go Vocal	https://www.govocal.com	

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Name	URL	Source
Konveio	https://www.konveio.com	
Munipolis	https://info.munipolis.com	
Social Pinpoint	https://www.socialpinpoint.com	
Deliberations.US	https://www.deliberations.us	
Crowdpolicy	https://www.crowdpolicy.com/en	
Real Deal	https://www.realdeal.eu	
EuComMeet	https://www.eucommeet.eu	

2.5.3 What deliberative formats do these systems support?

The formats and types of deliberation supported by these platforms vary widely, reflecting their diverse goals and target audiences. Platforms such as LiquidFeedback, Consul Democracy, and Adhocracy+ focus on **integrating deliberation with direct voting**, allowing participants to collaboratively refine and decide on proposals. These platforms often combine discussion forums with voting systems, ensuring that decisions are informed by inclusive deliberation.

Web-based platforms like Pol.is and Granicus **facilitate asynchronous group discussions**, leveraging AI to identify consensus points and organize input from large numbers of participants. CoUrbanize similarly supports asynchronous engagement, but with a focus on urban planning, enabling stakeholders to provide feedback on development projects.

Platforms designed for **synchronous interaction** include the *Stanford Online Deliberation Platform*¹⁴ and *Deliberations.US*,¹⁵ which support real-time video discussions. The Stanford Online Deliberation Platform features automated moderation to ensure **equitable participation**, while Deliberations.US provides tools for **balanced and fact-based group**

¹⁴ <https://deliberation.stanford.edu/tools-and-resources/online-deliberation-platform>

¹⁵ <https://www.deliberations.us/>

discussions. These platforms are particularly suited for educational and experimental settings where live interaction is critical.

Other platforms emphasize **structured workflows.** For example, Decidim integrates forums, proposal drafting, and voting into comprehensive participatory processes. Platforms like Your Priorities and All Our Ideas emphasize simplicity, offering tools for idea collection and voting to engage grassroots movements and communities with limited technical expertise.

The inclusion of AI **moderation tools** on platforms such as *Thinkscope*¹⁶ and Pol.is ensures that discussions remain civil and productive. These tools automate processes such as clustering similar opinions, flagging inappropriate content, and generating summaries, enhancing the scalability and efficiency of deliberation. Thinkscope, for example, divides participants into smaller "ThinkTanks" using Swarm AI technology, enabling more focused and productive discussions. By offering diverse formats and levels of interaction, these platforms cater to a wide array of deliberative needs, from grassroots activism to institutional policymaking.

2.5.4 What affordances do these systems provide?

The specific affordances of deliberation platforms highlight their strengths and suitability for various applications. AI-driven platforms like Pol.is, Thinkscope, and CoUrbanize stand out for their ability to **synthesize large-scale input** through tools such as opinion clustering, real-time summaries, and sentiment analysis. These features are particularly valuable for governments and organizations seeking actionable insights from diverse stakeholders.

Structured debate platforms such as *DebateGraph*,¹⁷ Consider.it, and Kialo provide tools to **map and evaluate arguments** systematically. DebateGraph excels in visualizing complex debates, making it a valuable resource for educators and policymakers. Consider.it emphasizes transparency by allowing participants to visualize the distribution of opinions, enabling more informed decision-making processes.

Decision-making platforms such as LiquidFeedback and Consul Democracy emphasize workflows that **integrate deliberation and voting.** LiquidFeedback supports preference voting, enabling participants to indicate their level of agreement with proposals. Consul Democracy includes tools for participatory budgeting, proposal management, and citizen voting, offering a comprehensive suite for collaborative governance.

Platforms like Your Priorities and Adhocracy+ focus on **accessibility** and **adaptability**, providing simple interfaces that empower underrepresented communities to participate in decision-making. Customizable workflows, open-source designs, and free access ensure that these platforms can be tailored to meet specific needs. By combining features such as equitable speaking time, consensus visualization, and participatory voting, these platforms provide robust frameworks for deliberation.

¹⁶ <https://www.thinkscope.ai>

¹⁷ <https://debategraph.org>

Another notable example is Granicus, which offers tools for **public engagement** and **decision-making processes**.

Its focus on communication management and citizen feedback has made it a preferred platform for government agencies and public sector organizations. By enabling streamlined communication with stakeholders, Granicus enhances transparency and trust in public decision-making.

2.5.5 Who is providing these software systems?

The providers of deliberation platforms reflect a diverse ecosystem that includes academic institutions, private companies, and open-source communities:

Academic contributions, such as the Stanford Online Deliberation Platform and *Deliberative Democracy Lab*,¹⁸ emphasize research-driven innovation and experimental design. These platforms are often used in educational and research contexts to explore new methods of structured deliberation.

Private companies, including Granicus, CoUrbanize, and 76 Engage,¹⁹ focus on delivering scalable solutions for governments and organizations. Their platforms often integrate advanced features such as AI-driven analytics and real-time feedback tools, enabling users to manage complex deliberative processes efficiently.

Open-source initiatives, such as Decidim, Your Priorities, and Adhocracy+, prioritize transparency and community-driven development. These platforms are maintained by collaborative communities and nonprofit organizations, reflecting a commitment to participatory values. Platforms like LiquidFeedback, supported by civic groups, exemplify how open-source tools can empower citizens to influence decision-making directly.

The diverse origins of these platforms highlight the broad interest in digital deliberation across sectors. Academic institutions contribute rigor and experimental insights, private companies bring usability and innovation, and open-source communities ensure adaptability and inclusivity. Together, these efforts foster an ecosystem where platforms evolve to meet the changing needs of society.

2.5.6 Where is democratic deliberation used and for what purpose?

The user base of deliberation platforms spans governments, educational institutions, organizations, and communities:

Governments frequently use platforms such as Consul Democracy, Decidim, and Granicus for participatory policymaking and civic engagement. These platforms enable policymakers to gather input from diverse stakeholders, fostering transparency and trust in governance.

¹⁸ https://deliberation.stanford.edu/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

¹⁹ <https://76engage.com/>

Educational institutions leverage platforms like Kialo, DebateGraph, and Stanford Online Deliberation Platform to engage students in structured debates and collaborative problem-solving. These tools help cultivate critical thinking and analytical skills, making them valuable in academic settings.

Corporate and nonprofit organizations employ platforms such as Granicus for stakeholder consultations and collaborative decision-making. CoUrbanize is widely used in urban planning projects to engage residents and ensure that development decisions reflect community needs. Similarly, Adhocracy+ supports organizations in managing stakeholder input for strategic planning and governance.

Community-driven platforms, such as Your Priorities and All Our Ideas, empower grassroots movements by providing tools for idea proposals and voting. These platforms are designed to amplify underrepresented voices, enabling communities to influence policies and initiatives directly. For example, Your Priorities has successfully engaged citizens in local decision-making processes, demonstrating its value in fostering democratic participation.

2.5.7 What evidence-based evaluations are available?

Evidence-based evaluations of deliberation platforms remain limited, with many platforms relying on case studies and user testimonials to demonstrate their impact. Platforms such as Pol.is and Granicus have documented use cases in global governmental projects, showcasing their effectiveness in fostering inclusivity and consensus-building. Similarly, LiquidFeedback and Decidim have been widely adopted by political organizations and municipalities, reflecting their utility in real-world applications.

Educational platforms like Kialo and DebateGraph are frequently cited in academic literature for their contributions to structured discourse and critical thinking. While formal evaluations are sparse, these platforms' widespread adoption underscores their practical value. The growing interest in digital deliberation presents an opportunity for researchers and developers to conduct systematic studies and refine these tools further.

2.5.8 Conclusion

From the analysis of existing platforms, several key insights emerge. **Scalability and inclusivity** are critical challenges that AI-enabled platforms, such as Pol.is and Thinkscape, address effectively by clustering opinions and synthesizing inputs. These features demonstrate the potential of AI to manage large-scale participation without compromising deliberative quality.

Feature integration is another strength of platforms like Consul Democracy and LiquidFeedback, which combine deliberation with decision-making workflows.

The incorporation of AI tools into these processes can further enhance efficiency by automating routine tasks, such as summarization and sentiment analysis, while providing actionable insights.

User-centric design is crucial for fostering engagement, as demonstrated by platforms like Granicus and Your Priorities. By offering intuitive interfaces and accessible workflows, these platforms ensure that diverse voices are included in decision-making processes.

Future AI-enabled platforms should build on these strengths by incorporating advanced analytics, natural language processing, and real-time feedback mechanisms.

AI's role in **moderating discussions** and ensuring civility is particularly significant (Molina & Sundar, 2022). Platforms that use AI for automated moderation, equitable speaking time, and opinion clustering showcase the potential for technology to create more inclusive and productive deliberative spaces. For example, Thinkscape leverages Swarm AI technology to divide participants into smaller groups and amplify collective intelligence. These capabilities illustrate how AI can facilitate deeper and more meaningful discussions.

By synthesizing the strengths of existing platforms while addressing their limitations, future AI-enabled tools can transform digital deliberation into a more scalable, inclusive, and impactful process. These advancements will enable societies to navigate increasingly complex decisions with greater participation and effectiveness. Challenges such as data privacy concerns, algorithmic biases, and digital literacy barriers must also be addressed to ensure equitable access and trust in these technologies. Privacy-enhancing technologies, transparent algorithms, and widespread digital literacy programs will be critical in overcoming these barriers and maximizing the potential of deliberation platforms.

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2.6 Artificial Intelligence features for democratic deliberation

Artificial intelligence (AI), especially Large Language Models (LLMs), are emerging as potential tools to address challenges and enhance the quality of public deliberations. This chapter seeks to synthesize current research about AI features that can be used to enhance deliberations. The questions that we aim to tackle are:

- Q1: Are there specific AI use cases for deliberation proposed (speculative, conceptual)?
- Q2: Are there specific AI use cases for deliberation discussed (specific examples)?
- Q3: What are the specific affordances of AI for deliberation?
- Q4: What are specific risks of AI for deliberation?

2.6.1 Approach

This systematic literature review followed PRISMA guidelines and employed a multi-stage process to synthesize research on AI's application in public deliberation. A comprehensive search was conducted across six databases, including

- *ACM Digital Library*,
- *arXiv*,
- *Google Scholar*,
- *ResearchGate*,
- *Scopus*, and
- *Web of Science*.

The search involved various combinations of keywords, such as

- AI,
- deliberation,
- decision-making,
- democratic values,
- citizen participation,
- large language models (LLMs),
- natural language processing (NLP),
- deliberative technologies,

- machine learning,
- civic participation,
- digital democracy, and
- text summarization.

From each database, we selected to review the top-100 studies. For some databases less than 100 results were returned based on the search. In this case, all the returned results were kept for the analysis. In summary, this process yielded 387 records. After removing 2 duplicates and excluding 30 records for other reasons, 355 records were screened based on title and abstract relevance. During this process, 148 records were excluded.

The remaining 207 reports were retrieved and assessed for eligibility, of which 177 were excluded for being too general or off-topic. This resulted in the final inclusion of 30 studies. Data from these 30 studies were extracted, analyzed, and synthesized to explore AI features, benefits, and challenges in deliberative processes.

Figure 3: PRISMA Documentation Chapter 6

2.6.2 Results

In a nutshell, the collected articles explore a wide range of functionalities for AI in democratic processes, from theoretical frameworks to practical applications.

Some articles investigate how AI can transform citizen participation (Formosa et al., 2024) and whether LLMs can truly advance democratic values (Lazar & Manuali, 2024). Others focus on the use of LLMs to improve online deliberation platforms (C. Small, 2024), including assessing the quality of contributions (Gelauff et al., 2024), and generating consensus statements (Bakker et al., 2022; Konya et al., 2023).

Several articles discuss AI-powered moderation and facilitation of online discussions (Fishkin et al., 2019) and the potential of AI to bring deliberative democracy to a wider audience (Landemore, 2024). The functionalities also include using AI to support better decision-making (A. Zhang et al., 2023), improve fact-checking (Giarelis et al., 2024) and improve citizen participation in governmental processes (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Balta et al., 2019; *Leveraging AI for Democracy*, 2024).

Furthermore, some articles explore how AI can make democratic processes more accessible (Saggion, n.d.), address the challenge of harmful content in online groups (D. Agarwal et al., 2024) and support the design of better digital participation platforms (Borchers et al., 2024). Finally, other papers explore the implementation of AI within citizen assemblies (McKinney, 2024) and the use of AI in the generation of data to improve applications for democratic participation (Wagner et al., 2024).

The following sections present:

1. the underlying democratic values for using AI in deliberations,
2. the AI features to augment/facilitate deliberative processes, and
3. risks of AI in deliberation.

2.6.3 Foundational Values for using AI in Deliberation

As a result of the analysis we identified some main democratic values that aim to be achieved by incorporating AI features in deliberative settings. These values are the goal for integrating AI features in existing deliberative settings.

- **Preserving Agency and Autonomy:** A fundamental principle in democratic practices involves enabling people to express their choices in the construction of the future of their societies; as such it is important to focus on approaches where citizens participate meaningfully, with systems augmenting but not curtailing that agency (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019; Giarelis et al., 2024; Tsai et al., 2024).
- **Encouraging Mutual Respect:** Any robust model of democracy relies upon mutual understanding (e.g., listening to opposing ideas and arguments and presenting rationales for particular proposals). In a context such as online deliberations, care should be taken to promote and enable understanding and tolerance among participants (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019).

- **Promoting Equality and Inclusiveness:** Enable people who often do not take part in deliberations to do so. This can be achieved by allowing participation to be both open and equitable, including groups previously often marginalised, whether by geographic, economic, educational, health or ability-based considerations (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; J. Davies et al., 2021; Mikhaylovskaya, 2024).

2.6.4 AI features to augment/facilitate deliberative processes

AI and LLMs have various capabilities, which can be applied to various parts of the deliberation pipeline, offering new opportunities for a technology-enhanced deliberative model which aims to maximize participation and thoughtful consideration. These capabilities include:

- **Facilitation:** The complex nature of some of today's problems (e.g., the environment or healthcare) often involves complex conversations and exchanges; in such settings facilitation, moderation or other guidance become increasingly crucial for better outputs and fairer participation, often managed through a facilitator (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019). A variety of applications here show how to help with a more effective deliberative environment
 - **Automated Moderator:** AI/LLMs can serve as a moderator which regulates turn-taking during online discussions to encourage more equitable participation and reduce bias by any few 'louder' participants (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019).
 - **Speaking Queue Enforcement (Video Deliberation):** AI can also aid a structured speaking queue to avoid biases, so users can be guaranteed speaking time while helping organize the deliberations and avoid the common scenario where one participant overtakes the conversation by constantly chiming in, thereby limiting exposure of opinions in groups (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019).
 - **Combating Harmful Content:** AI can facilitate asynchronous deliberation by detecting potentially harmful content. This feature can, for example, limit the spread of misinformation, acting as a complement to traditional fact-checking and moderation methods (D. Agarwal et al., 2024).
 - **Detecting toxic behavior:** Similar to the above (Combating Harmful Content) but for synchronous (live) deliberations. In this case, AI, for example, may block a user (Fishkin et al., 2019).
 - **Identify stalls in live conversations:** In this case AI may advance the agenda to the next item (Fishkin et al., 2019).

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- **Processing of Data and Information:** The large-scale content that can be generated through deliberations requires processing in order to provide useful insights. In that respect, AI, with different features has been tested across several frameworks.
 - **Summarizing Information:** AI can support the automatic production of informative summaries and reports. Such techniques have value by automatically transforming large amounts of unstructured data into short summaries for citizens or policy-makers (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Chowanda et al., 2017; Giarelis et al., n.d.; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
 - **Simplifying information:** AI/LLMs can take complex human language and simplify it. In (Y. Feng et al., 2023) authors found that LLMs were as effective as human annotators in simplifying sentences.
 - **Topic Modelling:** AI/LLMs and associated techniques can facilitate clustering similar points and identifying key topics that are part of the discussions.

This allows a quicker path for comprehension and to focus on crucial aspects that have emerged during deliberation, giving a more solid picture of discussions (Chowanda et al., 2017; Giarelis et al., n.d.; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
 - **Clustering and organizing arguments:** AI could help cluster arguments in an organized way so that the intersecting contributions of large amounts of people can actually be reduced to a manageable amount of content. This could be done in real time to help move the deliberation forward or afterwards to make sense of a large amount of data produced (Anastasiou, 2023; Landemore, 2024).
- **Engagement with Content:** Beyond merely providing a system to analyse content, AI provides features to more meaningfully engage and assess input.
 - **Fact-checking:** A combination of AI techniques can identify and address factuality, providing verifiable information while also allowing counterpoints to emerge and get presented (Giarelis et al., n.d.; Karacapilidis et al., n.d.; Špecián, 2024).
 - **Entity/relation Extraction:** The ability to structure unstructured text by detecting underlying entities/relations. For example, identify specific government departments (Giarelis et al., n.d.).
 - **Real-Time Translation:** To connect participants with different language bases, the AI can facilitate seamless transitions between languages by presenting output in desired languages or having translation models actively moderate conversations, thus bringing forth cross-cultural communication and inclusion (Konya et al., 2023; C. T. Small et al., 2023).

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- **Visualization:** AI generated output may come with options to show and plot data, agreements and disagreement areas on charts (e.g., mapping of the discussions to display patterns or visual data of users opinions over an argument); helping members discern areas of disagreement that need to be explored (C. T. Small et al., 2023).
- **Acting as question and answer systems:** AI/LLMs can be used as question and answer systems providing information to participants on demand. This, for example, means that LLMs could be available at any time to support participant learning when relevant experts are not present (McKinney, 2024).
- **Participation Focused Approaches:** In enhancing participation and inclusiveness, there are a multitude of features where AI may have a significant effect.
 - **Consensus building:** Based on AI-assisted analysis of individual statements, the system can surface potential points to align on with other members as well as novel suggestions to make decisions in alignment with citizen input, all with an aim towards consensus. It is based on the LLM abilities to recommend novel approaches to reach a wider consent or acceptance, e.g. assist groups that struggle in consensus formation via offering them routes or areas to bridge disagreement or make progress (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Ding & Ito, 2023; C. T. Small et al., 2023; Tessler et al., 2024).
 - **Generating Groups:** Based on various insights (including specific opinions shared, backgrounds, stated preference in past engagements), AI models may enable identification of groups based on different characteristics (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
 - **Comment Routing:** The complex nature of a public online deliberation generates many comment (comments) that cannot easily be processed by humans. To enable for all views to be properly and equitably considered in deliberation the use of AI to actively "route" appropriate responses to the "best fit" person within deliberation could maximize impact while reducing time cost and complexity for individual users (Fishkin et al., 2019; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
 - **Identifying High-Potential Ideas:** Through various patterns and AI-techniques, one might detect 'viral' or insightful information/ideas that gain the interest of multiple users. Those ideas can be promoted, thereby reducing the risk that valuable ideas get passed over by too narrow of dissemination within limited communities (C. T. Small et al., 2023).
 - **Assisting with question generation:** Participants of deliberations may feel like passive students rather than active collaborators. AI can assist participants to formulate questions or assist in generating ideas verified by staff in order to challenge speakers. Afterwards, participants can engage and

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build upon these suggestions, thereby deepening the interaction and fostering a more inclusive and robust dialogue (McKinney, 2024).

- **Monitor deliberative quality:** The potential of AI to analyze deliberation content in real-time can facilitate the monitoring of the deliberative quality. AI models trained on assessing metrics of deliberative quality could provide invaluable feedback to facilitators. For example, AI could identify and highlight instances that either promote or hinder constructive dialogue. This live-time analysis empowers facilitators to address shortcomings as they emerge, leading to richer and more effective deliberative processes (McKinney, 2024).
- **Playing devil's advocate:** Large Language Models (LLMs) have the potential to enhance the quality of deliberation outputs by acting as a devil's advocate, a role often played by humans.

By generating objections and challenging emerging consensus, LLMs can mitigate the risk of groupthink and promote more critically considered judgments. However, caution is crucial, as this role carries the risk of pushing specific perspectives. To avoid this, AI-generated content should be framed as open-ended questions, ensuring it prompts participants to consider different angles without directing their opinions, thereby fostering a more robust and balanced deliberation (McKinney, 2024).

- **Aggregating across deliberation:** Synthesizing vast amounts of qualitative data from multiple deliberation groups is a significant challenge for deliberations, limiting their scalability and the ability to meaningfully integrate diverse perspectives. While LLMs offer a promising solution by efficiently clustering viewpoints and identifying key agreements and disagreements, the application of AI in this context must be approached critically. The act of synthesis is crucial for making meaning, and AI systems could introduce errors or biases if not carefully managed. To mitigate these issues, AI aggregation systems must be fine-tuned, and human oversight must be maintained, particularly through presenting AI-generated outputs to participants for feedback and correction (McKinney, 2024).
- **Support effective communication:** AI/LLMs can significantly enhance communication with the wider public during the follow-up phase, where the outcomes of the deliberation are shared with relevant actors. They enable a shift from a uniform communication strategy to one that is more personalized and tailored to the needs of various groups. For example, LLMs can create different text versions to engage specific audiences, such as those segmented by age or political orientation (McKinney, 2024).

A more concise version of the above AI functionalities:

Table 9: AI Functionalities in the Context of Deliberation Mentioned by Literature

Category	AI functionality	Description
Facilitation	1. Automated Moderation	Manages turn-taking to ensure more equitable participation, preventing domination by individuals. (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019)
	2. Speaking Queue Enforcement	Guarantees speaking time for all participants, organizing deliberations, and preventing one person from taking over the conversation (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019).
	3. Combat Harmful Content	Facilitate asynchronous deliberation by detecting potentially harmful content (D. Agarwal et al., 2024).
	4. Detect toxic behavior	Similar to the above (Combating Harmful Content) but for synchronous (live) deliberations (Fishkin et al., 2019).
	5. Identify stalls in live conversations	In this case, AI may advance the agenda to the next item (Fishkin et al., 2019).
Processing of Data and Information	6. Summarizing Information	AI can support the automatic production of informative summaries and reports (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Chowanda et al., 2017; Giarelis et al., n.d.; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
	7. Simplifying information	AI/LLMs can take complex human language and simplify it (Y. Feng et al., 2023).
	8. Topic Modelling	Clusters similar points and identifies key categories in discussions, aiding comprehension and focusing on essential aspects (Chowanda et al., 2017; Giarelis et al., n.d.; C. T. Small et al., 2023).

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Category	AI functionality	Description
	9. Clustering and organizing arguments	AI could help cluster arguments in an organized way so that the intersecting contributions of large amounts of people can actually be reduced to a manageable amount of content (Landemore, 2024).
Engagement with Content	10. Fact-checking	Identifies and addresses factuality, providing verified information and allowing for counterpoints to emerge and get presented. (Giarelis et al., n.d.; Karacapilidis et al., n.d.; Špecián, 2024).
	11. Entity Extraction	Structure unstructured text by detecting underlying entities/relations (Giarelis et al., n.d.).
	12. Real-Time Translation	Enables real-time communication among participants speaking different languages via automated translation (Konya et al., 2023; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
	13. Visualization	Displays data and patterns of opinions via visuals, helping participants identify areas for discussion and address disagreements (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Fishkin et al., 2019).
	14. Acting as question and answer system	AI/LLMs can be used as question and answer systems, providing information to participants on demand (McKinney, 2024).
Participation Focused Approaches	15. Consensus building	Proposes suggestions and ways for users to align on common ground and bridges disagreements to move toward consensus (Arana-Catania et al., 2021; Ding & Ito, 2023; C. T. Small et al., 2023; Tessler et al., 2024).
	16. Generating Groups	Identifies groups based on various characteristics, potentially revealing hidden

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Category	AI functionality	Description
		power dynamics(Arana-Catania et al., 2021; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
	17. Comment Routing	Ensures all views are considered by sending comments to the appropriate individual within the deliberation, maximizing impact and reducing time cost (Fishkin et al., 2019; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
	18. Identifying High-Potential Ideas	Highlight/promote 'viral' or insightful information/ideas that gain the interest of multiple users (C. T. Small et al., 2023).
	19. Assisting with question generation	AI can assist participants to formulate questions or assist in generating ideas verified by staff in order to challenge speakers (McKinney, 2024).
	20. Measuring deliberative quality	AI can analyze deliberation in real-time, providing feedback to facilitators to improve discussion quality and inclusivity (McKinney, 2024).
	21. Playing devil's advocate	AI/LLMs can act as devil's advocates by challenging consensus and fostering critical thinking (must be used carefully with open-ended questions to avoid bias) (McKinney, 2024).
	22. Aggregating across deliberation	AI/LLMs can synthesize large amounts of deliberation data from multiple deliberation groups (McKinney, 2024).
	23. Support effective communication	AI/LLMs can significantly enhance communication with the wider public during the follow-up phase, where the outcomes of the deliberation are shared with relevant actors (McKinney, 2024).

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All the above 23 AI functionalities are language-specific since they require processing of either written text or voice/video in specific languages. For example, the summarization of information in Greek vs English requires either different AI models or cross-lingual adaptation or fine-tuning. In the frame of the AI4Deliberation project, four different pilots in four languages (English, Greek, Italian and German) will be developed. Thus, 92 (23x4) language-specific AI functionalities need to be considered.

2.6.5 Risk of AI in deliberation

Having seen several AI tools and modes that show positive value for use in deliberation, there are numerous downsides, which stem directly from either their architecture as complex models or issues in their deployment. As such, in incorporating new AI technologies, certain aspects warrant consideration and special attention:

- **Bias:** AI systems can and often exhibit bias in their decision outputs, which results in some sections of society being excluded (e.g. with ethnic minorities or individuals of different backgrounds and class in particular often underserved by models trained on highly homogenous data), or some proposals prioritized over other, more valid proposals. It's therefore vital that systems use proper techniques including, for instance, using AI that reflects public preferences rather than just those who have previously controlled systems (Konya et al., 2023), data-sampling methods or explicit algorithmic corrections to minimise the effect that this bias may create.
- **'Hallucination':** Another downside of relying solely on an AI is the 'hallucination' effect that results in outputs based on insufficient fact bases, which could harm participants that rely on them, producing answers not directly based on reality. A careful mapping between expert and lay opinion as part of deliberation would help reveal which approaches are necessary to handle instances where AI cannot fully and effectively synthesize complex reasoning tasks to deliver responses and also require oversight of any claims to reduce misreporting or faulty output based on low grade training materials (Giarelis et al., n.d.; C. T. Small et al., 2023).
- **Substitution vs Augmentation:** A risk that arises is related to the use of AI as a substitution mechanism; doing everything for the users which, though potentially reducing efforts of individuals, has a tendency to bypass several aspects that are core to quality deliberation (C. T. Small et al., 2023). The augmentation approach, by contrast, enables a co-creation space between machine learning and humans that is superior, as well as allows greater individual autonomy. The primary challenge moving forward will be in enabling that augmentation aspect instead of complete automation in LLM-based democratic models. Thereby, engaging participants by providing deeper insights and not treating them as passive recipients of the results.
- **Loss of Context and Human Connection:** It's important to stress how many elements are lost if the AI-supported methods lack human-driven factors. These missing pieces may have key negative outcomes for participation. Human moderators contribute

with non-verbal and embodied modes which include, crucially tone of voice, a sense of appropriate body language, empathy, rapport building; therefore an approach only built on automated models and tools must have limitations due to the loss of certain modes of expressions (such as body language) and will risk reducing meaningful, well intentioned engagement to simply another algorithmic step (Guridi et al., 2024; Špecián, 2024).

2.6.6 Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the 30 papers, 23 unique AI functionalities were identified. Some of the papers actually implement the functionality in practice, while others propose its uses in theory. The following table includes the number of papers that have implemented each AI functionality and the number of papers that have proposed the use of each functionality. For example, 4 papers have implemented “Summarizing Information”, while 11 papers propose its use. Based on these two numbers, we have calculated a maturity score giving more emphasis on the number of implementations as: $2 \times \text{\#papers_implement} + \text{\#papers_propose}$.

Based on this score, the “Summarizing Information” is the more mature AI feature, followed by “Automated Moderation”, “Topic Modelling”, “Clustering and organizing arguments”, “Real-Time Translation”, “Consensus building”, “Fact-checking” and “Entity Extraction”. The most mature AI features could be prioritized in the first implementation rounds of the project.

Table 10: Maturity Analysis Results

AI functionality	#papers implement	#papers propose	Maturity score
Summarizing Information	4	11	19
Automated Moderation	2	3	7
Topic Modelling	3	1	7
Clustering and organizing arguments	1	5	7
Real-Time Translation	1	5	7
Consensus building	3	1	7
Fact-checking	2	1	5
Entity Extraction	1	3	5
Simplifying information	1	1	3
Assisting with question generation	0	3	3
Measuring deliberative quality	1	1	3
Speaking Queue Enforcement	1	0	2
Combat Harmful Content	1	0	2
Detect toxic behavior	1	0	2
Identify stalls in live conversations	1	0	2
Visualization	0	2	2

AI functionality	#papers implement	#papers propose	Maturity score
Generating Groups	1	0	2
Comment Routing	1	0	2
Identifying High-Potential Ideas	1	0	2
Support effective communication	0	2	2
Acting as question and answer system	0	1	1
Playing devil's advocate	0	1	1
Aggregating across deliberation	0	1	1

AI applications in deliberative processes represent both novel potentials but also very serious risks. However, many issues pertaining to it can and should be directly addressed at a practical level. AI should be used carefully, ensuring the preservation of autonomy of participation while using AI and balancing the need for human and AI interaction in the various modes (such as moderation, reporting and translations, among other elements of the deliberation model).

The question of which aspects should remain human-led, and what would be better tackled via AI is one which should be addressed in order to enable more effective deliberations. The hope for using AI as powerful augmenting rather than automating tools remains a crucial value towards this direction.

2.7 Spotlight: Argument mining

As online platforms increasingly become the primary venues for deliberation and debate, the ability to process and analyse these vast troves of conversational data has grown in importance. However, while remarkable success has been achieved in natural language processing tasks such as sentiment analysis and opinion mining, these techniques fall short of giving a full and nuanced picture of a debate, being limited to identifying what opinions are expressed while offering little insight into why those opinions are held or the reasoning behind them.

This gap in understanding is where argumentation theory and its computational counterpart, argument mining, come into play. Argumentation theory—a multidisciplinary field spanning philosophy, linguistics, cognitive science, and computer science—studies the structure, formation, and evaluation of arguments. Central to this field is the concept of reasoning: arguments consist of claims supported or opposed by reasons. Argument mining aims to automate the identification and structuring of these components within unstructured natural language text, transforming vast datasets into structured, actionable insights. This deeper understanding is particularly valuable in contexts requiring critical deliberation, such as policymaking, ethical debates, or collaborative problem-solving.

In the realm of AI and online deliberation, argument mining is poised to play a transformative role. Online discussions, whether in forums, social media, or collaborative platforms, are often fragmented and overwhelming in volume. Argument mining offers a pathway to systematically extract key arguments, analyse their interconnections, and identify dominant themes or contentious points. This not only aids human comprehension but also enables AI systems to participate in deliberative processes by providing structured argumentation data.

As AI continues to integrate into decision-making processes, argument mining stands at the frontier of enabling machines to process, understand, and even contribute to deliberative dialogues. By automating the extraction of argumentative structures, argument mining holds the potential to enhance transparency, foster collaboration, and improve decision-making in both human and AI-driven systems.

2.7.1 Argument Mining Tasks

The figure provides an overview of the key tasks in the field of argument mining (Lawrence & Reed, 2020). Starting from the identification of argument components by segmenting and classifying these as part of the argument being made or not (these tasks are sometimes performed simultaneously, sometimes separated and sometimes the latter is omitted completely), we move down through levels of increasing complexity: first considering the role of individual clauses; secondly considering argumentative relations such as simple premise/conclusion relationships; and thirdly looking at whether a set of clauses forms a complex argumentative relation, such as an instance of an argumentation scheme (Walton et al., 2008).

All of these areas can play a key role in the deliberation process, whether that is differentiating factual statements from values and opinions, or finding the most central and divisive issues on a given topic (Lawrence, Park, et al., 2017).

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Figure 4: The tasks and levels of complexity in argument mining techniques.

The arrows shown between tasks in the figure indicate ways in which the results from one task have been used to inform the execution of another. For example, the arrow from the “Argument/Non-Argument” task to the “Contextual Clausal Properties” task, reflects much early argument mining work (e.g. Moens et al., 2007) which performed these tasks in sequence; deciding which parts of the text were argumentative and then assigning a role to them. This approach has been challenged however, with Carstens and Toni (2015) being the first to point out that whether a sentence is argumentative or not often depends on the context in which it is used, and instead advocating classifying relations first and then considering sentences to be argumentative if they have a relation connecting them (reflected in the arrow from “General Relations” to “Argument/Non-Argument”).

Similarly, some tasks can inform each other, for example, where Feng and Hirst (2011) showed that argument scheme instances could be classified given general relations between argument components, Lawrence and Reed (2015) showed that such general relations can be determined by classifying argument scheme components directly from segmented text.

This interdependency between tasks has given rise to a growth in the application of multi-objective learning approaches (e.g. Eger et al., 2017; Hou & Jochim, 2017; Morio & Fujita, 2018)), where all tasks are learnt and performed at the same time. These examples

highlight how the simple pipeline view of argument mining, which characterises a lot of older research work, is increasingly being superseded by more sophisticated and interconnected techniques.

2.7.2 Approaches to Argument Mining

Many of the earliest approaches to argument mining (V. W. Feng & Hirst, 2011; Moens et al., 2007; Palau & Moens, 2009) focused on applying existing computational linguistic techniques to identify specific facets of the argumentative structure contained within a text. Instead of requiring an a priori defined set of rules that the software applies to a given example of argumentative text, these techniques train machine learning algorithms on manually annotated argument datasets to produce models capable of automatically classifying text.

By feeding in a sufficient volume of text spans along with their annotated class – e.g. part of a sentence with the annotated label as ‘premise’ – the model learns to associate specific linguistic cues with this class and can then predict to which class new text spans should be assigned. In this way, the system learns a model on the basis of an appropriately labelled set of examples (the training data), which is then tested to an as yet unseen set of unlabelled examples (the test data) to test how well the system performs.

As advances are made in the performance of machine learning models, this strategy continues to deliver incrementally improving results (Galassi et al., 2020). More recent advances have started to explore characteristic features of natural language that are specifically related to argumentative intent or particular application domains. By combining such features and the accompanying techniques in a concerted approach, the insights from various disciplines and perspectives can be leveraged to achieve the best results (Lawrence & Reed, 2015).

2.7.3 Classifying Clauses

Typologies of clauses or propositions have traditionally played a central role in the study of debate and argumentation. The three genres of rhetorical argumentation distinguished by Aristotle (1991) in his *Rhetoric*, for instance, can in part be characterised on the basis of the statement types predominant in each. Judicial rhetoric considers factual statements in a legal case about past events in determining the guilt or innocence of an agent. Epideixis – or ceremonial oratory – tends to engender evaluative statements to praise or criticise behaviors and character traits. Lastly, deliberation in political discourse sees a predominant use of policy proposals appealing to the advantages and disadvantages of future actions.

In the modern study of argumentation and persuasion, the types of propositions and their verification when used as premises in an argument are crucial issues (Freeman, 2000), leading to a variety of typologies of statements.

For example, Reynolds and Reynolds (2002) distinguish between statistical, testimonial, anecdotal and analogical evidence; while Hoeken and Hustinx (2003) use a revised

distinction between individual examples, statistical information, causal explanations, and expert opinions; Fahnestock and Secor (1988) employ the classical stasis issues of fact, definition, cause, value, or action; and Wagemans (2016) follows standards from debate theory by distinguishing values, policies and facts.

Such typologies have also been used in the annotation of text corpora for the purpose of training automated systems for classifying statements by means of machine learning. Park and Cardie (2014) classify propositions as unverifiable, verifiable non-experiential, or verifiable experiential – where verifiable propositions constitute assertions of objectively verifiable truth values. In a follow-up study, the authors (Park & Cardie, 2018) develop a corpus annotated with five proposition types: fact, testimony, value, policy and reference. Dusmanu, Cabrio, and Villata (2017) distinguish between factual and opinion-based arguments on Twitter, while Hua and Wang (2017) classify argumentative evidence as based on (statistical) studies, facts, opinions, or reasoning. Visser et al. (2019) annotated the first television debate between Hillary Clinton and Donald Trump in the lead-up to the 2016 US presidential elections with statements of fact, policy, and value.

While the general classification of statement types is important in evaluating persuasive texts, the classification of factual statements has gained particular prominence in recent years as part of fact-checking measures to combat misinformation. For developing manual and automated procedures for fact-checking alike, it is paramount to first know which statements can or should be checked. It only makes sense to fact-check factual statements, not, for instance, evaluative or policy statements. To this end, Hassan, Li, and Tremayne (2015) classify sentences as non-factual, unimportant factual, and checkworthy factual. Similarly, Patwari, Goldwasser, and Bagchi (2017) and Jaradat et al. (2018) automatically determine the fact-check-worthiness of factual claims in political debates. Naderi and Hirst (2018), finally, automatically distinguish between true, false, stretch, and dodge statements in parliamentary proceedings. Given the role emotive language plays in the spread and success of fake news (Bakir & McStay, 2018), the automatic classification of value statements could also be leveraged in identifying and combating it.

2.7.4 Classifying Argument Relations

Identifying relations between pairs of propositions is a more complex and nuanced task than identifying the roles that an individual proposition may take. It is one thing to know, for example, that a given proposition is a premise; it is much more challenging to determine for which conclusion (or conclusions) it serves as a premise. Approaches to identifying these relations either build upon the prior classification of individual clauses or aim to extract relations directly.

Palau and Moens (2009), build upon their classification of each argument sentence as either premise or conclusion using a Context-Free Grammar (CFG), produced by grouping manually derived rules. This CFG is used to determine the internal structure of each individual argument.

Whilst the accuracy of classifying sentences as argument or non-argument is 0.80 and F-scores of 0.68 and 0.74 for classification as premise and conclusion respectively, for the harder task of determining argument structure, the accuracy achieved is 0.60.

Peldszus (2014) also builds on the initial task of identifying roles of segments in the Microtext corpus by adding a ‘combined’-level, showing, for all types, whether a segment’s function holds only in combination with that of another segment (combined) or not (simple). The target is specified by a position relative identifier with a numerical offset identifying the targeted segment relative from the position of the current segment. The prefix ‘n’ states that the proposition of the node itself is the target, while the prefix ‘r’ states that the relation coming from the node is the target. Again, the results for identifying the target of a relation (maximum F-score of 0.45) are lower than for identifying the roles (maximum F-score of 0.85).

This same microtext corpus is used in (Peldszus & Stede, 2015), which looks at identifying conflict relations by examining the texts for occurrences of counter-considerations (e.g. “Even though...”, or “It has been claimed that... however ...”), which the author uses to introduce a potential criticism of their argument, before going on to address the issue and so strengthen their point. This identification is carried out by labelling the textual segments as either ‘proponent’ or ‘opponent’ using a linear log-loss model, resulting in an F-score of 0.64 for identifying opposition relations between segments.

Whilst the work discussed thus far builds upon previous identification of component roles before identifying relations, Cabrio and Villata (2012) propose an approach to detect arguments and discover their relationships directly by building on existing work in Textual Entailment (Dagan et al., 2006). Textual Entailment (TE) refers to a “directional relation between two textual fragments, termed text (T) and hypothesis (H), respectively”. The relation holds whenever the truth of one text fragment follows from another. In this case, the T-H pair is a pair of arguments expressed by two different users in a dialogue on a certain topic and the TE system returns a judgement (entailment or contradiction) on the argument pair.

A dataset of 300 T-H pairs is created using manually selected topics from Debatepedia²⁰ which provides pre-annotated arguments (pro or con), and follows the criteria defined by the organisers of the Recognizing Textual Entailment (RTE) challenge.²¹ Of these 300 T-H pairs, 200 are used to train (100 entailment and 100 contradiction) and 100 to test (50 entailment and 50 contradiction). The pairs collected for the test set concern completely new topics, never seen by the system, and which are provided in their unlabelled form as input.

TE recognition is carried out using EDITS (Edit Distance Textual Entailment Suite).²² EDITS implements a distance-based framework which assumes that the probability of an entailment relation between a given T-H pair is inversely proportional to the distance between T and H.

²⁰ <http://www.debatepedia.org>

²¹ <http://www.nist.gov/tac/2010/RTE/>

²² <http://edits.fbk.eu/>

The system uses different approaches to distance computation, providing both edit distance algorithms (cost of the edit operations (insert, delete, etc.) to transform T into H) and similarity algorithms. Each algorithm returns a normalised distance score between 0 and 1. During training, distance scores are used to calculate a threshold that separates entailment from contradiction. Of the EDITS configurations which Cabrio and Villata tested, the highest accuracy is obtained using either Word Overlap or Cosine Similarity (0.66 in both cases), with Token Edit Distance performing significantly less well (accuracy=0.53), suggesting that semantic similarity plays a more important role than syntactic similarity (a result backed up by the comparative analysis of (Aker et al., 2017), which also found syntactic features to be the least informative in all of the experimental settings considered). Whilst these numbers are quite low, this is an interesting result, suggesting that the relationship between topics in an argument gives more of a clue as to how the components relate, than does the way in which those components are expressed. This is carried through in several later works, which look at relations between topics and semantic similarity between propositions.

Nguyen and Litman (2016) argue that looking at the content of such pairings to determine relationships does not make full use of the information available. They propose an approach that makes use of contextual features extracted from the surrounding sentences of source and target components as well as from general topic information. Experimental results show that using both general topic information and features of surrounding sentences is effective, but that predicting an argumentative relation will benefit most from combining these two sets of features.

The machine learning approaches to argument mining discussed so far have all used supervised learning to perform classification. However, unsupervised learning has also been applied to the task. In (Lawrence et al., 2014), a Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic model is used to determine the topical similarity of consecutive propositions in a piece of text. The intuition is that if a proposition is similar to its predecessor then there exists some argumentative link between them, whereas if there is low similarity between a proposition and its predecessor, the author is going back to address a previously made point and, in this case, the proposition is compared to all those preceding it to determine whether they should be connected. This assumes that the argument is built up as a tree structure in a depth-first manner, where an individual point is pursued fully before returning to address the previous issues. Although the assumption of a tree structure does not hold for all arguments, it is the case for around 95% of the argument analyses contained in AIFdb, and 80% of arguments in the Consumer Debt Collection Practices (CDCP) corpus as reported by Niculae, Park, and Cardie (2017).

Whilst no evidence is given by Niculae et al. supporting the hypothesis of topical relations with manual analysis of the data, the automated results do support the hypothesis, with a precision of 0.72, and a recall of 0.77 recorded when comparing the resulting structure to a manual analysis.

It should also be noted that what is being identified here is merely that an inference relationship exists between two propositions, with no indication of the directionality of this inference.

This same approach is implemented in (Lawrence & Reed, 2015), where the use of LDA topic models is replaced by using WordNet²³ to determine the semantic similarity between propositions. This change is required to overcome the difficulties in generating a topic model when the text being considered is only a short span, such as an online comment or blog post. The results are comparable to those achieved using LDA, with precision of 0.82 and recall of 0.56. In this case, the thresholds are adjusted to increase precision at the expense of recall, as the output from this method is combined with a range of other approaches to determine the final structure, and as such the failure of this approach to identify all of the connections can be compensated for by the other techniques.

A similar approach of assuming a relationship between argument components, if they refer to the same concepts or entities, is used by AFAlpha (L. Carstens et al., 2014), which represents customer reviews as trees of arguments, where a child-parent relationship between two sentences is determined if they refer to the same concepts, with the child being the sentence that has been posted later. A sentence is represented as a set of features, including its semantic characteristics such as metadata about the review in which the sentence appears, as well as features based on the sentence's syntactic and lexical nature, such as occurrences of certain words and phrase types. A feature vector thus represents each pair of sentences and is classified using a model trained on a data set comprised of data taken from the Q&A debating platform, Quaestio-it,²⁴ and IMDB.²⁵

Carstens and Toni continue this line of work in (L. Carstens & Toni, 2015) focusing, on the determination of argumentative relations, and foregoing the decision on whether an isolated piece of text is an argument or not. This focus is based on the observation that the relation to other texts is exactly what describes the argumentative function of a particular text span. The paper mentions a number of use cases, describing a method of evaluating claims, by giving a gauge of what proportion of a text argues for or against them.

The important role played by similarity is also exploited by Gemechu and Reed (2019) who borrow notions of aspect, target concept and opinion from opinion mining, and use these to decompose ADUs down into finer-grained components, and then use similarity measures between these components to identify argument relations.

Such decompositional argument mining not only performs well on diverse single-author arguments (outperforming the techniques of Peldszus and Stede on their Microtext corpus, and of Stab and Gurevych on their AAEC corpus) but also on arguments situated in dialogue (albeit at lower levels of performance: F1 ranging from 0.74 to 0.77 on both Microtext and AAEC, and 0.63 on US2016).

²³ <http://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

²⁴ <http://www.quaestio-it.com>

²⁵ <http://www.imdb.com>

Finally, Wachsmuth, Syed, and Stein (2018) highlight an interesting link between similarity and argumentative relations. The work presented aims to determine the best counterargument to any argument without prior knowledge of the argument's topic. The best performing model tested rewards a high overall similarity between a potential counterargument and the given argument's conclusion and premises, whilst punishing those counterarguments that are too similar to either of them. To some extent, this result captures the intuition that argumentative relations occur where something different is being said about the same topic.

2.7.5 Argument mining and deliberation

Although there are currently no widespread uses of argument mining in deliberation platforms directly, in this section, we will look at three key potential applications of argument mining and their relation to deliberation. These three application areas are: argument evaluation, argument analytics, and dialogue systems.

2.7.5.1 Automatic Argument Evaluation

Of particular note to deliberation is the use of argument mining techniques to provide support over the automatic evaluation and assessment of argumentative debates (Vecchi et al., 2021). Multiple corpora have been created over recent years capturing argumentative information in debates from different perspectives. For example, in (Orbach et al., 2019) where a corpus consisting of claim and rebuttal pairs extracted from debates is presented. An alternative approach to natural language debate resources is presented in (Roush & Balaji, 2020), where a corpus containing complete debates with their summaries is described. These resources can be useful to address specific analyses of argumentation in debates, such as finding counterarguments or producing argument summaries. They are, due to the complexity that a complete argumentative annotation process would require, limited for approaching a complete analysis and evaluation of argumentative debates. In this direction, the US2016 corpus (Visser et al., 2019) was created, containing complete argumentative annotations (divided into argument maps) of the 2016 US presidential debates. Similarly, the VivesDebate corpus (Ruiz-Dolz et al., 2021) provides a large resource containing complete argumentative annotations of 29 debates framed in a university debate tournament.

This corpus was extended with acoustic features in (Ruiz-Dolz & Iranzo-Sánchez, 2023), allowing to investigate the role of intonation and prosody in addition to argumentative features in debates. Most of the work carried out in the automatic assessment of natural language arguments has been focused on the evaluation of individual arguments rather than complete debates (Wachsmuth et al., 2017), (Al Khatib et al., 2020), (El Baff et al., 2020), (Marro et al., 2022). This fact, however, has started to change with the potential of natural language processing algorithms and large language models, and the progressive increase in the availability of debate corpora. In (Potash & Rumshisky, 2017), initial work investigating

the evaluation of debates is presented in which the authors make use of Recurrent Neural Networks to evaluate non-professional debates.

Following this trend, in (Shirafuji et al., 2019), the authors propose a method based on the persuasiveness of the debaters to predict the outcome of online text-based debates using a support vector machine. More recently, in (Hsiao et al., 2022), the authors present an algorithm for predicting the outcome of non-professional debates in online forums. A common point in all these approaches is that they focused mostly on non-professional debates (e.g., online debates). This changed in (Ruiz-Dolz et al., 2023), where the authors present a hybrid approach combining concepts from formal argumentation, such as argumentation frameworks and argumentation semantics, with natural language processing techniques to leverage structural aspects of the debate and predict the winner. Interestingly, in the field of formal argumentation, the structural aspects of argumentation have also played an important role in the assessment of, for example, formal argumentation frameworks that can encode a debate. For example, by using graph neural networks instead of classic solvers (Craandijk & Bex, 2021; Kuhlmann & Thimm, 2019; Malmqvist et al., 2020). In these cases, however, arguments are treated as abstract entities rather than natural language arguments.

2.7.5.2 Argument Analytics

Argument Analytics (Lawrence, Snaith, et al., 2017) provides a range of automated techniques for quantitatively processing and visualising characteristics of large sets of analysed argumentative data. More specifically, the developed methods work with any data conforming to the Argument Interchange Format, be it pre-annotated data (from AIFdb, for instance), or the output of argument mining software. Argument Analytics components range from the detailed statistics required for discourse analysis or argument mining to infographic-style representations, offering insights in a way that is accessible to a general audience. The extendable set of modules currently comprises: simple statistical data, which provides both an overview of the argument structure and frequencies of patterns such as argumentation schemes; dialogical data highlighting the behavior of participants of the dialogue; and real-time data allowing for the graphical representation of an argument structure developing over time. Together, these analytics open an avenue to giving feedback on live debates, generating hypotheses from large sets of evidence, producing summaries of citizen science, and more.

2.7.5.3 Dialogue Systems

The web-based discussion software Arvina (Lawrence, Bex, & Reed, 2012) allows participants to debate a range of topics in real-time in a way that is structured but at the same time unobtrusive. Arvina uses dialogue protocols written using the Dialogue Game Description Language (DGDL) (Bex et al., 2014) to structure the discussion between participants.

Such protocols determine which types of moves can be made (e.g. questioning, claiming, etc.), when these moves can be made (e.g. a dialogue starts with a claim; question moves

can only be made in the turn directly following a claim; etc.), and describe how each move updates the argument structure of the discussion taking place.

Arvina can support multiple human users interacting in the same dialogue, as well as incorporating software agents representing (the arguments of) specific authors who have their opinions stored in AIFdb (Lawrence, Bex, Reed, et al., 2012). So, for example, say that Wilma has constructed a complex, multi-layered argument using the OVA argument analysis tool (Janier et al., 2014), concerning the use of nuclear weapons. An agent representing Wilma can then be added to an Arvina discussion and questioned about these opinions, with the agent answering by giving Wilma's pre-annotated opinions.

The DGDL dialogue games available in Arvina have been developed to capture a range of structured conversations, for example, to facilitate the generation of mathematical proofs (Pease et al., 2014) or allow for debate of moral issues. The Polemicist (Lawrence et al., 2023) application, in particular, offers a custom version of Arvina, allowing users to interact with agents representing the panellists and witnesses from the BBC Moral Maze radio programme. Polemicist uses a fixed DGDL protocol, allowing the user to take on the role of the moderator of the debate: selecting topics, controlling the flow of the dialogue, and thus exploring all the angles of the rich argumentative content. Playing the role of moderator lets the user rearrange the arguments and create wholly novel virtual discussions between the contributions of participants that did not directly engage in the original debate, while still reflecting their stated opinions.

Whilst Arvina and Polemicist currently rely on pre-annotated material to provide the responses for agents in a dialogue, they represent a valuable use case for automatically mined arguments. If the argumentative structure in a radio transcription can be extracted by argument mining, conversations in the Polemicist could take place as the radio programme is being transmitted. Similarly, discussions aimed at creating new mathematical proofs in Arvina could feature counterexamples extracted from online mathematical publications. Combining such dialogue interfaces with a robust argument mining platform would enable users to discuss any issue of their choosing with any person whose opinions on that topic have been previously recorded.

2.8 How do we know if digital deliberation works?

In the frame of the AI4Deliberation project, various evaluations will take place that aim to critically assess various aspects of the use of AI in public deliberations. This includes evaluating the quality of AI results (e.g., the quality of the summarization), evaluating the quality of the AI-enabled deliberation process, evaluating the usability and user experience of the AI-enabled platform and evaluating the acceptance, usefulness and ease of the AI-enabled platform. This chapter seeks to synthesize current research about evaluation methods, metrics and approaches that can potentially be used later on in the frame of the project. We address the following questions here:

- What approaches exist to evaluate the quality of the results of AI-mediated deliberations?
- What approaches exist to evaluate the quality of the deliberative experience in AI mediated deliberations?
- What approaches exist to evaluate the quality of the technology (such as AI) in digitally mediated deliberations?

2.8.1 Approach

This chapter followed a hybrid approach to identify relevant literature. Following the PRISMA guidelines we adopted a multi-stage process to synthesize research on evaluation methods and metrics. Various searches were conducted in order to address the three research questions of the chapter. Additionally, we incorporated relevant pre-identified literature already familiar to the authors based on their expertise and prior experience, particularly in the evaluation of usability and acceptance. We also exploited relevant literature reviews, surveys and books such as (Celikyilmaz et al., 2021; Chang et al., 2023; Koutsabasis, 2016) . The identified literature is related to:

- The quality of results, including the quality of the outcome of the AI features, as well as the quality of the AI-enabled deliberation itself.
- The quality of the user experience – usability.
- The quality of technology - acceptance, usefulness and ease of use.

Regarding the PRISMA-based literature review, a search was conducted across various databases:

- *ACM Digital Library*,
- *arXiv*,
- *Google Scholar* (partially),
- *Scopus*, and
- *Web of Science*.

The search involved various combinations of keywords, such as

- evaluation,
- method,
- model,
- AI,

- large language models (LLMs),
- text generation,
- deliberation,
- usability,
- user experience,
- technology acceptance,
- usefulness and,
- ease of use.

Figure 5: PRISMA Documentation Chapter 8

From each database, we selected to review the top-100 studies (in case more than 100 results were returned). In summary, this process yielded 416 records (including records

identified through relevant literature reviews, surveys and books). Additional to these records, we also consider 15 pre-identified papers familiar to the authors based on their expertise. After removing records before screening and excluding ineligible records, 44 papers were selected to be included in the chapter.

2.8.2 Results

2.8.2.1 Quality of results: Approaches to Evaluate AI features

The quality of the results of an AI-enabled platform can be assessed based on two approaches: i) assess the outcome of the AI features (e.g., assess the quality of the summarization) or ii) assess the quality of the AI-enabled deliberation itself.

Regarding the assessing of the AI features, in the frame of AI4Deliberation, various AI features will be examined, such as text summarization, translation, question answering, fact-checking etc. The literature has already proposed evaluation methods for such tasks, including automatic evaluations and human evaluations:

- **Summarization:** the quality of summarization can be evaluated both automatically and by humans. Automatic evaluations can use metrics such as ROUGE (Lin, 2004) that measures n-gram overlap between generated and reference summaries and BERTScore (T. Zhang et al., 2020) that offers a deeper analysis by comparing semantic similarity through contextual embeddings. More advanced methods like QAEval (Deutsch et al., 2021) assess content quality by determining if the generated summary can answer specific questions. Human evaluators can assess the coherence, relevance, and informativeness of the summaries (Celikyilmaz et al., 2021).
- **Translation:** machine translation evaluation can be automatically conducted based on metrics like BLEU (Papineni et al., 2001), which measures n-gram precision with a brevity penalty. TER (Snover et al., 2006) assesses the number of edits required to match a hypothesis to a reference, offering a complementary perspective. Recent advancements include neural metrics such as COMET (Rei et al., 2020), which is fine-tuned on human feedback datasets to predict translation quality more accurately.
- **Question Answering (QA):** QA systems are often evaluated with metrics like Exact Match and F1-Score, which measure token-level accuracy against ground truth. Relevant frameworks are also proposed, such as ChatEval (Sedoc et al., 2019) which evaluates chatbots, including automated and human evaluations.
- **Fact-checking:** models like FactCC (Kryściński et al., 2019), FEQA [(Durmus et al., 2020) and QuestEval (Scialom et al., 2021) assess factual consistency by comparing generated content with source material through question answering or classification frameworks. These methods can identify hallucinations in generated text, ensuring alignment with the source information.

- **Ethics/trust Evaluation:** ethics is a horizontal dimension that needs to be evaluated across all AI features. The EU has proposed a relevant human-centered tool, namely Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI), to assess trustworthy AI. Additionally, a number of metrics have also been defined such as the Fairness Score and Bias Index (A. Agarwal et al., 2023), that can be used to automatically evaluate AI systems.

The above list of evaluation methods for various AI features does not aim to be exhaustive but provides a good basis for further investigation. The reason is that the AI features that will be employed in the frame of the project have not been decided yet. Thus, when the AI features to be used are decided in a later stage, then the more dedicated search will be conducted for the corresponding evaluation methods based on the above list.

Regarding the assessing of the quality of the AI-enabled deliberation itself two main indices have been proposed in deliberative processes: the Discourse Quality Index (Steenbergen et al., 2003), which assesses procedural and deliberative aspects of discourses, and the Deliberative Reason Index (Niemeyer & Veri, 2022), which measures the reasoning capabilities of participants (including the AI) in a deliberative process.

2.8.2.2 Quality of experience: User experience, usability

Empirical Usability Methodologies (i.e., gather data directly from users): methodologies centered on the observation and analysis of real users interacting with a product or system (including also AI). A common methodology is **usability testing** (Rubin & Chisnell, 2008), where users complete predefined tasks in a controlled environment while evaluators observe their activities and gather data. This method yields insights related to task success rates, completion times, and user satisfaction. Another method is **field studies** (Ciocca et al., 2012), which involves observing users in their natural environments to capture real-world interactions. Additional techniques include **think-aloud protocols** (McDonald et al., 2012), where users verbalize their thoughts during task execution, and **eye-tracking studies** (Novák et al., 2024), which automatically track and then analyze eye movement to evaluate the system. Additionally, specific questionnaires have been developed to collect relevant quantitative information, such as the SUS: System Usability Scale (Brooke, 1996).

Inspection Usability Methodologies: methodologies that use experts to assess the usability of a system (based on existing principles or frameworks). **Heuristic evaluation** is a methodology in which usability specialists review the interface against a set of heuristics, such as those proposed by Nielsen (e.g., minimize memory load, prevent errors, provide feedback) (Nielsen & Molich, 1990), to identify usability flaws. Extension of the Nielsen heuristics are also proposed for AI systems (Langevin et al., 2021) (e.g., User control and freedom, multimodal flexibility and efficiency of use, Trustworthiness). **Cognitive walkthroughs** (Jaiswal & Moosath, 2023), involve evaluators performing tasks and predicting user behaviors to determine whether the design supports the completion of the task.

The inspection usability methodologies are useful at early development stages as they do not require user involvement, making them cost-effective and efficient. However, they are limited by the evaluators' expertise and may not uncover issues specific to diverse user

contexts. A combination of inspection and empirical methodologies can provide a comprehensive understanding of usability challenges/solutions.

The above usability methodologies are already established and have been used for many years in “traditional” ICT systems. In recent years, they have been also applied/adopted to access AI systems, e.g. SUS is used to evaluate ChatGPT (Ma’ruf et al., 2023).

2.8.2.3 Quality of technology: acceptance, usefulness, ease of use

The **Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)** (Davis, 1989) defines two important factors influencing user decision in accepting technology, namely perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Developed based on the theory of reasoned action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1973), TAM examines the way personal impressions affect the adoption of a particular technology (Partala & Saari, 2015). Moreover, TAM focuses on initial adoption instead of continuous usage of a technology (Premkumar & Bhattacharjee, 2008). In addition to that, TAM deals mostly with voluntary adoption (Alamgir Hossain & Quaddus, 2011) and does not take into account qualitative, emotional, and cultural aspects that may influence the actual behavior (Ward, 2013).

Figure 6: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989)

Figure 7: TAM2 model (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000)

The original version of TAM was expanded – **TAM2** (TAM2) (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), including external factors (e.g., social influence processes and the cognitive instrumental processes) that affect technology acceptance. TAM2 was further enhanced in order to produce **TAM3** (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008), including more comprehensive factors in explaining individual acceptance of technology. TAM3 explains the *importance of the intervention*, i.e., pre-implementation and post-implementation intervention, in an IT adoption process. TAM3 has the main focus on how the intervention by the organisation can help employees to make better decisions on technology adoption. The proper application of TAM3 is believed to be able to reduce the risk of implementation failure.

Figure 8: TAM3 model (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008)

Another approach relevant to acceptance in the **Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology** (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003). UTAUT has four core determinants (i.e., performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions) of intention and usage and up to four moderators (i.e., age, gender, experience, and voluntariness of use) of key relationships.

Figure 9: UTAUT model (Venkatesh et al., 2003)

The **Information System (IS) success model** (DeLone & McLean, 1992) was introduced to provide a general and comprehensive evaluation of IS success from different perspectives. This model proposes seven IS success measurements and is structured in three layers: information quality, system quality and service quality (at the first layer), which affect user satisfaction and also the actual use of the IS (at the second level). In 2003, the model was updated (DeLone & McLean, 2003) to propose a new specification, intention of use, at the second layer and combined individual and organisational impacts into net benefit.

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Figure 10: IS success mode [\(DeLone & McLean, 1992\)](#)

The **e-Government Adoption Model (GAM)** (Shareef et al., 2011) comprises critical factors that enable citizens to adopt eGovernment at different stages of service maturity. This research showed that technology acceptance models cannot fully capture and specify citizens' behavior as regards eGovernment adoption, as it is influenced by many more factors, including organisational, human, economic, social and cultural issues. Therefore, GAM considers that technological, behavioral, social, cultural, organisational, economic, political, and marketing aspects might provide important insights while investigating explanatory variables for eGovernment adoption. Moreover, GAP assumes that eGovernment adoption behavior also differs based on service maturity levels.

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Figure 11: GAM model ([Shareef et al., 2011](#))

Focusing on the participation aspect of eGovernment, the **eParticipation Acceptance Model (ePAM)** (Panopoulou et al., 2021) was also proposed. ePAM was developed by CERTH, which is a partner in the AI4Deliberation project. ePAM integrates concepts from TAM (including TAM variations for eGovernment) and eParticipation evaluation literature.

ePAM includes TAM's main concepts of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Behavioral Intention to Use, and the four additional concepts of Technological Confidence, Integration to Governmental Processes, Perceived Facilitating Conditions and Social Influences. Compared to TAM, ePAM shows that acceptance of participatory government technology relates more to perceived usefulness than perceived ease of use. ePAM is more closely related to the AI4Deliberation project since the acceptance of AI-enhanced deliberations will be assessed (deliberations are a way of participation).

Figure 12: ePAM model (Panopoulou et al., 2021)

The above “traditional” acceptance models can also be applied to AI systems and settings. For example, in (Na et al., 2022) the authors apply TAM in Combination with the Technology–Organisation–Environment (TOE) Framework in order to assess the acceptance of AI-based technologies in construction firms. In (Wang et al., 2023) the authors apply TAM to assess the acceptance of AI in e-commerce. However, in other cases, extensions of TAM are proposed to assess AI systems. For example, in (Dahri et al., 2024) the authors extend TAM to assess the acceptance of AI-Powered ChatGPT. The extension includes dimensions like the social influence, perceived AI trust etc.

Additionally, other AI acceptance models have been proposed, which are not based on TAM. The AI Device Use Acceptance (AIDUA) model (Gursoy et al., 2019) is based on the Cognitive Appraisal and Cognitive Dissonance theories, and outlines how customers evaluate AI devices in service delivery. The model assumes three-stages: i) the first stage (primary appraisal) is about the evaluation of relevance and congruence of AI devices, ii) the second stage (secondary appraisal) is about evaluating the costs and benefits of the AI device use based on the perceived performance and effort expectancy and iii) the third stage (outcome stage) is about the emotions that emerge after the two previous stages.

Figure 13: The AI Device Use Acceptance (AIDUA) model ([Gursoy et al., 2019](#))

Another study also explores the acceptance of AI devices in the service industry (Pelau et al., 2021). The proposed model includes three main dimensions, namely “perceived empathy of AI”, “acceptance and trust towards AI” and “perceived anthropomorphic characteristics of AI”. In another study, the “perceived empathy” is also assessed for AI dialog systems (e.g., ChatGPT) (Concannon & Tomalin, 2024). In this study, the authors propose a 10-item Empathy Scale for Human-Computer Communication (ESHCC). ESHCC can evaluate text or voice-based interactions or transcripts.

Figure 14: Model for the consumer-AI device acceptance ([Pelau et al., 2021](#))

2.8.5 Conclusion

This chapter reviewed various evaluation models/metrics/approaches that potentially can be beneficial for the AI4Deliberation project in order to assess various aspects of the use of AI in public deliberations.

These models/metrics/approaches are related to the evaluation of the quality of AI results, evaluation of the quality of the AI-enabled deliberation process, evaluation of usability and evaluation of acceptance. In general, the identified models/metrics/approaches can be classified into three main categories:

- i) “traditional” models that focus on technology, which are also applicable to AI, ii) extensions of “traditional” models that address the unique characteristics of AI and iii) brand new models specifically designed for AI.

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2.9 Institutionalising AI-enabled deliberation

The term ‘AI-enabled deliberation’ already signifies that AI, or technology in general, is not enough to realise deliberative democracy. This literature review focuses on the artefacts needed besides the technical artefacts in order to arrive at meaningful deliberation processes. Such artefacts create the procedures, practices, and routines needed to operate the AI tools supporting deliberation in a safe and ethical manner.

Jiménez et al. (2019) have described what is needed for participation to be meaningful (their understanding of participation is based on deliberation). They argue that an enabling environment is needed to make participation meaningful, even when the deliberative process is (partly) mediated by technical artefacts. The enabling environment goes beyond mere instrumental aspects and technicalities for instigating and supporting deliberative processes. Instead, the enabling environment encompasses procedural elements and contextual factors. The procedural elements encompass the design requirements for the deliberation process and are based on the theoretical underpinnings of deliberative democracy. These elements can be operationalised through both institutional as well as technical artefacts (or a combination of the two). The contextual factors can be divided in the institutional context of participation and structural contextual factors. The institutional context comprises laws and regulations, social and cultural norms, etc. The structural contextual factors refer to factors that shape the deliberation, but cannot be influenced by participants or facilitators.

This chapter focuses on the procedural elements that cannot be engendered through technical artefacts and the general institutional context of AI-enabled deliberation platforms. We understand institutions as social rules that structure the behavior of actors involved or affected by AI-enabled deliberation (cf. Hodgson, 2006). This includes actors that design, develop, deploy, use and interact with AI deliberation methods. Institutions can be both formal and informal. Formal institutions are rules, norms, and strategies that have been approved through established decision-making processes – e.g., laws, policies, and procedures. Informal institutions are prevalent and accepted rules, norms, and strategies that have emerged besides official channels of decision-making, such as routines, (organisational) culture, values, and leadership. In the case of AI-enabled deliberation, institutions complement the technical artefacts. Together, the institutional and technical artefacts should ensure the effective, safe, and meaningful enactment of AI-enabled deliberation in the public domain, i.e., adhering to, guaranteeing, and strengthening democratic and Rule of Law practices. In other words, institutions that structure AI deliberation practices corresponding to democracy and the Rule of Law.

Jiménez et al. (2019) consider participation, and its deliberative elements, in general. This literature study zooms in on the enabling environment of AI-enabled deliberation platforms. This chapter is divided into three parts. First, this chapter examines what the literature says about non-technical artefacts for AI-enabled deliberation.

Secondly, the chapter focuses on the requirements and conditions for an enabling environment for AI-enabled deliberation that are described or prescribed in the literature. Finally, this study examines the literature on approaches to institutionalise AI-enabled deliberation platforms in public organisations.

2.9.1 Approach

We performed a literature search in two databases most applicable to the topic of institutional design for deliberation platforms:

- *Scopus*, and
- *Web of Science*.

We used the following search string in both databases:

("online deliberation" OR "deliberation platform" OR "digital deliberation" OR ("artificial intelligence" AND "deliberation")) AND (institution OR policy OR guidelines OR sociotechnical OR socio-technical)

The first part of the string demarcates the type of technology and/or platforms this research is focusing on. These search terms are the same as those used in other literature reviews in this report. The second part of the search string is in line with our specific focus on the institutional context of AI-enabled deliberation platforms. The search terms aim to bring up literature that discusses system elements beyond the technical elements.

The PRISMA diagram below shows the flow diagram of this literature study. The literature search resulted in 242 studies in Web of Science and 158 studies in Scopus. 310 unique studies remained after filtering out duplicates. Five of these studies were not accessible or retrievable. We proceeded with screening the studies by reading the titles and abstracts. In case of doubt, we scanned the full text of the study. Studies that 1) only had a technical focus, 2) focused on deliberation apart from a democratic setting, such as deliberation in multi-agent systems, 3) studies that considered deliberation in other environments than government, and 4) studies that were in languages other than English were excluded in this first screening. The screening resulted in 42 studies. After reading the full texts, 20 studies remained. Finally, we added 3 studies through backwards snowballing from the selected studies.

Figure 15: Prisma Documentation Chapter 9

2.9.2 Not only technology

The starting point of this literature study is that AI-enabled deliberation platforms are not only constituted of technology. Instead, such platforms are composed of both technical and institutional artefacts. The first part of this literature study answers the following question: What institutional artefacts in AI-enabled deliberation platforms do authors describe? The selection of studies shows two main perspectives on institutional artefacts: a socio-technical perspective and a value perspective.

Authors calling for a socio-technical perspective on AI-enabled deliberation platforms emphasise the importance of understanding the context in which the platform will be implemented (Anastasiou et al., 2023; J. A. Carstens & Friess, 2024). Carstens and Friess (2024) show that the operationalisation of deliberation in AI-enabled platforms is dependent on social and cultural norms.

They argue that a socio-technical perspective is needed to bring these norms into view. In this, socio-technical mostly refers to the context in which the system is implemented.

Like Carstens and Friess, Anastasiou et al. (2023) argue that designers of AI-enabled deliberation platforms focus too much on the technical artefacts in such platforms. They argue that considerations related to the societal impact of these deliberation platforms should be integrated into designing these platforms.

Authors who emphasise the value perspective, react to the focus on technology in most of the literature on AI-enabled deliberation platforms (Alnemr, 2020; Epstein et al., 2014; Shortall et al., 2022). Shortall et al. (2022) start from the same observation as the authors writing from the socio-technical perspective: the current literature on AI-enabled deliberation focuses on technology. Their literature study shows that the focus of the literature has become narrower compared to the studies reviewed by Fries and Eidler (2015) years before. However, Shortall et al. (2022) attribute this to “very little discussion about the values or interpretation of deliberative democracy that underpins automated facilitation tools” (p. 12). According to them, values or themes like inclusiveness, diversity, and equality lack attention in the literature on AI-enabled deliberation platforms.

Where other scholars see potential for AI-enabled deliberation platforms to advance democratic practices, Alnemr (2020) argues that technology can only enhance the deliberative qualities in a public debate. The technical aspects of deliberation platforms make them undemocratic by default. Alnemr relates this to the fact that citizens – who are the main actors in deliberative processes – are generally not involved in or part of the design process of AI-enabled deliberation platforms.

Finally, Porwol et al. (2016) combine both the value as well as the socio-technical perspective, and add a third perspective to arrive at an ontology for e-participation. Their ontology is based on perceiving technology-supported deliberation as a democratic process, as a socio-technical system, and as an initiative or project. The ontology aims to improve future deliberation systems.

2.9.3 Requirements and conditions for the institutional context of AI-enabled deliberation platforms

Designing AI-enabled deliberation platforms is about more than designing technical artefacts (see also Deligiaouri, 2013; Steibel, 2012). However, to design the non-technical artefacts, public organisations need requirements and conditions. Accordingly, the second question answered in this literature study is: *what requirements and conditions for institutional artefacts are described in literature on AI-enabled deliberation platforms?* Several studies list requirements and conditions for designing AI-enabled deliberation platforms (Friess, 2018; Friess & Eilders, 2015; Garard et al., 2018; Gastil, 2023; Itten & Mouter, 2022; Towne & Herbsleb, 2012; Velikanov & Prosser, 2017a, 2017b). From the lists of requirements in these studies, we filtered out the purely technical requirements and conditions. The requirements can be seen as a way to arrive at meaningful deliberation.

Deligiaouri (2013) argues that meaningful deliberation relates to both the participants as well as the organisers of deliberation. Citizens should feel engaged and that their voices are heard.

For governments, deliberation should provide possibilities to aggregate opinions and interests, and translate them into laws and policies.

A key article in listing requirements for non-technical elements is the literature study by Friess and Eilders (2015). The authors distinguish three main categories for requirements. These categories follow the structure of input, throughput, and output. The input for technology-supported deliberation is the institutional design, the throughput is the communication process, and the output are the deliberation results. Each category comprises several requirements. The list of these requirements was expanded by Friess (2018). Moreover, Garard et al. (2018) provide five general elements on which the organisation and operation of deliberation platforms should be based: participants, openness, facilitation, communication, and dialog.

The studies by Fries and Eilders, Friess, and Garard et al. provide general elements, but have also specified non-technical requirements. In addition, other authors have specified requirements and conditions. The main requirements are as follows:

- **Ensure the adoption of deliberation in official decision-making**
Actors that will work with the output of deliberation should be attendant to, show commitment to, meaningfully translate the output of deliberations into official policies or decision-making (Coleman & Moss, 2012; Escher et al., 2017; Friess & Eilders, 2015; Juusola & Varsaluoma, 2023; Nam, 2020; Steibel, 2012; Stromer-Galley et al., 2012; Towne & Herbsleb, 2012; Velikanov & Prosser, 2017a)
- **Address power imbalances between participants**
The design of deliberation platforms should make the input by less powerful participants more visible and refrain from reproducing the power of dominant participants (Coleman & Moss, 2012; Velikanov & Prosser, 2017a).
- **Organise moderation**
Several authors consider moderation as conditional to respectful, orderly, rational, purposeful, and inclusive online deliberation (Friess & Eilders, 2015; Steibel, 2012; Velikanov & Prosser, 2017a).
- **Provide possibilities for self-governance**
Participants should have the room to organise the deliberation process themselves. For example, by organising moderation and facilitation internally (Van Der Merwe & Meehan, 2011; Velikanov & Prosser, 2017b, 2017a).
- **Combine technology-based approaches with ‘traditional’ approaches**
Itten and Mouter (2022) argue that combining mini- and maxi-publics can bring the best of both worlds. In the same line, Haas Lyons et al. (2014) show the importance of mixing online and offline methods more broadly.

More specifically, Gastil (2023) identifies requirements for including game mechanisms in deliberation platforms.

Considering the aims of the AI4Deliberation project, these requirements are of special interest for the project. Gastil's "essay shows that the features of successful games ... can be deployed in deliberative design to achieve the desired ends of deliberation" ((2023), p. 1053).

Apart from design requirements, several authors list evaluation criteria to compare different deliberation platforms or assess individual platforms (Anastasiou et al., 2023; Porwol et al., 2016; Rehg et al., 2005). Rehg et al. (2005) distinguish four aspects to consider when assessing deliberative legitimacy of deliberation supported by technology: self-transformation, substantive dialectical quality, inclusion, and non-coerciveness. The ontology formulated by Porwol et al. (2016) is to be used to compare different deliberation systems with each other. Anastasiou et al. (2023) list evaluation criteria to assess the societal impact of deliberation platforms.

These requirements can support designers in specifying the institutional artefacts in AI-enabled deliberation platforms. At the same time, we should acknowledge the limitations of design. Deligiaouri (2013) argues that designers of deliberation platforms will not succeed in incorporating or synthesising all interests or satisfying all participants. At the most, they can engender a more inclusive and open decision-making process. Juusola and Varsaluoma (2023) indicate the many trade-offs for designers, such as those between anonymity and identification, or related to the trust of established actors in the deliberation (see also (Friess & Eilders, 2015)). Most importantly, designers and public organisations should be aware that the design of the AI-enabled deliberation platform cannot be controlled fully. The ultimate form and function of those platforms is also shaped by contextual factors (Karlsson, 2012).

2.9.4 Institutionalising AI-enabled deliberation

To adopt AI-enabled deliberation platforms, public organisations need instructions and guidelines to integrate such platforms into their work practices. The third and final question answered in this literature study concerns the process of institutionalisation: how to institutionalise AI-enabled deliberation?

Articles that (implicitly) refer to institutionalising AI-enabled deliberation platforms often provide recommendations for the design process of such platforms. First, scholars end their articles by recommending specific design methods for deliberation platforms, such as co-creation (Alnemr, 2020; J. A. Carstens & Friess, 2024), participatory design (Shortall et al., 2022), or value-sensitive design (Shortall et al., 2022). Second, authors recommend to ensure that designers or developers perceive the platforms from a socio-technical perspective (Anastasiou et al., 2023; J. A. Carstens & Friess, 2024). Anastasiou et al. (2023) mostly see a role for a socio-technical perspective in the evaluation of platform designers. For Carstens and Friess (2024) the integration of the socio-technical perspective in the design process is mostly a way to ensure that developers do not miss non-technical elements in platform

design. According to them, the socio-technical perspective brings the social and cultural norms discussed before into view and counters a techno-solutionist approach.

Likewise, Kreiss (2015) argues that designers should have a clear goal for deliberative processes when designing a platform, and should carefully construct a mental model of the citizen who will participate on the platform. Moreover, authors providing evaluation criteria (see the previous section) also signify that evaluation of platforms should be an explicit, and maybe recurrent, step in the life-cycle of the deliberation platforms.

Finally, where our search and selection of studies focused on deliberation processes within a governmental context, Moss and Coleman (2014) argue that policies or efforts on e-democracy should not only be initiated by, supported by, or originate from government. They come to this conclusion after showing that e-democracy policy in the UK has been insufficient in delivering meaningful e-democracy initiatives.

2.9.5 Synthesis

This chapter examined the enabling environment of institutions needed for AI-enabled deliberation platforms. Several authors observe that most literature on deliberation supported by AI is too focused on technology, thereby neglecting socio-technical and value aspects of AI systems in deliberation. Nevertheless, we also found studies that list requirements for non-technical artefacts in AI-enabled deliberation platforms. Public organisations can use these requirements to design deliberation platforms. This can also help to shift attention in the design process from technical to socio-technical systems.

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2.10 Best practices

2.10.1 Approach

The following section of the review is rooted in a systematic search that was performed on Google Scholar to investigate the intersection of deliberation with artificial intelligence (AI), with a view to discerning suitable scholarly literature as well as practical applications. This search was conducted using a selection of thoughtfully chosen keywords intended to identify a wide but narrow range of literature. The search terms were:

- "Artificial intelligence" AND "mini-public" OR "mini public" (156 results): Capturing studies and discussions about the application of AI in small-scale, deliberative democratic bodies.
- "Artificial intelligence" AND "citizens' assembly" AND "LLM" (16 results): Narrowing the focus to how large language models (LLMs) intersect with structured citizen deliberations.
- "Artificial intelligence" AND "deliberative platform" (65 results): Targeting platforms or tools where AI is explicitly designed to support or enhance deliberative engagement.

Objective: Identify at least 30 pertinent manuscripts that exhibit the optimal practices for combining AI with deliberative processes, evaluate their practical application, and offer insights into possible uses. The following inclusion criteria were applied to ensure the relevance and quality of the review:

- **Relevance to Deliberative or Democratic Processes:** The work should emphasize the function, application, or adoption of AI in deliberation contexts, including citizens' assemblies, mini-publics, or other participatory models.
- **Exploration of Best Practices, Challenges, and Opportunities:** Research should address practical implications, such as the best practices, challenges, or opportunities for incorporating AI to support deliberative democracy.
- **Empirical Evidence or Case Studies:** Special consideration was given to publications that presented empirical data, case studies, or illustrations of AI-augmented deliberative platforms or tools with real applications and results.

To maintain the relevance and timeliness of the review, the following exclusion criteria were applied:

- **Papers Published Before 2021:** Papers published up to 2021 were excluded for the review to obtain a view of recent advances in AI and deliberation processes as a reflection of the fast-paced development of technology as well as its application within democratic innovation.

- **Lack of Direct Analysis of the AI-Deliberation Intersection:** Articles referring to artificial intelligence or deliberation peripherally, without direct examination of their intersection, were excluded. Articles that discuss general AI ethics, machine learning models, or deliberative democracy separately, without a practical or theoretical intersection, were excluded.
- **Exclusive Focus on AI in Governance or Public Policy:** Research that only investigated the application of AI for governance, public administration, or for making policies with no relevance to deliberative platforms or democratic innovations (e.g., deliberative platforms, citizen panels, citizen assemblies) was ignored.

Figure 16: Prisma Documentation Chapter 10

2.10.2 Introduction

Digital deliberation platforms have evolved significantly in recent years, moving from rudimentary discussion forums to sophisticated systems that often employ AI. This shift has sparked both enthusiasm and caution among scholars of participatory democracy. Also, AI offers tools for *scaling* deliberation, *structuring* complex debates, and *moderating* interactions in ways that might otherwise be unfeasible (Fishkin et al., 2025; C. T. Small et al., 2023).

On the other hand, critics warn that opaque algorithms risk *undermining* transparency, *exacerbating* bias, or *crowding out* key human processes of reflection and mutual respect (Shortall et al., 2021; Sieber et al., 2024).

We draw on 33 studies that show how AI can support or undermine core deliberative principles, from agenda setting to small group dialogues and large-scale public input. The sections below outline the main debates and concrete examples of AI-facilitated deliberation at each stage of the democratic process.

2.10.3 Foundational Principles: Inclusivity, Transparency and Accessibility

Numerous scholars emphasize *inclusivity* as a cornerstone of digital deliberation (Barandiaran et al., 2024; Fontes et al., 2024; Mariani et al., 2024; Shortall et al., 2021). Platforms must ensure that every participant — regardless of digital literacy, physical location, or socioeconomic background — can participate meaningfully in the process. This can be achieved by designing AI tools with clear instructions and features that enhance and structure the user experience (Gianola et al., 2024), multilingual support (Landemore, 2024; Vebrova et al., n.d.) and user-friendly interfaces (Fieschli & Muldoon, 2024).

Transparency in platform governance, data handling and algorithmic processes is frequently cited as a foundational principle for digital deliberation and crucial for building trust and legitimacy (Barandiaran et al., 2024; Hashemi et al., 2024). Hashemi et al. (2024) argue, for example, that explainable AI (XAI) is vital for participatory budgeting contexts, where participants must understand the algorithms that structure funding allocations. Shortall et al. (2022; 2021) caution that opaque systems risk exacerbating biases, thereby undermining mutual respect and civic trust. To address this concern, researchers propose:

- *Algorithmic Disclosure*: Clearly communicating how AI-driven clustering, moderation, or summarization occurs.
- *Axiomatic Frameworks*: Outlining the assumptions behind AI outputs so users can evaluate their fairness (Hashemi et al., 2024).

Transparency is similarly central: both the platform's rules and any AI-driven functionalities must be openly documented so that users understand *how* data is processed and *why* certain outcomes emerge (Hashemi et al., 2024; Landemore, 2024).

For example, the Decidim platform (Barandiaran & et al., 2024; Barandiaran et al., 2024) was founded on the “social contract” principle, emphasizing free software, open content, and democratic oversight. Those principles are central to enabling the *Decidim* community to ensure that participants can *co-develop* and *customize* modules, potentially including AI plug-ins, without ceding governance to opaque systems. Thus, transparency has become the principal means for trust between users and technology. In this respect, as Carter et al. (2024) note in their deliberative jury on AI in Australian healthcare, design strategies that foreground participant understanding and balanced information build the trust necessary for a genuine exchange of views.

2.10.4 Human Oversight and Hybrid Approaches

Numerous studies emphasize hybrid methodologies that couple AI assistance with human input. This human-AI labor division is viewed as the most reliable strategy for ensuring high quality across the board.

Fishkin et al. (2025) describe how an “AI-assisted” moderation system in the Stanford Online Deliberation Platform flags uncivil behavior and manages speaking time, yet ultimately relies on human facilitators to interpret context and maintain the spirit of respectful dialogue.

- *Moderation and Turn-Taking*: AI can streamline who speaks and when, preventing domination by a few voices.
- *Conflict Mediation*: Humans remain critical in guiding heated discussions back to productive territory (Barry et al., 2025).

Hybrid approaches also mean bridging offline and online spaces. The Po.lis platform, for instance, has been integrated with *in-person* citizens’ assemblies, enabling large-scale opinion clustering and sense-making prior to face-to-face deliberation (Barry et al., 2025). Rountree et al. (2024) similarly describe how *Zoom* and shared *note-taking tools* (e.g., Mural) facilitate online components of a climate assembly while preserving critical *in-person* elements such as facilitated small-group dialogue. Generally, by combining offline and online interactions, participants can reap the benefits of AI-driven summarization and data analysis (C. T. Small et al., 2023) without sacrificing the *civility* and *depth* often achieved in face-to-face discussions (Arnesen, & et al., 2024).

2.10.5 Co-Design of AI Tools

A recurring theme is *co-design*, where platform developers and participants collaboratively shape how AI tools function. Boucher et al. (2023) advocate “collective intelligence design,” urging that citizens should have input on the features, transparency settings, and intended outcomes of the AI they use.

In a similar vein, Barandiaran et al. (2024; 2024) note that Decidim’s modular architecture allows communities to adapt AI modules to local contexts, respecting cultural norms and privacy preferences.

2.10.6 Best Practices for AI-Enhanced Deliberative Platforms

2.10.6.1 AI in digitally mediated deliberation

The literature identifies several key roles for AI in enhancing digital deliberation. **AI-assisted facilitation** can automate tasks such as turn-taking, summarizing discussions, flagging inappropriate language, and managing group dynamics, freeing up human facilitators to focus on more complex interventions (Fishkin et al., 2025; C. T. Small et al., 2023). **AI-powered moderation** can help maintain civility and address harmful online behaviors, though human oversight is still essential (Shortall et al., 2022; C. T. Small et al., 2023).

Algorithms can also illustrate incivility, manage speaking quotas, and classify participants according to attitudes, interests accentuated, and positions adopted, but the final decision on conflict resolution or the capturing of nuances from rich input is still with humans. Costello et al. (2024) illustrate how dialogues with AI can even *reduce conspiracy beliefs*, hinting at the potential of AI-based “counter-argument” or “devil’s advocate” systems (McKinney, 2024) that challenge participants to engage in reasoned debate. **Translation tools** powered by AI can break down language barriers and promote multilingual deliberation, fostering greater inclusivity (Landemore, 2024; Vebrova & et al., n.d.).

2.10.6.2 Data Clustering and Opinion Mapping

A main advantage of AI in large-scale deliberation is its ability to make sense of voluminous, diverse inputs. Po.lis, detailed in Barry et al. (2025), employs machine learning to cluster statements, revealing points of consensus and disagreement. Landemore (2024) similarly posits that AI-powered clustering lowers cognitive load for participants by visually mapping common ground. Key practices here include:

- **Consensus Identification:** Flagging shared values and statements across opinion groups.
- **Conflict Visibility:** Highlighting disagreements that need deeper exploration.

In general **data analysis** capabilities of AI, including topic modeling, sentiment analysis, and clustering of opinions, can help identify consensus points, areas of polarization, key themes emerging from large datasets (Landemore, 2023; Mariani et al., 2024; C. T. Small et al., 2023), and overall monitoring the deliberative integrity of the democratic decision-making process (Veri, 2023). Finally, **argument mapping** tools enhanced by AI can visualize the structure of debates, making complex arguments more accessible and facilitating deeper understanding (Deseriis, 2023; Shortall & et al., 2021).

2.10.6.3 Summarization and Note-Taking

AI-generated summaries can relieve participants of labor-intensive tasks. Rountree and Richards (2024) and Mariani et al. (2024) show how automated note-taking in platforms like Zoom or Mural helps participants focus on *reasoning* over logistics or helps track the *progress of arguments* and highlight underexplored points (W. Zhang & et al, 2022). However, these authors stress that summaries should be subject to participant review to ensure accuracy.

2.10.6.4 Automated Moderation and Gamification

Shortall et al. (2021) discuss employing AI-based “automated facilitation,” which can manage uncivil comments, offer clarifications, and maintain balanced speaking times. Gamification elements like earning points for constructive engagement have also shown promise in boosting participant involvement and maintaining a respectful tone. Yet, researchers warn that poorly designed gamification might shift the focus away from genuine deliberation to mere point-chasing (Boucher & et al, 2023; Shortall et al., 2022).

2.10.6.5 Translation, Accessibility and Multilingual Facilitation

In large or diverse polities, multilingual capacity becomes paramount. AI-driven translation can expedite inclusive engagement, ensuring that participants are not siloed by language barriers (Ovadya, 2023; Rask & Bokyoung, 2024). Landemore (2024) similarly proposes real-time translation modules integrated with AI-based facilitation. Careful design is essential to avoid losing nuance in translation, a challenge that calls for ongoing human oversight and iterative improvements (Fontes et al., 2024).

2.10.6.6 Reasoning

The problem of *misinformation*, both deliberate and accidental, remains central in digital deliberation. Tessler et al. (2024) describe how AI can “help humans find common ground” by neutralizing false claims through authoritative fact-checking or clarity checks. Shortall et al. (2022) refer to “reason against the machine” strategies, underscoring the importance of designing AI to flag dubious sources while still respecting open debate. Tools that highlight conflicting statements prompt participants to reflect on underlying evidence, helping to foster a more *reasoned* discourse.

2.10.7 Ethical and Practical Considerations

2.10.7.1 Algorithmic Bias and Social Equity

A central caution in the literature is that AI tools can reproduce or amplify existing biases (Carter & et al., 2024; Deseriis, 2023; Shortall et al., 2022). Algorithmic bias is a major concern, as AI systems can perpetuate and amplify existing social inequalities if not carefully designed and monitored (Shortall & et al., 2021; C. T. Small et al., 2023). Yet, as outlined by

Cohen and Suzor (2024), if AI moderation or clustering consistently disfavors certain viewpoints or demographic groups, the platform’s legitimacy is undermined (T. Cohen & Suzor, 2024). Scholars call for:

- *Regular Audits*: Ongoing reviews of AI outputs for unfair patterns.
- *Inclusive Data*: Ensuring training datasets are representative of diverse groups.
- *User feedback loops* that can catch and correct system skew (Hashemi et al., 2024).

2.10.7.2 Privacy and Anonymity

Privacy emerges as another cornerstone issue (Barandiaran & et al., 2024; Hashemi et al., 2024). Pol.is, for instance, allows participants to comment anonymously, reducing self-censorship and fear of reprisal (Barry et al., 2025). Vebrova et al. (n.d.) similarly find that *pseudo-anonymity* fosters more honest expressions of viewpoints.

2.10.7.3 Regulatory frameworks

Some authors link potential technical issues to broader questions of *institutional* design.

Fischli and Muldoon (2024) propose that decentralized architectures like D-CENT or DECODE can empower local communities to set norms for AI usage, reducing reliance on top-down governance. In a similar vein, Cohen and Suzor (T. Cohen & Suzor, 2024) argue that “public interest” demands procedures for contesting AI decisions, comparable to the appeals mechanisms in established legal systems. These considerations shape how AI might be integrated into democracies at scale (McKinney, 2024), including the potential for large-scale *citizens’ assemblies* or *mini-publics* that draw on real-time data analytics (e.g., (Veri, 2023)).

2.10.7.4 Preservation of Deliberative Principles

While AI can expedite data processing, the ultimate success of digital deliberation hinges on preserving *mutual respect, equality of voice, and reasoned argumentation*. Landmore (2023) warns that overly automated processes risk losing the moral depth of human-to-human engagement.

Ovadya (2023) similarly highlights the importance of “alignment mechanisms” to ensure AI systems uphold democratic values.

Fundamentally, research warns that technology should *complement* rather than *replace* human deliberation (Gastil & Felicetti, 2025; Talarico, 2022). Ensuring participants have space for reflection and reason-giving is critical to achieving genuine democratic legitimacy (Landmore, 2023). As Ovadya (2023) notes, while AI can reduce logistical burdens and moderate large-scale discussions, the deeper *transformative* potential of deliberation, which lies in building empathy, compromise, and shared understanding, ultimately rests on human processes that algorithms can only partially enable.

2.10.8 Frameworks and Patterns in Literature

An inductive reading of these studies reveals a common *three-pillar framework*:

1. *Transparency and Explainability*
 - 1.1. Make the AI's internal logic accessible to participants.
 - 1.2. Provide clear rationales for algorithmic outputs.
2. *Hybrid Facilitation and Human Oversight*
 - 2.1. Retain humans in decision-making loops for moderation and conflict resolution.
 - 2.2. Ensure AI tools serve as supportive instruments rather than primary decision-makers.
3. *Iterative Ethical Safeguards*
 - 3.1. Regularly audit AI outputs for bias or errors.
 - 3.2. Employ open design processes allowing participant scrutiny and feedback.

By consistently applying these pillars, digital deliberation platforms can harness AI's scalability and data-handling capabilities without compromising the core principles of democratic deliberation.

2.10.9 Conceptual Map

The main outcomes of T1.1 and the identified concepts (i.e., features that contribute to successful digital deliberation, affordances of digital deliberation platforms, problems of offline deliberation addressed by digital deliberation, AI features for democratic deliberation, deliberative formats, existing deliberation platforms, methods to measure AI, best practices) are represented as a conceptual map. The conceptual map is visually depicted using DebateGraph, which is a collaborative online platform designed to illustrate complex issues and their interconnections clearly.

The DebateGraph link of the results is the following:

<https://debategraph.org/Stream.aspx?nid=731860&vt=ngraph&dc=all>

The aim is to use DebateGraph throughout the project lifecycle enabling the further refining and improvement of the outcomes as the project evolves.

The following figures show some selected visualisations of the results from DebateGraph.

Figure 17. Graph view, AI-enabled deliberations: Conceptual Map

Figure 18. Graph view, AI-enabled deliberations: Deliberative Formats

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Figure 19. Graph view, AI-enabled deliberations: Problems of Offline Deliberation Addressed by Digital Deliberation

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Figure 20. Tree view, AI-enabled deliberations: Best Practices - (Design Recommendations) Ensure legitimate, transparent, and user owned outcomes (Design Recommendations)

Figure 21. Tree view, AI-enabled deliberations: Affordances of Digital Deliberation Platforms

2.10.10 Conclusion

Across the literature, there is broad consensus that AI can meaningfully expand the inclusivity and scope of democratic deliberation. From automating facilitation tasks (Fishkin et al., 2025) to summarizing large-scale discussions (Rountree & et al., 2024) to clustering

viewpoints (Barry et al., 2025; Landemore, 2024), researchers underscore AI's capacity to deepen collective reasoning. Nevertheless, they repeatedly caution against allowing technology to override the distinctly *human* aspects of reflective, respectful discourse.

Through transparency, human oversight, and ethical guardrails, AI can effectively complement humans in democratic settings. When applied responsibly, AI enables broad public input, clarifies contested issues, and helps participants discover areas of shared concern.

Looking ahead, future experimentation and open-source development can refine these practices further, ensuring that democracy remains participatory and inclusive in an era of accelerating technological change.

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3. Technology Foresight

This chapter presents the outcomes of “T1.2 Technology foresight on wide adoption of using AI in deliberations” that aims to: *“conduct a Technology Foresight following an open process, with the participation of Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB) members and anyone else interested. The foresight is expected to provide four different scenarios for the future with diverse use of AI and relevant policy outcomes.”*

To map future scenarios, we employed a technology foresight that is a *“systematic and holistic approach to exploring the long-term futures of Science, Technology and Innovation and to dealing with uncertainties and complexities where anticipatory thinking is key”*. Different methods can be used to conduct a technology foresight. In AI4Deliberation, we mainly employed the Delphi survey, Scenario planning, and stress testing.

The focus of the technology foresight is to **explore future scenarios related to the use of AI in deliberative democracy by 2030**. Deliberative democracy suggests everyone is given the opportunity to express their opinion to ensure the legitimacy of decisions. It involves engaging citizens and stakeholders in discussions to reach consensus or informed opinions on complex societal issues.

The main outcome of the Technology Foresight was to identify and sketch **four future scenarios**: one, namely “Utopia or Garden”, where AI is working to its full potential, all legal/ethical/organization/technical challenges have been addressed, stakeholders have embraced its use, and its full potential has been achieved. A second, namely “Dystopia”, where all concerns raised by skepticism have been realized and AI is used to demolish rather than to improve democracy. Two intermediate scenarios were also identified and outlined.

The aim of Technology Foresight is not to predict the future but rather to investigate different alternatives, aiming to improve our understanding of relevant conditions. The outcomes of the technology foresight are made publicly available through DebateGraph for further consultation throughout the lifetime of the project.

The rest of the chapter presents in detail the methodology followed as well as the produced results, including the results of a literature review in the domain and the results of the Delphi study that involved 12 domain experts in two rounds.

3.1 Methodology

This section presents existing methodologies related to Technology Foresight as well as the methodological approach used to conduct the Technology Foresight of AI4Deliberation.

3.1.1 Existing methodologies

This subsection briefly describes existing methodologies related to technology foresight.

3.1.1.1 Technology Foresight

Technology Foresight is a systematic approach to explore potential long-term futures of technology (Dannemand Andersen et al., 2023). It aims to explore future technological developments and their impact on various domains (Coppoletta et al., 2025). At the core of Technology Foresight is dealing with uncertainties.

Technology Foresight can support various critical functions of organisations (e.g., governments) (Coppoletta et al., 2025). For example, it can: i) support decision-makers by evaluating scenarios to anticipate future trends and threats (Coppoletta et al., 2025), ii) identify ground-breaking technologies and innovations (Dannemand Andersen et al., 2023), iii) guide technology planning and management (Dannemand Andersen et al., 2023; Minghui et al., 2022). In public administration, technology foresight can support policy/regulation formulation that facilitates innovation and economic growth (Coppoletta et al., 2025; Dannemand Andersen et al., 2023). It can also help identify future research possibilities and investments and inform funding priorities.

Various techniques have been proposed to conduct a technology foresight. These techniques include, for example, Delphi survey, scenario planning, technology road mapping, horizon scanning, bibliometrics, vision investigation, expert discussion etc. (Dannemand Andersen et al., 2023; Minghui et al., 2022).

3.1.1.2 Delphi Method

The Delphi Method is a technique used to gather and manage the input of experts to address complex problems (Cuhls, 2023; Grupp & Linstone, 1999). Delphi uses multiple rounds of questionnaires that are sent to a panel of experts, with anonymous feedback provided between rounds. The feedback is then summarized and presented to the experts, enabling them to revise their opinion (Grupp & Linstone, 1999). This iterative process aims to converge opinions (ultimately leading to consensus). It also enables the identification of areas of disagreement.

The Delphi method is useful when dealing with issues where knowledge is uncertain or incomplete (e.g., technology foresight) (Cuhls, 2023; Grupp & Linstone, 1999). An advantage is that experts can change their opinion. Delphi does not necessarily force consensus, allowing for the identification of diverse viewpoints (Grupp & Linstone, 1999). The emphasis is on the structured exchange of information and reflection among experts on topics where empirical data may be lacking (Steinmüller, 2023).

There are also cases where Delphi and Scenario planning are used together for foresight exercises. Di Zio et al. (2024) present "Delphi-based scenario development" as a strategic foresight approach to handle future risks and emerging threats. This approach uses Delphi surveys and other qualitative and quantitative tools in a sequence to build future scenarios and it is presented as a framework that can be applied to various domains, including technology and involves steps where the output of a Delphi survey becomes the input for constructing risk scenarios (Di Zio et al., 2024). In addition, a significant case is presented where the Delphi survey is integrated into scenario planning to enhance its effectiveness in

long-term strategy planning, specifically for renewable energy development towards 2030 in China (Chen et al., 2020). Lastly, in the field of software technology, a study used a Delphi survey to gather expert opinions on the likely future of software interoperability in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction industry (Koivu, 2002). Following the Delphi survey, the technique of building scenarios was chosen as the basic framework for representing the findings (Koivu, 2002).

3.1.1.3 Scenario Planning

Scenario planning is a method that has steadily grown in popularity as a recognized organizational intervention since the mid-20th century (Crawford, 2019). It serves as an effective tool for examining future uncertainties and investigating assumptions within organizations (Chermack, 2005). In a world where prediction can be unreliable due to rapid change, scenarios are gaining credibility as valuable tools for preparing for what might happen.

Scenario planning involves the creation and analysis of multiple future scenarios (not to a single forecast) (Drew, 2006). These scenarios can be thought of as tools for ordering one's perceptions about alternative future environments in which one's decisions might play out (Chermack, 2005) e.g., stories that present hypothetical events in the future

Scenario planning has its roots in military strategy and later found significant application in the corporate world in the 1970s (Shell employed it to help the company navigate major disruptions such as oil price shocks) (Crawford, 2019; Drew, 2006; Undheim, 2024). There are two approaches for scenario planning: i) inductive approach - relies on storytelling to identify underlying drivers of change, and ii) deductive approach - uses structured frameworks (i.e., 2x2 matrix) based on critical uncertainties to generate alternative future scenarios (Undheim, 2024).

3.2 Methodological approach

The Technology Foresight exercise described in this deliverable followed a structured, multi-phase methodology that integrated a literature review, an initial exploratory survey, a Delphi method, scenario planning, and stress testing. The goal was to systematically explore uncertainties, gather expert insight, and assess the resilience of potential strategies across alternative futures. The aim was to explore **future scenarios related to the use of AI in deliberative democracy by 2030**. The methodological steps followed were:

1. **Literature review:** The process began with a focused literature review aiming to identify key factors and uncertainties related to the use of AI in deliberative democracy. The findings were grouped into seven distinct "categories of uncertainty" (Ethical & Social, Technical, Organizational and Governance, AI Autonomy vs Human Oversight, Citizen Engagement and Trust, Design and Implementation, Democratic Values and Governance). This step helped ground the technology foresight in existing research.
2. **Exploratory Survey (Pre-Delphi):** The findings of the literature review were presented to the project consortium at the January 2025 online Interim Plenary meeting. During the

presentation an online survey (EUSurvey – **the questionnaire is available in the Appendix**) was circulated asking for their input, including a preparatory ranking activity, where partners participated in a structured survey which included qualitative and quantitative inputs. In the qualitative section, partners were asked to propose critical uncertainties they believed would significantly impact AI adoption in online deliberative platforms. In the quantitative section, partners evaluated each category's Likelihood (how likely is this uncertainty to materialize) and Impact (If this uncertainty materializes, how significant will its impact be) using Likert scale questions.

The outcomes of this exploratory survey helped us to validate and refine the uncertainties identified through the literature review and shape the design of the Delphi process. Based on the feedback received from the exploratory survey and considering also relevant frameworks and methodologies (EIF, PEST analysis, STEEPV) the seven uncertainty categories identified through the literature review were re-organized into five categories namely “Legal & Ethical”, “Social & trust”, “Organizational”, “Technological” and “Political”. These categories were finally used at Delphi.

3. **Delphi method:** The Delphi method involved structured questionnaires using EUSurvey (**the questionnaires are available in the Appendix**), leveraging expert opinions in two rounds to reach a consensus or clarify points of divergence.
 - **Two Delphi rounds** were conducted, engaging **12 experts** with diverse expertise such as Law & Ethics, Technology, Digital Democracy, Social Sciences, and Political Sciences. The 12 experts included the members of the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB) and project partners with highly relevant expertise. The distribution of expertise among the participants was as follows (each expert may have more than one area of expertise): Law & Ethics (4 experts), Technology (6 experts), Digital Democracy (6 experts), Social Sciences (5 experts), and Political Sciences (5 experts). Additionally, the experts' experience ranged between 5 and 30 years, with an average of approximately 19 years.
 - During the **first Delphi round**, experts evaluated the uncertainty categories (the final five categories refined based on the exploratory survey) based on their **Likelihood** and **Impact** using a 5-point Likert scale. Additionally, insights were collected through open-ended questions, in order to gather expert perspectives for each uncertainty category on: i) **Positive and negative developments** related to the identified uncertainties, ii) **Drivers** of positive developments and **causes of failure** for negative developments and iii) **Mitigation strategies** to prevent or minimize negative developments.
 - The **second Delphi round** aimed to **validate and refine the outcomes of the first round** as well as to collect insights and **experts' vision on future scenarios** regarding AI and Deliberative Democracy by 2030. Experts reviewed the qualitative insights derived from the first Delphi round (positive/negative developments, drivers, causes of failure and mitigation strategies), and validated and provided additional feedback. Furthermore, they created short narrative scenarios, specifically envisioning best-case (Utopian) and worst-case (Dystopian) scenarios regarding AI integration into deliberative democratic processes by 2030. The second Delphi round included

the **stress-testing** of the Utopian scenario against potential disruptions identified from the most impactful uncertainty categories identified at round 1 (“Social and trust” and “Political”). Complementary to the two surveys conducted for Delphi, in some cases dedicated interviews with SEAB members were also conducted to clarify and discuss their input.

4. **Scenario Planning:** The results of the Delphi process were synthesized into **four scenarios**. Each scenario served as a lens for imagining how technologies, policies, and societal, legal, ethical and organizational factors might co-evolve. The scenario development facilitated a deeper exploration of implications stemming from critical uncertainties identified in the Delphi rounds, offering, in this way, a structured basis for assessing the resilience and adaptability of envisioned futures. The four developed scenarios include:
- A positive - "Utopia" future where AI improves deliberative democracy by 2030 (i.e., positive developments and mitigation strategies identified through Delphi are realized).
 - A negative - "Dystopia" future where AI undermines deliberative democracy by 2030 (i.e., negative developments identified through Delphi are realized).
 - An intermediate scenario where "Utopia" future is disrupted by negative "Social and Trust" developments (“Social and trust” was identified as the most impactful uncertainty category)
 - An intermediate scenario where "Utopia" future is disrupted by negative "Political" developments (“Political” was identified as the second most impactful uncertainty category).

The outcomes of the Technology Foresight are visually depicted using DebateGraph, which is a collaborative online platform designed to illustrate complex issues and their interconnections clearly. The DebateGraph instance of the outcomes will stay live throughout the project, enabling the further refining and improvement of the outcomes as the project evolves.

3.3 Results

This section presents the results of the Technology Foresight exercise described in the deliverable. The results include: i) the results of the literature review, ii) the outcomes of the exploratory survey and iii) the results of the Delphi method (two rounds). In order to improve the readability of the produced results, the results of the literature review and the results of the Delphi are presented together for each of the five uncertainty categories. Specifically, the section begins with the results of the Exploratory Survey, followed by the combined results of the literature and Delphi method for each uncertainty category.

3.3.1 Exploratory Survey

This subsection presents some details about the Exploratory Survey (Pre-Delphi) and its results. The findings of the literature review were presented to the project consortium at the

January 2025 online Interim Plenary meeting. During the presentation, an online survey (EUSurvey) was circulated asking for their input, including a preparatory ranking activity, where partners participated in a structured survey which included qualitative and quantitative inputs.

The survey included 11 participants (consortium partners) with various professional backgrounds, including research/academia (4 participants), technical (4 participants) e.g., developers and data scientists, Policy/Governance (2 participants) and Civil Society (1 participant). Participants work in different sectors, including Academia (5 participants), the Private sector (5 participants) and NGOs (1 participant). Regarding “AI experience”, 7 participants had a high level of expertise, while 4 participants had moderate experience.

In the qualitative section of the survey, participants were asked an open-ended question: "What do you think are the most critical uncertainties that could impact the adoption and use of AI in deliberation platforms?". The responses did not highlight any new uncertainty compared to the seven initially identified uncertainty categories. The most popular uncertainties in the qualitative section were related to Trust, Citizen Participation, Inclusion, and Algorithmic Biases.

In the quantitative section, participants rated each of the seven uncertainty categories based on their Likelihood (probability of occurrence) and Impact (potential significance if materialized) - using a Likert scale. The uncertainty categories used were: Ethical & Social, Technical, Organizational and Governance, AI Autonomy vs Human Oversight, Citizen Engagement and Trust, Design and Implementation, Democratic Values. The aggregated survey results (mean values) were as follows (T.11., F.22):

Table 11: Quantitative results from the exploratory survey

	Mean Likelihood	Mean Impact	Overall score (Likelihood x Impact)
Ethical & Social	4,09	4,55	18,6
Technical challenges	3,55	3,82	13,5
Organizational and governance issues	3,27	3,64	11,9
AI autonomy vs Human oversight	3,45	3,36	11,6
Citizen engagement and trust	3,82	3,82	14,6
Design and implementation challenges	2,73	3,45	9,4
Democratic values	3,64	3,36	12,2

Figure 22: Overall Risk Scores for Uncertainty Categories Identified in the Exploratory Survey

The outcomes of this exploratory survey helped us to validate and refine the uncertainties identified through the literature review and shape the design of the Delphi process. Specifically, the seven uncertainty categories identified through the literature review were re-organized into five categories, namely “Legal & Ethical”, “Social & trust”, “Organizational”, “Technological” and “Political”. These categories were finally used at Delphi. This consolidation process considered two primary criteria:

1. **Overlap:** categories with closely related themes were merged. For example, "AI Autonomy vs. Human Oversight" was merged with "Ethical & Social".
2. **Uncertainty Prioritization:** The results from the exploratory survey helped us to prioritize uncertainties based on their likelihood and impact. Categories with lower scores were merged into other categories. For example, "Design and Implementation Challenges," was merged into "Technological".

3.3.2 Delphi results and literature review findings

This subsection presents a combination of the outcomes of the literature review and the outcomes of the Delphi. The results are presented for each “category of uncertainty” including:

- The information identified during the literature review
- The information collected from Delphi (both rounds)
 - **Impact** - If the uncertainty category materializes, how significant will its impact be?
 - **Likelihood** - how likely is this uncertainty to materialize?
 - **Positive & negative developments** related to the uncertainty category
 - **Drivers of positive developments** for the uncertainty category
 - **Causes of failure for negative developments** of the uncertainty category
 - **Mitigation strategies** to prevent negative developments of the uncertainty category

The categories of uncertainties that are considered are:

- **Legal & Ethical:** Uncertainties related to regulations/laws, ethical issues (e.g., AI transparency, privacy, AI autonomy vs human oversight, fragmented regulation, regulatory gaps).
- **Social & Trust:** Uncertainties related to acceptance of AI by citizens, participation and trust (e.g., misinformation, citizen engagement, digital divide, inclusion).
- **Organizational:** Uncertainties related to the readiness of public administration, governance issues and coordination between public administrations (e.g., resource allocation, resistance to change, scalability of AI in public administration).
- **Technological:** Uncertainties related to the adoption of technology, reliability of platforms, cybersecurity and data management (e.g., algorithm bias, security issues, low data quality, infrastructure limitations, explainability).
- **Political:** Uncertainties related to political support, alignment with democratic values (e.g., polarization, policy continuity, risk of AI misuse in political processes).

All uncertainties are considered in the frame of use of AI in deliberative processes.

3.3.2.1 Legal & Ethical

Key Literature review findings

Digital deliberation platforms can analyze feedback data that might contain personal and sensitive information, raising data privacy concerns. Therefore, it is very important to comply with regulations like GDPR (Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024). The current administrative rules and legal systems were not made to be applied to the scenarios involving AI, which may lead to imbalances and the need for new regulatory frameworks (Correia et al., 2024). However, some institutions, like the EU, are trying to come up with AI-specific legislation (AI Act), but significant global fragmentation persists (Feldstein, 2023).

The integration of AI in eGovernment platforms (e.g., online participation systems) raises issues about transparency and explainability. The main issues come from the nature of AI which produces decisions that are hard to understand (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2021; Dobbe et al., 2021; Heinrichs, 2022; Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024). The rising public interest in transparency has led to new legislation about "right to explanation" (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2021), but the technical obstacles to achieving explainability still persist (Dobbe et al., 2021).

AI integration also poses risks to autonomy and human control. The risk is that citizens may grant excessive control to AI systems, which could result in "technology obedience" (Mökander & Schroeder, 2024). AI nudges can limit people's freedom to choose by acting in a paternalistic way. Optimizing AI policies can conflict with people's freedom to make their own choices and with democratic decision-making based on shared values. (Mökander & Schroeder, 2024). Using algorithms to guide online deliberation can undermine democratic goals by imposing expert rules and limiting citizens' ability to shape the discussion (Alnemr, 2020).

Additionally, AI system opacity creates accountability and responsibility issues which emerge during discussions about legal reforms for AI applications in public services (van Noordt et al., n.d.). The black-box nature of AI prevents the understanding of algorithmic decisions and prevents the assignment of responsibility for algorithmic public choices (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2021; Loi & Spielkamp, 2021). The responsibility for undesirable outcomes remains unclear under current law because public administration and technology companies have not received specific liability definitions for AI systems. The black-box nature of AI creates limitations for organizations to provide explanations, but simultaneously requires them to establish ongoing discussions about algorithms (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2021).

Finally, the deployment of AI in public contexts requires immediate attention to issues regarding fairness, bias and discrimination. AI systems maintain and strengthen biases found in training data, which results in discriminatory outcomes while creating challenges for non-discrimination and equal treatment (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2021; Mökander & Schroeder, 2024). AI detection of hidden discrimination remains a potential benefit according to some researchers (Heinrichs, 2022). However, concerns remain that existing social biases may persist and even worsen in critical areas (Arnesen et al., 2024).

Delphi results

A summary of the qualitative results collected during Delphi (both rounds) for the uncertainty category “**legal and ethical**” is presented below.

Positive Developments

- The AI Act and other relevant regulations are progressing in setting legal boundaries.
- Strengthened ethical oversight mechanisms (e.g. independent AI ethics committees).
- Widespread awareness of transparency, explainability, fairness and accountability issues. Including also the implementation of relevant mechanisms.
- GDPR reinforces data protection in AI.
- Increased scrutiny by audit organizations (e.g., independent audits of AI systems can enhance transparency and accountability).
- Emergence of socio-technical assessment practices. This may include the evaluation of societal impact during AI system design and deployment.

Negative Developments

- Laws lag behind AI evolution.

- Overregulation and overlapping legal frameworks. This may lead to conflicting or duplicative laws creating uncertainty and thus hindering implementation.
- Lack of harmonization across legal systems. In this case, fragmented regulations (e.g., across the EU) may weaken cohesive governance of AI.
- Lack of legal recognition for non-human (AI-generated) contributions in deliberative processes. In this case, AI-generated content will not be legally acceptable in public deliberations.
- Very strict regulations may hinder EU AI developments and thus increase dependence on non-EU technologies. This will lead to high dependence on foreign AI models.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- Strong regulatory frameworks that ensure transparent, accountable, and responsible AI systems in public deliberations.
- Alignment of AI systems with democratic values (e.g., inclusiveness, fairness, respect of human rights).
- Civic pressure for ethical use of AI in democratic processes.
- Auditing institutions and oversight bodies play an active role in ensuring the accountability and transparency of AI systems used in deliberative processes.

Causes of Failure

- Rapid AI pace vs. slow law-making processes. In this case regulatory frameworks may be unprepared to handle rapid and transformative shifts of AI capabilities.
- Unclear ethical boundaries may lead to uncertainty regarding the appropriate use of AI in deliberative processes.
- Failure to enforce legal norms or apply them across contexts.
- Failure to consistently apply legal rules in different situations can weaken trust in how AI is used in deliberative processes.
- Over-reliance on legal frameworks - without also considering ethical, social and technical measures - can lead to weak AI oversight.
- Reliance on proprietary AI systems whose goals may not be fully aligned with democratic values can lead to limited transparency, accountability and public control.

Mitigation Strategies

- Monitor and adapt AI Act to be aligned with rapid AI advancements.
- Establish multi-stakeholder governance bodies (e.g., involving stakeholders from government, civil society, academia, industry) to ensure the transparent and accountable use of AI in public deliberations.
- Develop legal safeguards (e.g., transparency requirements, bias mitigation measures, inclusive participation protocols) to ensure the fair representation/participation of marginalized groups in AI-mediated deliberations.

- Clarify the legal boundaries for the use of AI in public deliberations and integrate ethical guidelines into policy, procurement processes, decision-making frameworks etc.
- Build adaptive legal frameworks that are flexible and modular, capable of evolving in alignment with AI advancements and societal change.
- Support innovation-friendly regulation to strengthen EU AI markets. Develop legal frameworks that help innovation while safeguarding democratic values.
- Invest in public digital literacy programs to educate citizens on AI in order to reduce misinformation and increase informed participation.
- Establish regular audits to assess bias, explainability, fairness, and the impact of AI tools used for deliberative processes.
- Create rapid response frameworks to address AI harm (e.g., negative impacts or unintended consequences of AI) and establish pathways (formal processes) for resolving these issues in deliberative processes.
- Create ethical AI certification standards for public deliberations to ensure democratic compliance and a 'trust mark' (i.e., a symbol indicating compliance with ethical and legal standards for platforms).
- Encourage accountability by protecting individuals who raise concerns about unethical or dangerous AI use.

3.3.2.2 Social & Trust

Key Literature Review Findings

The implementation of AI within digital deliberation and eGovernment creates uncertainties about public trust in these AI systems. Users tend to feel suspicious about machine learning and natural language processing outcomes because these techniques operate with transparency limitations (Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024).

AI models' opaque decision-making processes create transparency issues, which lead users to doubt result validity and decrease their acceptance of AI-driven digital deliberation platforms. Even when AI explanations are provided, they face public distrust, because users typically do not understand technical explanations, and they may doubt the explanations, especially when the topics are politically sensitive (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2021; De Bruijn et al., 2022).

Also, there are risks related to misinformation and the integrity of data, raising public trust concerns (Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024). The unmonitored spread of unverified narratives through chatbots using LLMs poses risks of opinion manipulation, which might lead to anti-democratic outcomes (Feldstein, 2023). The potential of AI systems to generate persuasive propaganda and disinformation for population control intensifies the existing uncertainty (Feldstein, 2023). Trust depends on revealing how data is used alongside the fairness of algorithms and the decision-making procedures (Salem et al., 2024).

Another key area of uncertainty revolves around citizen acceptance and the levels of public participation when AI is involved. Despite AI's potential to enhance citizen engagement, its

role as an enabler of democratic discussions is sometimes underrepresented in government policy documents (Toll et al., 2020). People generally dislike the use of AI in politics, especially when decisions are fully automated, and they're more skeptical when the issues are more important (Toll et al., 2020). Furthermore, online spaces can allow more people to take part, but they're often disrupted by hostile politics and rude behavior, which can harm meaningful discussion and social unity (Gastil, 2023). Another important issue regards access to and confidence in AI technology, which are closely linked to socio-economic disparities (Pislaru et al., 2024). Marginalized or under-resourced groups may perceive AI as inaccessible or threatening, creating a digital divide that hinders inclusive participation.

Social cohesion and inclusion face important uncertainties too. The digital platforms powered by AI technology allow diverse citizen connections yet there are concerns that online participation does not provide equal representation for all societal segments (Kalampokis, 2024). AI tools that operationalize deliberative norms such as rationality and civility through methods like argument mining and hate speech detection may unintentionally silence minority voices, because these tools favor users who have better educational backgrounds and specific communication abilities (Carstens & Friess, 2024). Focusing only on data bias in AI fairness overlooks the broader socio-technical context, potentially deepening existing inequalities by ignoring how AI interacts with cultural norms and social hierarchies. AI tools have the potential to enforce the communication styles of dominant groups through automation, which would silence marginalized voices according to Carstens and Friess (2024).

Delphi results

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during Delphi (both rounds) for the uncertainty category "**Social Trust**".

Positive Developments

- Growing citizen engagement and public interest in the social impact of AI.
- New citizen deliberation platforms and co-creation models that promote participatory governance.
- AI is used responsibly and increases inclusivity and representativeness while also reducing polarization.
- Improved public AI literacy that leads to enhanced trust.
- Real-world success stories of AI have a huge symbolic value for building trust.
- Increased public oversight of AI systems helps build trust.

Negative Developments

- AI is used to increase polarization, disinformation and public distrust.
- Public trust in AI is reduced due to negative narratives e.g. negative media coverage, misinformation, or lack of transparency
- Misuse (unfair) of AI can trigger protests, resistance, or social tensions. Potentially leading to new forms of violence (e.g., human to machine violence).
- Rising concerns about lack of transparency, the spread of deep fakes, digital divide, and declining democratic participation.
- Citizens may feel powerless or alienated, leading to disengagement from deliberative processes or overreliance on AI to make political decisions for them.
- Lock-in effects to specific AI vendors reduces competition, and increases the potential of social control.
- Increased automation can reduce the space for meaningful human deliberation.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- Investment in AI literacy and digital education to empower citizens and promote informed participation.
- Broad public dialogue and exposure to responsible AI implementations.
- Emphasis on deliberative principles (transparency, oversight, accountability).
- Responsible integration of AI in deliberative processes can increase diversity of voices and participation.
- Emergence of local and community-driven AI tools that align with local democratic traditions and norms.
- Building civic tech ecosystems including e.g., AI solutions designed to enhance citizen engagement, improve trust/co-creation.
- Encouraging citizen participation through rewards, gamification, and budgeting can drive positive engagement and empowerment.

Causes of Failure

- Citizens feel disempowered or excluded from deliberative democracy.
- Misuse of AI by powerful political and economic actors for their own gain.
- Spread of Misinformation (e.g., fake news, manipulated content).
- Growing digital Inequality that excludes vulnerable or marginalized populations from AI-mediated deliberative processes.
- Lack of understanding of AI's role in deliberative democracy.
- AI systems designed without consideration for local democratic traditions, cultures, and deliberative norms.
- Perception that AI systems are designed and controlled by foreign or untrusted entities.

Mitigation Strategies

- Implement AI literacy programs and targeted public education (prioritize youth, elderly, and disadvantaged groups).
- Develop transparent deliberative platforms with public review and oversight.
- Promote human-centered AI design in deliberative processes with a focus on explainability and fairness.

- Include citizens and society stakeholders in designing and developing AI tools that promote democratic values and inclusivity.
- Involve citizens directly in shaping how AI is used in public deliberation, through co-design workshops, citizen juries, and participatory tech assessments.
- Use AI in a responsible way to counter misinformation (e.g., fact-checking, trust metrics).
- Give emphasis to human-centered AI design. Including explainability and fairness features.
- Establish incentives for civic engagement (e.g., recognition, rewards) to encourage wider public participation.
- Establish AI transparency standards about AI systems and their decision-making processes.
- Support long-term studies on AI's social or psychological impact in public deliberation.
- Highlight real-world success stories to demonstrate benefits and increase public trust.
- Foster inclusive, diverse debate, potentially including unconventional contributors (e.g., AI voices).
- Promote balanced narratives e.g., avoid polarized public discussions about the use of AI in deliberations.
- Avoid overreliance on AI for misinformation control. It is important to recognize the limits of automated moderation and the need for social legitimacy.
- Ensure AI systems are adapted to local democratic traditions and social norms.

3.3.2.3 Organizational

Key Literature review findings

Public administration's inertia (e.g., rigid routines, centralized decision-making, unwillingness to share data, and preference for the status quo) can hold back the use of AI (Madan & Ashok, 2023). Resource limitations, such as the funds and personnel with AI expertise, further compound this uncertainty. Resistance from unions due to perceived job losses also contributes (Madan & Ashok, 2023). Also, the capability to deploy AI technologies often depends on a strong foundation of prior e-government developments, particularly regarding data management and digital infrastructure (Van Noordt & Tangi, 2023; Toll et al., 2020). The need for infrastructure is important for AI to be developed and used. A failure to do so can limit progress (Toll et al., 2020). A lack of computational power and access to large datasets can make using AI within e-government difficult (Toll et al., 2020). Therefore, public administrations with a weaker e-government history may face greater challenges in their readiness for AI adoption. The lack of internal expertise causes public administration to depend more on private technology companies for AI development, which creates issues regarding accountability and transparency and may result in most public investments benefiting the private sector (Attard-Frost et al., 2024).

Funding for AI in the public sector is usually ad-hoc and project-based rather than structural. This can lead to financial instability, challenging the maintenance and scalability of AI systems beyond the initial pilot phase (Van Noordt & Tangi, 2023).

The governance of AI needs active involvement from AI developers, end-users, civil society members and policymakers for its effective implementation (Dobbe et al., 2021). The establishment of communication channels, which incorporate feedback mechanisms to include stakeholder perspectives in design decisions, presents an ongoing challenge. The successful implementation of responsible AI demands public, private, and civil society collaboration. However, the exact nature of this partnership, along with the roles of different actors' responsibilities, remains unclear, affecting coordination (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023). Different stakeholders possess varying levels of power during collaborative governance efforts creating obstacles to successful teamwork (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023).

Delphi results

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during Delphi (both rounds) for the uncertainty category “**Organizational**”.

Positive Developments

- Public organizations are investing in AI readiness/innovation. This enhances the efficiency, inclusivity, and transparency of deliberative processes.
- AI helps streamline public sector workflows related to deliberative processes. This can happen e.g., by automating tasks and reducing bureaucratic barriers.
- AI advancements drive innovation in governance and decision-making processes.

Negative Developments

- Resistance to AI integration in deliberative processes is widespread.
- Lack of learning/adaptation about AI, and rigid hierarchies.
- Efforts to implement AI in deliberative processes are fragmented (i.e., without coordination) across government agencies. This may result in inefficiencies in enhancing public participation and decision-making.
- The ageing population and longer working lives in Europe can make public institutions more rigid and resistant to change (including AI).
- Short political cycles limit long-term AI planning and organizational continuity. This makes it difficult to implement sustainable AI strategies.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- The adoption of AI readiness strategies and innovation mandates within public administration enhances deliberative processes.
- Active learning, experimentation, and internal innovation labs within public administration can foster continuous improvement in deliberative processes including the use of AI.
- Cross-sector and public-private AI collaborations are growing, promoting more inclusive participation in deliberative processes
- Public pressure and international examples of AI use in deliberative processes can drive organizational reform.
- The focus on efficiency, inclusion, and digital transformation using AI helps improve deliberative processes and decision-making.
- The shortage of personnel within the public sector may serve as a driver for the adoption of AI leading to enhanced efficiency and service delivery.
- Sufficient time and institutional space for thoughtful integration of AI in deliberative processes.

Causes of Failure

- Low digital - AI literacy within public institutions, especially among senior officials.
- Cultural resistance, weak leadership, and unclear implementation guidance can hinder the effective use of AI in deliberative processes
- Underfunding can limit the resources needed to implement AI in deliberative processes.
- Lack of strategic planning and copy-paste approaches from foreign models can hinder the effective integration of AI in deliberative processes and lead to misalignment with local needs.
- Lack of interdisciplinary approaches can lead to misaligned or incomplete implementation (e.g., not effective solutions, missed opportunities) of AI in deliberative processes.

Mitigation Strategies

- Support collaboration and cooperation between different government agencies and support shared frameworks for AI governance.
- Educate public sector officials about AI deliberation tools and success stories.
- Promote leadership based on values to guide AI transformation aligned with democratic values.
- Ensure clear accountability and well-defined roles for stakeholders involved in AI use within deliberative processes.
- Design the integration of AI using human fallback mechanisms in critical deliberative processes.
- Develop plans (e.g., transition strategies) to address the potential loss of jobs across public organizations due to the adoption of AI in deliberative processes.
- Implement change management and internal communication strategies to ensure easy adoption of AI in deliberative processes.
- Establish long-term AI planning mechanisms. This can enable the overcoming of short political cycles, ensuring long-term integration of AI in deliberative processes.

- Standardize benchmarks to help government institutions assess their maturity in adopting AI for deliberative processes.
- Build capacity of government institutions for AI governance, including oversight bodies.

3.3.2.4 Technological

Key Literature Review Findings

AI introduces new risks such as intelligent cyberattacks, data manipulation, and increased system vulnerabilities (Toll et al., 2020). There are also concerns about the security and integrity of personal data. Additionally, there are concerns related to the use of deliberate data harm organizations and society (Toll et al., 2020).

AI systems can make predictions, but these can be based on biased training data. Thus leading to discriminatory results that affect public goods e.g., justice and equity (Dodd & Cordella, 2019; Mökander & Schroeder, 2024; Carstens & Friess, 2024). For example, AI was used in courts to predict criminal recidivism, showing bias against African Americans (Mökander & Schroeder, 2024).

Furthermore, the “black box” nature of AI is a major challenge. This is because AI decision-making processes remain difficult to understand (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023; Loi & Spielkamp, 2021; Madan & Ashok, 2023). This lack of explainability is a challenge that even AI developers struggle to reconstruct the decision-making processes within complex AI (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023; Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024). This situation can lead to uncertainty about allocating responsibilities (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023). The nature of AI is not always based on clear cause-and-effect relationships, which contributes to this opacity (Kasych et al., 2023). In contrast, efforts to provide explanations for AI decisions can sometimes lead to confusion rather than clarity (e.g. through information overload) (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023). A long-term adoption of AI remains uncertain, since its behavior and outcomes can be unpredictable over time (Dodd & Cordella, 2019).

In the public sector, AI can use a large amount of personal data. This raises privacy concerns and threats like data theft from malicious attacks and misuse, increasing cybersecurity issues (Wirtz & Müller, 2019). AI can also involve new types of intelligent cyberattacks or manipulated data, which can have serious consequences (Toll et al., 2020). Additionally, AI systems can produce flawed decisions arising from poor data quality or problematic properties of data sets. The reliance on correlations in data to infer causality can also lead to misguided evidence (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023).

Finally, in online deliberation, where algorithms replace human facilitators, the reliability and fairness of these algorithms are crucial. Biases embedded in their design could negatively impact the inclusiveness and authenticity of the deliberation (Alnemr, 2020; Carstens & Friess, 2024). Also, separating expert-designed online deliberation from broader democratic values is concerning, as the digital tools used may not align with democratic ideals (Alnemr, 2020).

Delphi results

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during Delphi (both rounds) for the uncertainty category “**Technological**”.

Positive Developments:

- Accessibility, efficiency and user-friendliness of AI tools have significantly increased enabling their wider adoption in deliberative processes.
- The development of explainable AI (xAI) and of frameworks that promote AI transparency continues to advance. This supports the trustworthy use of AI.
- Generative AI and large language models (LLMs) have advanced, creating new opportunities for public use and participation.
- The progress in cybersecurity and data management systems has increased the trust of AI tools.
- Open-source movements and community-led initiatives enable the co-creation of AI tools. This can support their alignment with democratic values.
- Emphasis on data quality in AI training is improving output reliability.
- The availability of testing environments (sandboxes) and evaluation protocols for AI. This has improved the safety of AI tool experimentation in deliberative processes.

Negative Developments:

- AI models lack transparency and can embed algorithmic bias into deliberative processes.
- AI tools that lack a specific democratic purpose can be used improperly to damage deliberative processes.
- Limited testing and validation of AI tools. This also includes the integration of untested AI tools into deliberative processes.
- Increased cybersecurity vulnerabilities in deliberation platforms and risk of misuse by malicious actors.
- Lack of mechanisms to include public feedback in AI-driven decision-making can limit engagement and weaken deliberative processes.

Drivers of Positive Developments:

- Progress in explainable AI (xAI), open-source platforms, and human-aligned model development. This ensures that AI tools used in deliberative processes are aligned with democratic values and foster public trust.

- Collaborative efforts between e.g., academia, public sector, civil society, for deploying AI in deliberative processes.
- Focus on AI for societal good, especially in deliberative processes.
- AI models exist in flexible and adaptable formats which support inclusive deliberations (i.e., ensure marginalized voices can participate).

Causes of Failure:

- Premature adoption of tools without clear governance can undermine democratic principles.
- AI-driven deliberative processes remain at risk because of cybersecurity weaknesses.
- The lack of adequate testing/validation of AI tools in deliberative processes leads to unreliable or biased results.
- Weak governance structures create conditions that make AI applications in deliberative processes susceptible to misuse and bias.
- AI development is driven primarily by commercial interests rather than democratic values.

Mitigation Strategies:

- Promote open-source development and public sector innovation related to the use of AI in deliberative processes.
- AI tools used in deliberative processes need security-by-design protocols which prevent unauthorized manipulation and misuse.
- Design flexible, human-aligned AI systems that enhance participation and transparency of deliberative processes.
- Invest in explainable AI and bias mitigation of AI tools integrated into deliberative processes.
- Provide clear guidelines for appropriate AI deployment in deliberative processes.
- Encourage multi-sector collaboration in development and planning of AI tools used in deliberative processes.
- Pay attention to non-transparent, commercial deployments that ignore public interest.
- Develop and deploy AI tools to identify potential manipulation in deliberative processes by other AI tools (AI is used to monitor AI).
- Allocate resources for independent monitoring to ensure accountability and public oversight of AI tools used in deliberative processes.
- Develop AI infrastructure within Europe to reduce dependency on foreign technology giants (e.g., USA, China). This can reduce external influence.
- Set up safe, experimental environments (sandboxes) where new AI solutions can be piloted. This can ensure their effectiveness and safety in real-world applications.

3.3.2.5 Political

Key Literature Review Findings

The use of biased AI systems in deliberative settings can distort opinions and promote certain views while discriminating against others, thus raising questions about fairness and neutrality (Arnesen et al., 2024). As Dobbe et al. point out, the choice of capturing everything in terms of an AI model and objective function is political, and imposing such abstractions can reify inequities (Dobbe et al., 2021).

The potential for manipulation of information and public opinion through AI is a major factor (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023). In online deliberation platforms, AI could shape arguments, silence opposing views, or fake agreement, weakening the core of deliberative democracy, which depends on open and honest discussion (Kasych et al., 2023). This creates worries about the fairness of the deliberation and the risk of outside influence, making it unclear if the group's decisions truly reflect their will (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023).

The growing political use of AI brings new influential actors into the system which includes AI developers and technology owners who control these systems (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2021, 2023; Dobbe et al., 2021). Their decisions during the design and implementation of AI tools for deliberation can determine both the process and its outcomes in ways that may not be transparent or democratically accountable (Dobbe et al., 2021). This can lead to uncertainty about whose interests are being served by the AI and whether the technology is truly empowering citizens or just reinforcing existing power imbalances (Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023). The use of AI in the public sector prioritizes operational efficiency at the expense of human values and freedom of decision (Dobbe et al., 2021).

Using AI in sensitive areas like deliberation requires clearly defining the values and goals it should follow (Mökander & Schroeder, 2024). However, agreeing on these values can be politically debated and how they are built into AI can strongly affect deliberation results. This process of translating complex ethical and political values into algorithmic parameters is difficult and can lead to debates about whose values are chosen and whether the AI reflects the right goals. (Dobbe et al., 2021).

AI can make information processing more efficient in deliberations, yet democratic values such as human judgment, inclusive dialogue and real-time interaction remain uncertain in political discussions (Arnesen et al., 2024; Kasych et al., 2023; Siachos & Karacapilidis, 2024). Relying too much on AI could reduce political involvement and meaningful human interaction, raising concerns about the long-term impact on democracy's quality and legitimacy (Kasych et al., 2023).

Delphi results

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during Delphi (both rounds) for the uncertainty category “**Political**”.

Positive Developments

- Increased political awareness and leadership around AI's democratic impacts. This enables political leaders to recognize AI's influence on democratic processes.
- AI is seen as a tool to improve governance, deliberative processes and decision-making.
- Political support for ethical AI frameworks to ensure they serve the public good (including AI use in deliberative processes).
- Growing debate about transparency, accountability, and inclusion in AI policy.

Negative Developments

- Increasing dependence on foreign AI providers (e.g., US, China) leads to dependency, geopolitical imbalance and strategic concerns (e.g., in deliberative processes, this could lead to AI systems that reflect foreign interests, influence or control over democratic systems).
- AI is being used for manipulation, disinformation, and polarization in political discourse.
- Risk of technocracy and exclusion, where AI decisions override democratic debate.
- Lack of trust in political institutions, and growing fragmentation or resistance to change (e.g., AI-driven processes in deliberation could face resistance if the public distrusts political institutions).
- Delegation of democratic will to AI systems may trigger authoritarian drift.
- A gap between policy rhetoric and practical implementation (related to the use of AI in deliberative processes) persists.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- AI supports evidence-based policymaking about issues related to deliberative processes
- Cross-country learning and benchmarking. Countries can learn from one another's experiences with AI in deliberative processes, adapting successful models to their own contexts
- Politicians see public benefit and legitimacy from AI integration.
- Long-term, forward-looking political visions for the use of AI in deliberative processes.
- Global competition and international benchmarking drive the modernization of AI use in deliberative processes.
- Growing interest in European AI independence from foreign (USA, China) companies.

Causes of Failure

- Lack of political safeguards enables abuse (e.g., manipulation) of AI for political advantage (e.g., electoral gain)
- Exclusionary use of AI in political processes (elitism or technocracy).
- Rapid adoption of AI in deliberative processes without safeguards could deepen conflict and institutional erosion.
- Over-reliance on non-elected actors (e.g., tech companies) in shaping political processes (i.e., deliberative processes).
- Strategic competition between antagonistic nations overrides other political checks and balances.
- Over-reliance on foreign AI ecosystems may weaken national independence and reduce a country's control over its democratic and deliberative processes.
- The digital literacy gap between low and high income countries is increasing. This may lead low-income countries facing greater challenges in adopting AI for deliberative processes.

Mitigation Strategies

- Foster cross-party dialogue on AI's role in deliberative democracy.
- Develop laws regulating AI in political processes e.g., elections, policy formation, and civic dialogue.
- Support transparency in AI-influenced political decisions (e.g., showing how input was processed).
- Take a long-term policy view related to the use of AI in deliberative democracy.
- Educate political leaders and decision-makers on responsible AI adoption (non-educated political actors may be over-confident in using unverified AI tools, or hesitate to use anything new)
- Publicly support labs that prototype and evaluate AI tools for democratic use, focusing on inclusivity, safety, and legitimacy.
- Consider establishing a Democratic AI Deliberation Observatory to monitor and assess AI's evolving role in democratic processes. This could include the development of standardized indicators for assessing democratic impact of AI
- Support Citizen AI Governance Councils to enable public oversight and co-creation of AI policy.
- Reduce dependency on foreign AI providers by supporting EU AI

3.3.2.6 Comparative analysis

This subsection presents a comparative analysis of the five uncertainty categories presented in the previous subsections. The assessment revealed that the uncertainty categories do not have big variations in both likelihood and impact scores. Many categories are interrelated, with changes in one domain likely affecting others. This interdependence underscores the need for integrated strategic approaches that take into account interactions between technological, political, organizational, and societal dimensions.

The following diagram (F.23) presents the mean likelihood and mean impact of all five uncertainty categories. The category “Social & Trust” is the one with the highest scores in both followed by the “Political”. One observation is that three categories (“Social & Trust”, “Political” and “Technological”) have greater values in Impact while the rest (“Legal & Ethical” and “Organizational”) have greater values in Likelihood. The uncertainty categories where impact exceeded likelihood indicate areas where potential consequences are significant despite being considered less probable.

Figure 23: Mean Likelihood and Impact Scores for Uncertainty Categories Identified in the Delphi Study

The following diagram (F.24) presents the overall risk score (Likelihood x Impact). Based on this score, the two most important categories are the “Social & Trust” and the “Political”. These two categories are the ones that drive the two intermediate scenarios presented in the next section.

Figure 24: Overall risk score for Uncertainty Categories Identified in the Delphi Study

The following table (T.12) presents detailed numbers of the Likelihood, Impact and overall score of all uncertainty categories.

Table 12: Quantitative Results from the Delphi Study

Uncertainty Category	Mean Likelihood	Mean Impact	Overall score (Likelihood x Impact)
Social & trust	4,8	4,9	23,7
Political	4,1	4,4	17,9
Technological	3,9	4,1	16,0
Legal & Ethical	3,9	3,5	13,9
Organizational	4	3,4	13,8

A feedback received from Delphi highlights that individual uncertainty categories are likely to vary significantly depending on contextual factors such as national digital infrastructure, levels of digital literacy, regulatory maturity, and civic engagement. As such, any strategic planning or policy intervention must be tailored to reflect local conditions.

Another finding is the relatively lower impact rating assigned to organizational uncertainty. This may reflect an assumption of institutional resilience or adaptability; however, it also signals a potential underestimation of the challenges related to organizational change, capacity building, and digital transformation in public sector institutions.

3.4 Four future Scenarios

The Delphi findings (positive/negative developments, drivers of positive developments, causes of failure and mitigation strategies, short narratives about the future of deliberative democracy) were synthesized into **four scenarios exploring how AI might shape deliberative democracy by 2030**. Each scenario reflects different ways technologies, policies, and societal factors could co-evolve, based on critical uncertainties identified during the Delphi process. This approach offers a structured way to assess the resilience and adaptability of possible futures. The four scenarios include:

- A “**Utopia**” future where AI strengthens deliberative democracy.
- A “**Dystopia**” future where AI undermines deliberative democracy.
- An intermediate scenario where “**Utopia**” is **disrupted by negative Social and Trust** developments: “**The Broken Promise: AI's Democratic Potential Undone by Collapse of Trust and Social Division**”.
- An intermediate scenario where “**Utopia**” is **disrupted by negative Political** developments: “**AI Democracy Hijacked: AI-Powered Deliberative Democracy Undermined by Political Manipulation and Polarization**”

3.4.1 Utopia: AI empowers deliberative democracy

The ethical and inclusive integration of artificial intelligence has transformed deliberative democracy across Europe into a fundamentally revitalized system by 2030. AI now functions as a reliable democratic partner instead of a threat to democratic systems, while it supports institutions and enables citizen empowerment at large scales.

Digital deliberation platforms operate across all devices while supporting multiple languages and have become widespread throughout society. AI tools simplify complex policy matters for citizens who participate voluntarily through meaningful interactions. The combination of multimodal interfaces and personal AI agents creates customized participation experiences which respect all users equally while focusing on marginalized communities. Public digital literacy campaigns, along with inclusive design principles, create an environment where everyone can participate without exclusion.

AI functions with complete transparency, explainability and ethical standards to enhance human reasoning without taking its place. The open-source, decentralized structure of deliberative platforms enables users to see algorithmic operations while protecting their data privacy. Personal bots initiate voting dialogue with citizens to encourage reflective thought before elections. AI technology provides multiple perspective summaries and policy outcome simulations and consensus identification to help people understand different viewpoints better and decrease political polarization.

Public institutions use AI technology as a means to enhance their responsiveness instead of implementing control measures. Combining independent audits, citizen co-design workshops and democratic oversight bodies helps to maintain AI accountability. Legal frameworks that adapt to technological speed include explainability features alongside fairness standards and bias reduction measures, while community ethics charters serve to govern AI at the local level. The “trust marks” system serves as a certification standard for organizations that follow democratic principles.

The deliberative process maintains full audibility and traceability through blockchain technology and zero-knowledge proof systems. The process allows citizens to monitor the impact of their contributions on the final decisions. Public trust increases when feedback processes are transparent because they demonstrate the validity of participatory mechanisms. AI systems function to detect false information while fighting it to maintain productive and fact-based discussions.

The implementation of AI-supported deliberations creates stronger civic solidarity instead of separating people from each other. Digital facilitators assist citizens during deliberation to reveal common values and to present disagreements in a respectful manner. Deliberation functions as a civic habit which exists across all scales from local to national to cross-national levels. People and AI now co-govern in a continuous process which operates through synchronized collaboration.

AI transforms governance in this optimistic future beyond mere improvement. The technology strengthens group problem-solving abilities while making democracy more

robust and building stronger public trust. Democracy will not merely endure the AI era by 2030. It's thriving because of it.

3.4.2 Dystopia: AI undermines deliberative democracy

In 2030, the promise of AI-enhanced democratic participation has transformed into an actual system which uses manipulation and exclusion alongside algorithmic control. The remaining elements of deliberative democracy exist as an artificial construct which political and corporate leaders use to create the appearance of public engagement while maintaining their own power base.

The deliberative platforms use opaque, commercially driven AI systems which focus on engaging numbers instead of inclusive practices. Recommendation engines use advanced algorithms to push emotionally charged content which creates ideological bubbles that suppress dissenting opinions. The system removes controversial topics through automated processes while producing predictable outcomes that support established power groups.

AI technologies produce massive amounts of false information which damages citizens' capacity to distinguish fact from fiction. Trust in institutions has collapsed. Deliberative processes become symbolic, as citizens are forced to rely on opaque, black-box systems to interpret how decisions are truly made. The outcome results in public disengagement and widespread apathy together with disillusionment.

The digital divide, along with inaccessible AI interfaces, creates additional exclusion for marginalized communities who already receive inadequate service. The lack of technical skills and advanced digital tools makes certain groups invisible to the deliberative process. AI-driven influence works like a market, where the highest bidder gains access. Voting, engagement, and representation become commodities that benefit the wealthy while creating unfair advantages for the less privileged.

The government lacks both regulatory ability and political determination to control deliberative processes. So they transfer deliberation duties to private AI platforms. Legal systems fail to keep pace with technological advancements. The oversight system remains weak, while cross-sector collaboration has failed and long-term democratic planning has been replaced by reactive policies which follow geopolitical pressures and lobbying interests.

The breakdown of civic relationships occurs because people become trapped in opposing realities, created specifically for each individual. The public discussion breaks into separate fragments while social media virality takes precedence over logical reasoning and politicians choose to represent popular social media content instead of public opinions. The transformation of citizens into mere data points leads to their complete loss of belief in their ability to influence societal development.

The emergence of Artificial Super intelligence (ASI) by 2030 has accelerated the deterioration in democracy. People surrender to AI policy decisions because they believe technology outperforms human judgment, thus they choose AI entertainment over democratic debates. The process of deliberation has evolved into a passive system which separates into distinct

layers while becoming superficial. The democratic system maintains its outward aspect but has lost its operational capabilities.

In this dystopian future, AI has not overthrown democracy, it has quietly replaced it. What remains is a technocratic illusion of participation, driven by algorithms that prioritize efficiency, control, and profit over dialogue, inclusion, and collective reasoning.

3.4.3 The Broken Promise: AI's Democratic Potential Undone by Collapse of Trust and Social Division

The technical infrastructure needed for AI-enhanced deliberative democracy becomes operational by 2030, but the social structure begins to deteriorate. The combination of advanced platforms and well-designed legal and ethical safeguards failed to prevent the complete breakdown of public trust in AI systems. The Utopian vision, which appeared promising ten years ago, has become a vacant shell because of widespread distrust and political fragmentation and public disinterest.

The initial success of civic AI projects collapsed because several major scandals revealed how AI systems received secret programming that served commercial and political agendas. The public began questioning algorithmic decision-making because its reasoning processes remained unclear and its biases went unaddressed. The public discovered that privacy protections were violated which sparked widespread anger and destroyed the faith that citizens had in their empowerment tools.

The population divides into two opposing groups known as “Tech Believers” and “Technophobics” as society separates into these distinct factions. AI deliberation tools have become instruments of exclusion, according to marginalized communities, who have always doubted centralized technologies. The absence of institutional trust allows misinformation to spread rapidly which damages the already weak foundation of digital democracy.

The number of participants on digital deliberative platforms decreases dramatically while civic engagement weakens. The public's perception of reality takes precedence over actual technical transparency, which is guaranteed through open-source code and public audits. The emotionally charged environment, which stems from surveillance fears and manipulation concerns and cultural disconnection, makes the platforms appear untrustworthy to the public. People choose to disengage from public life because they believe their voices either go unheard or get taken advantage of.

The technology which used to unite people now drives them apart. Social media algorithms which focus on user engagement create stronger filter bubbles that enhance divisive content distribution. Rapid pace of technological change creates psychological exhaustion which affects people who struggle to maintain their technological capabilities. The few who remain in deliberative democracy create echo chambers while the majority of people choose to remain silent.

Government institutions try to respond through algorithm disclosure and oversight council creation and digital literacy program launches, but their initiatives arrive too late and remain

fragmented. Political actors use the current unrest to portray AI governance as elitist and unaccountable to the public. The public demonstrates rising opposition against "machine governance" which leads to the breakdown of civic solidarity.

The Broken Promise of Empowerment: Technically, AI platforms continue to function. But socially, they are broken. Trust as a fragile yet essential component of democracy, has frayed. The initial attempt at participatory innovation through AI ends in disappointment because the emotional, cultural and historical issues that AI cannot fix remain unaddressed.

Here, AI's democratic promise is unrealized, not because it failed to work, but because people stopped believing it ever could.

3.4.4 AI Democracy Hijacked: AI-Powered Deliberative Democracy Undermined by Political Manipulation and Polarization

The dream of AI-powered democratic renewal has been corrupted from within by 2030. The technical strength and ethical foundation of deliberative platforms have led to their transformation into political manipulation instruments. The infrastructure for inclusive and transparent civic engagement remains intact, but its legitimacy has been purposefully damaged.

Sophisticated AI systems, which were created to support informed dialogue now serve as political weapons for their users. Advanced language models produce synthetic participation at scale by generating orchestrated content which floods deliberative platforms. Developers who support particular political views build hidden algorithmic biases into their systems, which direct discussions toward specific predetermined results. The high level of participation consists of staged events that follow predetermined scripts.

AI systems now function as tools to strengthen partisan messages while exploiting social divisions instead of helping people make thoughtful decisions. Political operatives use platform dynamics to exploit algorithmic weaknesses which enables them to manipulate public opinion. The opposing views either get eliminated by "bot storms" or get discredited through accusations of algorithmic bias. People start to doubt whether their participation leads to real deliberation or if they are trapped in a sophisticated simulation.

The democratic system faces legitimacy problems because politicians choose to present AI-generated data that supports their positions, but ignore opposing findings as invalid. The collapse of public confidence occurs because people now view deliberative processes as propaganda tools instead of democratic empowerment mechanisms. The combination of cyberattacks on political bots and foreign influence concerns intensifies public worries about the situation.

Well-funded actors utilize AI capabilities to deliver targeted content that polarizes specific voter segments through micro-targeted persuasion methods. The power dynamics of deliberation have shifted from a collective process to a data-based competition that benefits only those who possess technological and financial resources. The technological advantages

of well-funded actors make it impossible for smaller civic groups and marginalized communities to express themselves effectively.

The adoption of Artificial Superintelligence (ASI) leads to an accelerated movement toward centralized decision-making, which results in the abandonment of democratic principles. Political governments choose to use Artificial Superintelligence (ASI) for decision-making because they want to avoid geopolitical disadvantages. The public strongly reduces their participation in civic activities because they believe deliberative spaces have been captured by manipulative political forces, which render them useless.

AI functions to serve power rather than the public good in this transformed world. People step away from public activities because they doubt the participatory nature of systems, which actually operate under political agendas that remain hidden from view. The calculated misuse of AI in a polarized political environment leads to the erosion of trust, transparency and legitimacy rather than any failure of the technology.

3.5 Visual representation of results - DebateGraph

The outcomes of the Technology Foresight are visually depicted using DebateGraph, which is a collaborative online platform designed to illustrate complex issues and their interconnections clearly. Specifically, in DebateGraph are included:

- The five categories of uncertainty
- And for each category are included all the positive/negative developments, drivers of positive developments, causes of failure and mitigation strategies

The DebateGraph link of the results is the following:

<https://debategraph.org/Stream.aspx?nid=731338&vt=ngraph&dc=all>

The aim is to use DebateGraph throughout the project lifecycle, enabling the further refining and improvement of the outcomes as the project evolves.

The following figures show some visualisations of the results from DebateGraph.

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Figure 25: Outline view of the Technology Foresight results using Debateraph

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Figure 26: Tree-radial view of the Technology Foresight results using Debateraph

Figure 27: Graph view of the Technology Foresight results using Debateraph

3.4.Conclusion

This section presents the outcomes of the Technology Foresight exercise aimed at exploring the future use of AI in deliberative democracy by 2030. We employed a structured and

multi-phase methodology, involving a comprehensive literature review, exploratory survey, Delphi method, scenario planning, and stress testing. The aim was to assess the uncertainties and potential futures related to the integration of AI in democratic processes.

The primary contribution of this work is the identification of four distinct future scenarios that reflect different possibilities for AI's role in deliberative democracy. The "Utopia" scenario envisions AI operating at its full potential, enhancing democratic processes by addressing ethical, legal, and technical challenges. In contrast, the "Dystopia" scenario anticipates the worst-case outcomes, where AI undermines democratic values. Two intermediate scenarios, disrupted by key uncertainties in social trust and political factors, further highlight the complexity of the challenges ahead.

The insights derived mainly through two Delphi rounds and aim to provide valuable perspectives for policymakers and stakeholders. The produced scenarios offer a framework for exploring strategic options, understanding potential risks, and preparing for alternative futures. The DebateGraph platform will serve as a living document, allowing for ongoing consultation and refinement of the foresight results as new insights emerge over the lifetime of the project.

The Technology Foresight process highlights the need for forward-thinking and adaptable planning in the uncertain world of AI and deliberative democracy. The outcomes are not predictions, but scenarios that can guide future decisions and policies, helping ensure AI supports democratic deliberations rather than undermining them.

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4. Stakeholder needs & considerations on using AI in deliberations

This chapter of deliverable D1.1 is the outcome of “Task 1.3 - Stakeholders' needs & considerations on using AI in deliberations”. This is the third task of Work Package 1, “Demystify digital Deliberations.” The main objective of this task is to elicit stakeholders' needs and considerations on using AI in deliberations. The expected results are the creation of detailed scenarios, functional/non-functional requirements, epics, user stories, and a product backlog containing project activities. Based on those, we aim to create over 30 user stories with information provided by over 100 people, from over 4 countries, which also consist of the KPIs of this Task.

This section consists of three main subsections that present the approach followed to achieve the main objective, the expected results, and the outcomes of the following steps.

4.1 Methodological Approach

In this section, we present the main approach of Task 1.3 of Work Package 1. To achieve the main objective and produce the expected results, we used standard elicitation techniques (Wieggers & Beatty, 2013), including document analysis (literature review), questionnaires, and interviews. The detailed process is presented below. After every step, the final product (i.e., questionnaire, semi-structured interviews, requirements, product backlog, etc.) was reviewed by the whole consortium, in some cases through multiple rounds of feedback (e.g., steps 2 to 4).

Step 1. Literature analysis. In this step, we collected and summarized the findings of task 1.1 to extract requirements provided by the literature.

Step 2. Pilots' citizens' opinion. In this step, we created a questionnaire (consent form included) to ask the opinion of citizens on using AI in deliberations. This questionnaire was distributed (through the EUSurvey tool) to the four project pilots and translated into their native language.

Step 3. Pilots' employees' opinion. In this step, we created and translated a semi-structured interview (consent form included) in order to gather the opinions and considerations on using AI in deliberations of some pilot personnel.

Step 4. Best practice case owners' and platform owners' considerations. In this step, we created and translated a semi-structured interview (consent form included) to gather the opinions and considerations on using AI in deliberations of best practice case owners (i.e., people who have done deliberations and used various deliberation processes) and platform owners identified in task 1.1.

Step 5. Ethics approval. Based on the content of the survey (i.e., it did not included any personal information - use of consent form) and interviews with pilots' employees (project's internal stakeholders - use of consent form), best practice case owners, and platform owners

(interviewees were respective experts in their field and not part of any vulnerable groups - use of consent form), the advice of the project's Ethics Manager was that we were not obligated to apply for an ethics approval. However, we applied for and received ethics approval from the ethics committee of the Center of Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) for the following:

- The English and Greek versions of the survey questionnaire.
- The Greek version of the semi-structured interview for pilot employees.
- The semi-structured interview for the best practice case owners.
- The semi-structured interview for the platform owners.

Step 6. Requirements extraction, use case diagram, scenarios, and Product Backlog. In this step, we analyzed the findings of the previous steps, and we extracted functional and non-functional requirements, epics, and user stories; based on these, we created the system's Use Case diagram, three different scenarios, and an initial product backlog with the suggested project's activities.

Step 7. German citizens' opinion. In this step, we employed an external polling company to gather the opinions and considerations of citizens in Germany on using AI in deliberations.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Findings in Literature regarding requirements

During Task 1.1 of the same work package, research was conducted to review the literature regarding various aspects of the use of AI in deliberations. Based on the findings, we summarized and extracted some requirements. This step is very important to see what has already been done and tested in the literature and what actually works.

More specifically, we searched for

- The affordances and drawbacks of digitally mediated democratic deliberation
- Existing deliberation formats
- Existing platforms
- AI features that are used in deliberations
- Available approaches to argumentation mining
- Evaluation models for AI
- Institutionalization frameworks

The extracted requirements from the corresponding sections of T1.1 are imported into the requirements tables (T. 13 - 14).

4.2.2 Survey using questionnaire (citizens)

4.2.2.1 Survey Demographics and AI Adoption

In this survey, 282 people from 7 countries answered the questionnaire (Appendix E). The population was mostly people from Greece. A few of them also come from Italy and Germany. There were also a few from Belgium, Luxembourg, the UK, and the US (F.30). 52% were between 35 and 54, and 27% were 55-64 years old (F.28). Nearly 60% had advanced degrees, mainly master's and PhDs (F.29).

Figure 28. "Participants Overview I" - A visual representation of participants age and gender

Figure 29. "Participants Overview II" - A visual representation of participants' education level

Figure 30. "Participants Overview III" - A visual representation of participants' country in the map

According to the survey, various AI tools appeared across different educational backgrounds. People with PhDs expressed the strongest support. 61.3% of participants with a PhD rated AI as "definitely helpful", slightly above bachelor's degree holders (60.8%) and even higher than those with master's degrees (54.7%). People with associate degrees or vocational certificates showed more reserved positivity. Around 37.5% found AI "definitely helpful", while 43.8% saw it as "probably helpful" (F.31). The data revealed that more education typically means more appreciation for AI features, challenging the assumption that higher academic achievement might breed greater AI distrust.

Figure 31. "Education Level vs. AI Adoption" - Correlation between education level and AI adoption

Figure 32. "Age vs. AI Adoption" - Correlation between age and AI adoption

The study also identified applications of artificial intelligence used by the participants in everyday activities. Scholarly activities, summarization of extensive texts, and simplification of complex ideas were among the activities used by students and teachers. Thesis composition, idea development, and academic writing organization were also mentioned.

Increased productivity in workspaces was reported, too. Creating reports, solving programming issues, and analyzing large pools of data seem easier with the use of such tools. A lot of participants also highlighted how AI tools took over simple, repetitive manual tasks and speeded up routine processes. People also described numerous applications outside work and education. These range from translation services to visual representations. Figure 33 presents different tasks where participants use AI tools.

Figure 33. "AI Application Domains" - Breakdown of different contexts where users apply AI tools

Despite all the advantages AI tools offer in various tasks and contexts, survey respondents also highlighted some concerns (F.34). Numerous individuals expressed annoyance when the technologies presented incorrect data with complete confidence. Such encounters convinced many participants that while these tools perform well for generating ideas and managing routine tasks, people still need to check the results to ensure they're correct.

Additionally, a few participants noted that in more complex tasks (e.g., nuanced coding processes or specialized research inquiries), AI responses sometimes lacked the required depth or precision. This indicates that although AI can be a valuable assistant in various domains, its effectiveness may be constrained when addressing highly specialized or intricate problems.

Figure 34. Identified problems by using AI

4.2.2.2 Key findings regarding the use of AI in deliberations

Feedback shows consensus among participants that AI would be a useful tool, but in no way could it completely replace humans and human thinking. Some key points raised are:

- AI is best positioned as a facilitator that enhances and supports human involvement
- Democratic supervision of AI systems remains essential
- Preserving the human element is vital.

The participants highlighted several valuable applications of AI that could enhance deliberations. **Translations** in various languages (including sign language) to facilitate the inclusion of more people, especially from marginalized populations, **Information Management** for providing relevant data, constructing models, calculating potential outcomes, and verifying information during real-time discussions, **Visual representations** of complex datasets, and **Coordination**, including meeting notifications, and calendar scheduling.

Furthermore, there are also very important findings regarding some specific AI features e.g., Discussion summarization, Discussion moderation, Fact-checking, Translation services, Identifying areas of agreement, Suggesting alternative perspectives, Processing user feedback, and Tracking discussion patterns (F.35).

	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
Translationservices	282	4,10	,057	,959	,920
Factchecking	282	3,89	,061	1,028	1,056
Discussionsummarization	282	3,88	,060	1,000	1,000
Identifyingareasofagreement	282	3,70	,055	,920	,846
Suggestingalternativeperspectives	282	3,68	,061	1,021	1,042
Processinguserfeedback	282	3,68	,062	1,046	1,095
Trackingdiscussionpatterns	282	3,60	,063	1,063	1,131
Discussionmoderation	282	3,53	,062	1,047	1,097
Valid N (listwise)	282				

Figure 35. Descriptive statistics regarding AI features (N(Statistic):sample size, Mean(Statistic):average score of each item, Mean (Std. Error):how much the sample mean is expected to vary from the true population mean, Std. Deviation (Statistic):the amount of variability or spread in the responses, Variance(Statistic):measures variability in squared units)

As we can see in Figure 35, translation services, fact-checking, and discussion summarization are considered the most valuable features, while discussion moderation and tracking discussion patterns seem less important for users. Furthermore, looking at the std. deviation, we can see unanimous support among respondents for features like translation services and identifying areas of agreement, while the opinions are more divided regarding features like tracking discussion patterns and processing user feedback.

We also have information about specific items (functionalities and others) (F.36) and the opinions of citizens regarding their importance. The data reveals that citizens prefer functions that support decisions and promote transparency. Among the most important functions are functions that allow users to flag AI-generated summaries for errors and suggest improvements, help users understand AI decision-making, and give them access to public audit logs of AI activity. In contrast, items about user anonymity or personalization seem less important (like uploading an avatar instead of a photo, participating under a pseudonym, and suggesting topics based on user preferences). Additionally, these functions show higher variance, reflecting more divided opinions.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
ID1 flag the AI generated summaries of discussions for errors	282	4,53	,823	,677
ID10 know how and why AI acts when contributing to discussions	282	4,37	,943	,888
ID11 save and make public IY available audit logs of significant	282	4,34	,931	,866
ID12 provide feedback on AI features and participate in their improvement	282	4,30	,950	,902
ID6 allow users to suggest improvements to automatic translation	282	4,24	,956	,915
ID5 provide clear explanations when content is identified as a spot	282	4,13	1,072	1,149
ID4 flag potentially misleading information	282	4,07	1,066	1,137
ID9 provide evidence for the suggested different perspectives	282	3,98	1,024	1,050
ID3 suggest relevant sources and evidence during discussions	282	3,89	,966	,934
ID8 connected with different perspectives on the topics being discussed	282	3,79	1,050	1,103
ID14 recognize meaningful contributions through contextualized data	282	3,65	1,113	1,238
ID13 civic engagement incentives to encourage meaningful participation	282	3,58	1,197	1,433
ID17 allow participation in discussions via audio	282	3,57	1,149	1,320
ID16 allow participation in discussions via video	282	3,49	1,157	1,340
ID2 actively moderate monitor or regulate facilitated discussion	282	3,27	1,037	1,075
ID7 suggest deliberations and topics based on your preferences	282	3,11	1,068	1,140
ID18 option of participating under a pseudonym instead of your name	282	3,07	1,345	1,810
ID15 option to upload an avatar instead of using your profile picture	282	2,98	1,358	1,843
Valid N (listwise)	282			

Figure 36. Items' importance (N: sample size, Mean: average score of each item, Std. Deviation: the amount of variability or spread in the responses, Variance: measures variability in squared units)

Finally, the survey also reveals some concerns regarding the use of AI in deliberations:

- **Confidentiality and data security:** Protection of personal data, biometric elements, and sensitive information.
- **Reliability and accuracy:** Concerns about false information (hallucinations), misleading conclusions, and simplification of complex issues.
- **Bias and limitations:** Fears of biased presentation of views and information.
- **Impersonal communication:** Concerns about the dehumanization of dialogue.
- **Control and transparency:** Considerations regarding who controls the AI and how transparent the processes are.

4.2.3 Interviews

This subsection presents a summary of the interviews that we have conducted within Task 1.3 with pilot employees, best practice case owners, and platform owners.

In total, we have conducted eighteen interviews with pilot employees (Semi-structured interview in Appendix F): two interviews with the International Pilot, five interviews with the Italian pilot, six interviews with the Greek pilot, and five interviews with the German pilot. During these interviews, we aimed to gather pilots' needs regarding the use of AI in deliberations. This was an effective way to capture diverse, real-time insights directly from people who engage with processes and tools daily.

Regarding the interviews with the best practice case owners and the platform owners (Appendix G and H respectively; consent forms can be found in Appendix I), we reached out to many people in these categories, and we received positive responses from 11 in total. During these interviews, we aimed to obtain critical information about deliberation processes and platforms with or without AI features, from people who have already successfully implemented similar platforms or processes.

In general, we identified a lot of suggested functionalities from the interviewees. Among them, the system should support different deliberate processes, including debates and voting in both synchronous and asynchronous ways. Also, the results suggest that the system should use AI capabilities in order to provide summaries, classify arguments, moderate discussions, and automate routine tasks. Furthermore, in the interviews, the need to interact using various formats (e.g., text, images, audio, and video) is highlighted. Additionally, the need to provide visualizations of outcomes and trends found great consensus among participants. Finally, distinct roles among users (e.g., admin and moderator) and collaboration with other systems (using APIs and plugins) were also mentioned.

Apart from the functionalities, other important features were also mentioned. Usability, accessibility, privacy, and security were some of them. Scale efficiency and adaptability were also prominent in responses. Finally, transparency and explainability of the AI interventions were pointed out. In the following section, the extracted requirements from the interviews are presented.

It is worth mentioning that the survey and all interviews were conducted according to the highest ethical standards, complying with EU, international, and national laws. The project

has undergone strict ethical review, with measures in place to secure informed consent and protect personal data. The project's Ethics Manager oversaw these processes, guaranteeing that all research and development activities respect fundamental rights and legal obligations.

4.2.4 Requirements

In this subsection, we list the requirements²⁶ as functional and non-functional based on the above results (sections 4.2.1 – 4.2.3). The extraction of requirements (T.13 and T.14) was completed manually, and in some cases, the ReqGenie (Fotrousi & Tavantzis, 2025) (in ChatGPT) and ChatGPT (in temporary mode) were used to check the manually extracted results. The requirements with similar meanings were grouped. Finally, it is important to mention that only fully anonymized text from the interviews was used in the previously mentioned tools.

Table 13: Functional Requirements (Citizens:C, Internal Interviews:I, Best Practice Case Owners and Platform Owners: E, Literature Review:L)

ID	Requirement	Source
F1	Summarization	
F1.1	The system should provide summaries of the discussions.	C, I, E, L
F1.2	The system should generate summaries in text.	C, I, E
F1.3	The system should generate summaries in audio.	C, I, E
F2	Moderation	
F2.1	The system shall automatically suggest discussion rules and flag inappropriate or harmful content.	C, I, E, L
F2.2	The system shall use AI to moderate (monitor, regulate, facilitate) discussions to ensure inclusiveness.	C, I, E, L
F2.3	The system should have content moderation tools, including reporting, flagging, and reviewing.	E, L
F2.4	The system should have administrator/moderator tools (delete, approve, categorize).	E, L
F2.5	The system should highlight positive engagement.	L
F2.6	The system should offer structured sessions where users co-set rules of engagement, assisted by templates or AI agents.	L

²⁶ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc2119>

ID	Requirement	Source
F3	Fact-Checking	
F3.1	The system shall identify factual claims and provide verified information to ensure accuracy during discussions.	C, I, E
F3.2	The system shall enable the AI to flag potentially misleading information.	C, I
F3.3	The system shall provide evidence when addressing misinformation.	C, I
F3.4	The system should have a shared repository of trusted resources.	L
F4	Translation	
F4.1	The system shall offer automated translation of discussion content to support multilingual participation.	C, I, E, L
F4.2	The system shall automatically translate audio or video content into sign language.	C, I
F4.3	The system shall translate technical, legal, and general complex language into plain language to ensure clarity and ease of understanding.	C, I, E, L
F5	Identifying Areas of Agreement	
F5.1	The system shall automatically cluster similar arguments or points and identify shared categories to highlight areas of agreement in discussions and reduce repetitive overload.	C, I, E, L
F6	Gamification	
F6.1	The system shall recognize meaningful contributions through contextualized achievements that reflect the quality and impact of participation (e.g., bridging opposing viewpoints, elevating evidence-based discussion, fostering inclusive dialogue, and community-building karma).	C, I, E, L
F6.2	The system shall include civic engagement incentives (such as deliberation expertise badges, consensus-building achievements, and dialogue quality recognition) to encourage meaningful participation.	C, I, E, L

ID	Requirement	Source
F6.3	The platform should have AI-gamified onboarding modules to establish trust.	L
F7	Suggesting Alternative Perspectives	
F7.1	The system shall propose diverse viewpoints to enrich discussions and support critical thinking.	C, E, L
F7.2	The system shall provide evidence for the suggested different perspectives.	C
F8	User Feedback	
F8.1	The system shall analyze user feedback to prioritise updates and improvements to AI features and discussion tools.	C, I
F8.2	The system shall enable users to flag AI-generated summaries for errors or inaccuracies.	C
F8.3	The system shall allow users to suggest improvements to automatic (AI) translations.	C
F8.4	The system shall enable users to provide feedback on deliberation processes they have used or participated in.	I
F9	Tracking Discussion Patterns	
F9.1	The system shall monitor discussion engagement patterns and dynamics to support improvements in future deliberations.	C
F9.2	The system shall enable the AI to suggest deliberations and topics based on user preferences and previous activity.	C
F9.3	The system shall group and classify information by themes or topics.	C
F10	Participation Features	
F10.1	The system shall allow users to upload an avatar or a photo.	C
F10.2	The system shall allow participation in discussions via video.	C
F10.3	The system shall allow participation in discussions via audio.	C

ID	Requirement	Source
F10.4	The system should allow users to have control over their identification level (e.g., using a pseudonym instead of their name or avatar instead of their photo).	C, I, E
F10.5	The system should allow only read (anonymous) access.	I
F10.6	The system should support synchronous (e.g., chat, live meetings/events) deliberations.	I, E
F10.7	The system should support asynchronous (e.g., forums, comment threads) deliberations.	I, E, L
F10.8	The system should facilitate various deliberative processes, such as debates, consultations, vote & justification, Q&A sessions, collaborative drafting (e.g., legislation), participatory budgeting, and deliberative polling.	I, E
F11	Transparency & Accountability	
F11.1	The system shall provide users with information on how and why AI acts when contributing to discussions (e.g., content moderation, summarization, consensus building).	C, I, L
F11.2	The system shall save and make publicly available audit logs of significant AI interventions in discussions (e.g., content removal, fact-checking decisions, consensus summaries).	C, I, L
F11.3	The system shall ensure the AI provides clear explanations when content is identified as potentially misleading.	C, I, L
F11.4	The system should provide mechanisms to show participants how their input and contributions were considered or used.	I, L
F11.5	The system should provide updates on policy outcomes influenced by the completed deliberations.	L
F12	Analysis & Visualization & Communication	
F12.1	The system should generate reports in various forms (e.g., open data, CSV, XML) and provide data visualizations like diagrams, knowledge graphs, simulations, fact cards, and 3D visual representations (if possible, in real-time).	C, I, E, L

ID	Requirement	Source
F12.2	The system should incorporate metrics (e.g., argument quality, civility, knowledge change) that reflect both procedural and outcome-focused deliberation quality.	L
F12.3	The system should allow users to create and submit content in various formats, including text, images, audio, video, files, and comments.	C, I, E
F12.4	The system should utilize tools (with AI) to collect, track, archive, and analyse process data (e.g., participation rates, discussion activity, task completion, outcomes) for monitoring, evaluation, accountability, and benchmarking.	I, E
F12.5	The system should have a chatbot for direct communication with the user.	I, E
F12.6	The system should include optional demographic or attitudinal surveys to gauge representativeness and address potential selection biases.	L
F13	Support	
F13.1	The system shall provide meeting reminders and support scheduling tasks.	C
F13.2	The system shall send discussion topics and agendas helping users find and focus on relevant threads.	C, L
F13.3	The system shall offer secretarial functions, including note-taking and follow-up messages with summary during synchronous deliberations.	C
F13.4	The system should employ individual AI-reasoning tools to help participants develop and refine their arguments.	L
F13.5	The system shall allow authorized users to upload training material to a centralized repository for access by other users.	I, E, L
F14	Registration & Authentication	
F14.1	The system should support registration and then log in with email/username.	I, E

ID	Requirement	Source
F14.2	The system should support registration methods with government ID and with integration of government systems for verified identity.	I, E
F14.3	The system should include secure authentication mechanisms (e.g., multi-factor authentication, CAPTCHA).	I
F14.4	The system should ask for clear consent when needed (e.g., access to the camera or microphone).	I
F14.5	The system should ensure that the same user cannot have multiple accounts.	I, E
F15	Access Control & Permissions	
F15.1	The system should support distinct user roles (e.g., administrator, moderator, facilitator, participant/citizen, researcher, guest) with corresponding permissions for creating content, moderating, accessing data, and managing the system. Support multiple administrators per project/space.	I, E
F16	Personalization	
F16.1	The system should remember the user settings, especially for accessibility features.	I
F16.2	The system should allow users to create profiles and personalize their experience (e.g., dashboards, content feeds, shortcuts, notification preferences).	I, L
F16.3	The system should provide discovery and filtering mechanisms (e.g., topic tags, robust search) to help participants navigate extensive content and avoid information overload.	L
F17	Argument mining	
F17.1	The system should be able to extract/classify arguments.	E, L

Table 14. Non-Functional Requirements (Citizens:C, Internal Interviews:I, Best Practice Case Owners and Platform Owners: E, Literature Review:L)

ID	Requirement	Source
NF1	Security & Privacy	
NF1.1	The system must secure all user data, including discussions, participation logs, and feedback, during storage and transmission.	C, I, E
NF1.2	The system must ensure the privacy of users, particularly when using avatars or pseudonyms.	C, I, E, L
NF1.3	The system shall provide clear and transparent policies regarding data collection, storage, and usage.	C, I
NF1.4	The system must comply with current and emerging legal frameworks (national/international), including those related to AI applications (e.g., e.g., GDPR, local laws, potentially EU AI Act).	I, E
NF1.5	The AI models must be developed and trained responsibly to avoid inappropriate outputs (e.g., misinformation, offensive content, hate speech) and reproducing biases/errors. Requires ethical training and continuous evaluation.	I, E
NF1.6	The system's data should not be used for statistical purposes or to record political opinions and should be managed by an independent authority.	I
NF1.7	The system's commercial interests (if any) should be separated from the deliberation process.	L
NF2	Performance & Scalability & Adaptability	
NF2.1	The AI must deliver summarization, translation, moderation, and suggestions with minimal delay to maintain real-time interaction.	C, I, E
NF2.2	The system should support large discussions with many simultaneous users without loss of performance.	C, I, E
NF2.3	The system's architecture must support continuous development, improvements, and updates to keep pace with	I, E

ID	Requirement	Source
	evolving user needs, AI capabilities, deliberative practices, and legal requirements.	
NF2.4	The system should comply with standards for data handling and interoperability (e.g., DCAT-AP, Open Data Directive, CPSV-AP).	I
NF2.5	The system should be optimized for efficient use of resources, including bandwidth and power, potentially enabling operation under limited connectivity.	I, E
NF2.6	The system should be able to work with other systems and tools, such as video conferencing platforms, live streaming services (e.g., YouTube), external AI tools, government platforms (e.g., opengov.gr), regulatory instruments, external databases, and social media channels.	I, E
NF2.7	The system should function effectively across various cultural and geographic contexts.	E
NF3	Operational & Accessibility	
NF3.1	Interfaces for feedback, moderation, and participation should be user-friendly and accessible to users with various skill levels.	C, I, E, L
NF3.2	The system should comply with accessibility standards (e.g., WCAG) to support participation by users with disabilities.	C, I, E
NF3.3	The system should follow established usability principles (e.g., ISO 9241-110) and potentially use familiar UI patterns.	I, E
NF3.4	The system should be fully accessible and functional across various devices (smartphones, tablets, desktops) and operating systems (including specific mentions like Apple devices).	I, E, L
NF3.5	The system should utilize standardized, flexible communication protocols, APIs, and plugins (e.g., REST/JSON or WordPress plugins) for data exchange and integration with other systems.	I
NF3.6	The system should be open-source to enable transparency, customization and community involvement.	I, E
NF3.7	User authentication should be simple in order not to discourage participation.	I

ID	Requirement	Source
NF3.8	The system should be hosted online (e.g., Cloud-based like AWS).	I, E
NF3.9	The system should use outreach tools (email invites, social media campaigns, partnerships with community groups) to recruit participants from varied backgrounds.	L
NF4	Transparency & Auditability	
NF4.1	All AI contributions (e.g., moderation, summarization, flagging) must be explainable and understandable by users.	C, I, E
NF4.2	Platform ownership, funding sources, and data policies must be transparent.	L
NF5	Human Oversight	
NF5.1	The system shall include multiple levels of human control and supervision.	C, I, E
NF5.2	The system shall allow error identification and correction under human supervision.	C, I
NF6	Support	
NF6.1	Training material should exist in various formats (text guides, videos, tutorials, case studies, simulations, and audio) to support users and other roles (admin, moderators, etc.) for effective platform use.	I, E, L
NF7	Design	
NF7.1	Gamification must support meaningful participation, not just reward activity.	I, E, L

4.2.5 Use Case Diagram

This subsection contains the first proposed Use case diagram (F.37) for the AI4Deliberation system. In some cases, a slightly higher level was maintained to facilitate the reader's understanding.

Figure 37. Use case diagram of the AI4Deliberation System

4.2.6 Epics and User Stories

In this subsection, based on the requirements we extracted in section 4.2.4, we are recording the epics and user stories in the following table (T.15). In total, 24 epics and 95 user stories are recorded.

Table 15: Epics and User Stories

ID	User Story
E1	As a user, I want the system to summarise discussions both in text and audio so that I can read or hear the key points without reading the whole discussion.
US1.1	As a user, I want the system to automatically identify and extract important information from a discussion so that I can get an overview of what was said without reading the entire discussion.
US1.2	As a user, I want the system to generate a clear and comprehensive text summary of the discussion so that I can read the main points quickly.
US1.3	As a user, I want the system to generate an audio summary so that I can listen to the key points when reading is not possible.
E2	As an administrator, I want the system to have AI-supported moderation so that the discussions stay inclusive and safe.

ID	User Story
US2.1	As an administrator, I want the system to suggest discussion rules and automatically flag inappropriate or harmful content so that conversations stay respectful.
US2.2	As a user, I want the system to use AI to monitor and guide the conversation in real time so that discussions remain inclusive.
US2.3	As a user, I want to be able to report and flag inappropriate content so that unacceptable behaviors can be addressed quickly.
US2.4	As an administrator or moderator, I want the ability to delete, approve, and categorize posts or discussions so that I can maintain the structure and civility of the platform.
US2.5	As a platform owner, I want the system to provide acknowledgements of positive behavior so that appropriate interactions are encouraged in the community.
US2.6	As a community designer, I want the system to offer structured sessions where users can co-set rules, assisted by AI agents or ready templates so that discussions are grounded in shared expectations.
E3	As a facilitator, I want the system to provide AI fact-checking support to identify and verify arguments so that discussions remain trustworthy.
US3.1	As a user, I want the system to provide verified information for identified claims in real time so that I can rely on accurate content.
US3.2	As a moderator, I want the AI to automatically flag potentially misleading content so that I can quickly review and respond to questionable material.
US3.3	As a user, I want the system to provide evidence and explanations for flagged as misleading content so that I am aware of the reasons behind flagging.
US3.4	As a community member, I want to have access to a repository of trusted material so that I can verify information myself.
E4	As a user, I want automated translations and language simplification tools so that I can participate in deliberations no matter what language I speak or my knowledge background.
US4.1	As a user, I want the system to automatically translate discussions so that I can engage meaningfully in conversations without language barriers.

ID	User Story
US4.2	As a user, I want the system to translate audio or video content into sign language so that I can fully access and contribute to the discussion.
US4.3	As a user, I want the system to simplify complex language so that I can understand and participate in discussions that use difficult terminology.
E5	As a facilitator, I want the system to identify common ground and collect similar arguments so that consensus can be highlighted, promoting constructive discussions.
US5.1	As an administrator, I want the system to automatically group similar arguments and identify shared categories to reduce repetition and avoid information overload for users.
E6	As a platform owner, I want the system to reward high-quality contributions to motivate constructive participation in deliberations.
US6.1	As a platform owner, I want the system to recognize important contributions through achievements so that the platform rewards the behaviors that align with our goals.
US6.2	As a platform owner, I want the platform to include gamified incentives such as deliberation badges and consensus-building achievements so that users are encouraged to develop skills and behaviors that enhance democratic discourse.
US6.3	As a platform owner, I want the platform to offer AI-driven gamified onboarding processes so that new users are more likely to engage in respectful and high-quality deliberations.
E7	As a user, I want the system to offer alternative viewpoints supported with evidence, so that I can develop a more critical understanding of the topic based on reliable information.
US7.1	As a user, I want the system to suggest alternative viewpoints to my opinion so that I can consider new ideas.
US7.2	As a user, I want the system to provide reliable sources to support the alternative viewpoints so that I can verify the provided information.
E8	As a user, I want to give feedback on AI tools and processes and report issues so that I feel heard and motivated to stay engaged.

ID	User Story
US8.1	As a platform owner, I want the system to analyse user feedback and identify areas of improvement so that our development team can prioritize changes and updates.
US8.2	As a user, I want to be able to flag inaccurate AI-generated summaries so that the content quality remains high.
US8.3	As a user, I want to suggest improvements in the automated translations so that the platform can improve translation quality.
US8.4	As a user, I want to provide feedback on the deliberation processes that I have participated in so that the system administrators and facilitators can improve future deliberations.
E9	As a user, I want the system to analyze how discussions evolve and provide me with topic recommendations so that my experience is more engaging and meaningful.
US9.1	As a user, I want the system to analyse how people interact in discussions so that future discussions can be better structured and more engaging.
US9.2	As a user, I want the system to recommend topics aligned with my interests so that I can join discussions that are most interesting for me.
US9.3	As a user, I want discussions to be automatically grouped by themes or topics so that I can easily follow interesting deliberations.
E10	As a user, I want multiple ways to participate in discussions and control my identity visibility so that I can contribute comfortably and meaningfully to deliberations.
US10.1	As a user, I want to upload an avatar or photo for my profile so that I can personalise my presence in discussions.
US10.2	As a user, I want the option to join discussions using video so that I can express myself more clearly and connect directly with other participants.
US10.3	As a user, I want to contribute using audio so that I can participate, although I have specific accessibility needs.
US10.4	As a user, I want to choose whether to use my real identity or not so that I can participate while protecting my privacy.

ID	User Story
US10.5	As a platform administrator, I want to allow users to view content without logging in so that they can just inform themselves from different deliberations.
US10.6	As a platform owner, I want users to participate in live events (e.g., live chat or video events) so that they can participate in real time deliberations and connect with others directly.
US10.7	As a platform owner, I want asynchronous formats that promote reflection and deliberation depth, so that engagement quality is prioritised over speed.
US10.8	As a platform owner, I want the platform to support various deliberative processes, such as debates, consultations, vote & justification, Q&A sessions, collaborative drafting (e.g., legislation), participatory budgeting, and deliberative polling, often following pre-defined or customizable workflows.
E11	As a user, I want transparent and accountable AI behavior, so that everyone can trust the system's interventions, understand AI decisions and see how users' input affects policy outcomes.
US11.1	As a user, I want the system to explain how and why the AI takes specific actions so that I can understand the reasons behind AI involvement.
US11.2	As a user, I want the system to log and publish significant AI interventions (e.g., content removal, consensus summaries), so that AI behavior is accountable, traceable, and auditable by the public and the platform administrators.
US11.3	As a user, I want the AI to provide clear and comprehensible explanations when identifying content as misleading so that I can challenge incorrect decisions or correct my input in good faith.
US11.4	As a system designer, I want to highlight user contributions in update notes or notifications so that transparency and trust are increased.
US11.5	As a user, I want periodic updates on how the discussions influenced policies or decisions so that I see the real value of my input.
E12	As an administrator, I want the system to analyse, visualise, and communicate deliberation data and outcomes effectively so that everyone can engage meaningfully, evaluate deliberation quality, and support evidence-based decisions.

ID	User Story
US12.1	As a user, I want the system to be able to generate reports and provide data visualizations (e.g., CSV, XML, knowledge graphs, simulations, 3D visuals) so that I can explore results through visual representations.
US12.2	As a researcher, I want the system to have metrics (e.g., argument quality, civility, and knowledge change) so that I have more information about the quality of deliberations.
US12.3	As a user, I want to submit my contributions in various formats (text, images, videos, audio, files, surveys, proposals, etc.) so that I can express my ideas in different ways.
US12.4	As an administrator, I want the system to track and analyse participation data using AI (e.g., engagement rates, outcomes) so that I can monitor accountability and engagement.
US12.5	As a user, I want to interact with a chatbot that can provide direct communication, guidance, and feedback so that I can navigate the platform easily and with less effort.
US12.6	As a researcher, I want the system to offer optional demographic surveys so that I can have this kind of information for the deliberations.
E13	As a user, I want the system to support my engagement through reminders, agendas, and assistance so that I can participate more effectively.
US13.1	As a user, I want the system to send me reminders and support scheduling tasks so that I can avoid missing important deliberations (for live events) or important deadlines (for asynchronous discussions).
US13.2	As a user, I want the system to provide discussion topics and structured agendas so that I can easily find threads relevant to my interests.
US13.3	As a user, I want the system to offer secretarial functions like note-taking and follow-up summaries, so that I understand the discussions at my own pace.
US13.4	As a user, I want access to AI reasoning tools that help me develop and refine my arguments so that I can improve the quality of my input.
US13.5	As an admin, I want to upload training material such as documents, videos, audio, and presentations to the system so that users can use them in order to support their participation through learning.

ID	User Story
E14	As an administrator, I want the platform to offer secure, verified, and consent-based registration and login processes so that access is safe, trustworthy, and fair.
US14.1	As an administrator, I want to enable email/username-based registration so that users can quickly create accounts while I maintain a record of registrants.
US14.2	As an administrator, I want to support registration via government ID and integration with government identity systems so that I can validate users and ensure trusted participation.
US14.3	As an administrator, I want to enforce secure authentication mechanisms like multi-factor authentication and CAPTCHA, so that I can prevent unauthorized access and reduce the risk of automated or malicious login attempts.
US14.4	As an administrator, I want the platform to request explicit user consent when accessing personal devices (e.g., camera or microphone), so that I can ensure legal compliance and maintain user trust.
US14.5	As an administrator, I want the system to prevent users from creating multiple accounts so that I can maintain fairness, avoid duplicate voting or participation, and preserve data integrity.
E15	As a platform owner, I want to define and manage distinct user roles with specific permissions so that I can control who can create, view, manage, or moderate content and data in a secure and organized way.
US15.1	As an administrator, I want to create and assign roles such as administrator, moderator, facilitator, participant/citizen, researcher, and guest so that I can control the actions each user type can perform.
E16	As a platform administrator, I want the system to support personalized experiences through user profiles, saved preferences, and content discovery tools so that users can access content in a way that fits their needs and abilities, while I ensure accessibility, usability, and engagement across diverse participant groups.
US16.1	As a platform administrator, I want the system to remember each user's accessibility settings (e.g., font size, contrast mode, screen reader preferences), so that users with different needs can return to a consistent, usable experience without reconfiguring settings.

ID	User Story
US16.2	As a platform administrator, I want to enable users to create profiles and personalize their dashboards, content feeds, and notifications so that they can manage their experience based on roles, interests, and engagement style.
US16.3	As an admin, I want the system to provide powerful discovery tools like topic tagging, filtering, and advanced search so that participants can navigate large amounts of content without feeling overwhelmed.
E17	As a platform administrator, I want the system to automatically extract and classify arguments from user-generated content so that I can support structured, meaningful debates and provide tools for analyzing the positions of participants.
US17.1	As a platform administrator, I want the system to automatically extract and classify arguments from discussions so that I can enable more structured and secure deliberations.
E18	As a user, I want the system to prioritize data security, user privacy, and ethical AI practices so that I can trust it more.
US18.1	As a user, I want all user data (e.g., discussions, participation logs, feedback) to be securely stored and transmitted using encryption and best security practices so that the integrity and confidentiality of our data are protected against breaches.
US18.2	As a platform owner, I want the system to secure the users' data when they use pseudonymity or avatar so that users can participate without fear of social pressure or judgment.
US18.3	As a user, I want clear and accessible policies outlining what data is collected, how it's stored, and how it's used so that I can make informed decisions about my participation.
US18.4	As a platform owner, I want the system to comply with national and international regulations like GDPR and AI Act so that legal risks are minimized and user rights are protected.
US18.5	As a platform owner, I want AI models to be responsibly trained and continuously evaluated so that the system avoids misinformation, harmful content, or bias.
US18.6	As a platform owner, I want user data to be managed by an independent body to avoid using it for political profiling or statistical exploitation.

PENDING APPROVAL

ID	User Story
US18.7	As a researcher, I want any commercial activities to be strictly separated from the deliberative process so that trust in the system is maintained.
E19	As a platform owner, I want the system to perform AI-supported tasks in real time, scale efficiently for large participation, and adapt to evolving needs, technologies, and legal frameworks so that deliberative processes remain seamless and updated.
US19.1	As a user, I want AI functionalities to work with minimal delay so that I remain engaged in real time.
US19.2	As a platform owner, I want the system to support large numbers of simultaneous users without degrading performance so that participation can scale without loss of quality.
US19.3	As a platform owner, I want the system's architecture to allow continuous improvements and updates so that it can evolve with changing user feedback, AI capabilities, and legal standards.
US19.4	As an internal stakeholder, I want the system to comply with recognized data and interoperability standards (e.g., DCAT-AP, CPSV-AP) so that it can interact with other compliant platforms and datasets.
US19.5	As a platform owner, I want the system to be optimized for efficient use of bandwidth and power so that it can function reliably even in regions with limited connectivity or low-end hardware.
US19.6	As an internal stakeholder, I want the system to integrate smoothly with external tools like video conferencing platforms, government portals, and social media so that users have a unified and enriched deliberation experience.
US19.7	As a platform owner, I want the system to support multicultural contexts and adapt to regional user needs so that it can be deployed effectively across diverse locations and populations.
E20	As a user, I want the system to be easy to use, fully accessible, open, and operational across devices and networks so that people of all backgrounds and abilities can participate in deliberations.
US20.1	As a user, I want interfaces for feedback, moderation, and participation to be simple and intuitive so that I can engage easily regardless of my knowledge level.

ID	User Story
US20.2	As a user, I want the system to comply with accessibility standards like WCAG so that everyone can participate equally.
US20.3	As a UX designer, I want the system to follow usability principles (e.g., ISO 9241-110) and familiar UI standards so that users can navigate comfortably.
US20.4	As a user, I want the system to work seamlessly on smartphones, tablets, desktops, and across different operating systems like iOS and Android so that I can participate from anywhere, on any device.
US20.5	As a developer, I want the system to use standard protocols, APIs, and plugins (e.g., REST/JSON or WordPress plugin) so that it can easily exchange data and functionalities with other tools.
US20.6	As a developer, I want the system to be open-source so that it supports transparency, community auditing, and potential customization.
US20.7	As a UX designer, I want authentication to be straightforward so that it encourages participation instead of making it difficult.
US20.8	As a platform administrator, I want the platform to be hosted online, preferably via scalable cloud services like AWS so that it is resilient, secure, and easy to maintain.
US20.9	As a community organizer, I want the system to support communication tools (e.g., email invites, social media, local partnerships) so that I can reach people from various places easily.
E21	As a user, I want the system and the AI contributions to be transparent and explainable so that I can understand how decisions are made.
US21.1	As a user, I want all AI actions (e.g., moderation, summarization, flagging) to be clearly explained in simple terms so that I can understand how decisions are made and evaluate the role of AI in deliberations.
US21.2	As a user, I want to know who owns and funds the platform, and how data policies are formed and enforced, so that I can trust that the system serves the public interest.
E22	As a user, I want the system to include human supervision and correction mechanisms so that AI actions remain accountable, errors can be addressed, and trust in the system is maintained.

ID	User Story
US22.1	As a user, I want the system to include various levels of human oversight and control over AI outputs, so that critical decisions are monitored and no automated actions occur without human checks.
US22.2	As a moderator, I want the system to allow identification and correction of AI-generated errors through human supervision so that any mistakes can be resolved quickly and with transparency.
E23	As a platform owner, I want comprehensive training material in various formats for all user roles so that users, moderators, and administrators can onboard quickly and use the platform effectively.
US23.1	As a user (all roles), I want access to training materials in formats like text guides, videos, tutorials, case studies, and simulations so that I can learn to use the platform effectively in a way that suits my learning style.
E24	As a platform owner, I want gamification elements to promote thoughtful and constructive participation rather than superficial activity so that the platform supports genuine deliberation and civic engagement.
US24.1	As a platform owner, I want the gamification system to encourage and reward meaningful participation rather than just activity for the sake of earning points so that user engagement contributes to the overall value and quality of the deliberations.

4.2.7 Detailed scenarios

In this subsection, we present three detailed scenarios for three different categories of users (a simple user, an admin, and a moderator). In these scenarios, we are trying to display the possibilities that every one of these users has through the system. A lot of the following steps are optional.

Scenario 1: User – Participating in a deliberation

1. Register (create an account) on the platform using email and basic personal details.
2. Upload a profile picture or an avatar to personalize their identity.
3. Log in using their username and password.
4. Access training material to understand how AI-enabled deliberations work.
5. Searching through categorized deliberations in order to find an interesting one, based on their preferences.
6. Join an asynchronous ongoing deliberation.
7. Ask for a translation in their native language.
8. Give feedback on the translation.

9. Read through the topic and existing contributions or Choose to create an AI generated summary of the topic in order to understand the key points of the contributions.
10. Listen to an audio version of the summary.
11. Give feedback to the summary.
12. View Fact-Checked responses flagged by the system.
13. Give feedback on the flagged material.
14. Ask for the log, in order to see the reasons for the AI flagged or removed material.
15. Give feedback on other users' posts.
16. Choose to create by prompting the system AI-generated alternative perspectives, encouraging critical thinking.
17. Write and post their own perspective on the issue, responding to others or posing questions.
18. Generate an AI generated report for the discussion with key points and some graphic visualizations.

Scenario 2: Admin – Managing content and categories

1. Log in as an admin.
2. Access the Content Management Dashboard.
3. Browse newly submitted user contributions.
4. Approve, reject or modify contributions flagged by the AI.
5. Approve or modify content categorised by the AI.
6. Search for inappropriate content, flag it for review, and delete if necessary.
7. Check user feedback and manage reported issues (e.g., abuse, spam).
8. Review summary and feedback metrics for each discussion to detect low-quality engagement.
9. Export a report of moderation actions, user activity or feedback for the team meeting.
10. Collaborate with moderators to propose discussion rules.
11. Upload training material.

Scenario 3: Moderator – Structuring and guiding deliberations

1. Register for a Moderator account on the platform using email and basic personal details.
2. Log in as a moderator.
3. Access training material to understand how AI-enabled deliberations works.
4. Navigate to the Agenda Setup interface.
5. Create a meeting agenda for a synchronous deliberation, including topic name, objectives, timeline, and discussion format.
6. Define Rules for Discussion (e.g., respectful language, time limits).
7. Set participation reminders to be automatically sent via email or notifications.
8. During the session, use tools to moderate live discussions, ensuring no one dominates or derails the conversation.
9. Approve or not AI-moderating actions.
10. Approve AI diverse perspective suggestions to ensure inclusive contributions by nudging underrepresented viewpoints.
11. Use AI clustering suggestions to identify common themes and redirect discussions accordingly.

12. Monitor the AI-generated tracking patterns to identify hyperactive and silent users or off-topic trends.
13. Provide real-time feedback or interventions based on AI suggestions.
14. After the session, review the AI-generated summary and suggest changes before publishing.
15. Coordinate with admins for content issues.

4.2.8 Product Backlog

This subsection contains the product backlog with the project activities. For the prioritization of the product backlog, we are going to use the MoSCoW technique (Ton, 2022) (Must Have, Should Have, Could Have, Won't Have), and we will prioritize the activities based on the users' needs, the findings of previous steps, and what we have promised in the proposal. More specifically, User Stories that are extracted from all different sources (i.e., C,I,E,L), are very important for citizens and interviewees, and those promised in the proposal are prioritized as MH. User Stories that are extracted from fewer sources or are less mentioned in interviews are prioritized as SH and CH.

It is worth mentioning that this is the first version of the product backlog. This product backlog doesn't represent a fixed scope or commitment. Items in the backlog can be re-prioritized, rewritten, added to, or removed at any time as the project evolves.

Table 16: Product backlog for the project's activities

Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
E1	Summarization	US1.1	Automatically identify and extract key information from discussions.	MH	
		US1.2	Generate a clear and concise text summary of a discussion.	MH	US1.1
		US1.3	Generate an audio version of the summary.	MH	US1.2
E2	Moderation	US2.1	Suggest discussion rules and flag inappropriate content.	MH	US19.1
		US2.2	Guide the conversation for inclusiveness.	MH	US2.1

Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US2.3	(Human) report, flag, and review inappropriate content.	SH	
		US2.4	(Human) delete, approve, and categorize posts.	SH	US2.3
		US2.5	Acknowledge positive behavior (e.g., 'Thanks').	CH	
		US2.6	Offer structured sessions to co-set discussion rules.	CH	US2.1
E3	Fact-Checking	US3.1	Identify factual claims and provide verified info.	MH	US19.1
		US3.2	Flag potentially misleading content.	MH	US3.1
		US3.3	Provide evidence-based explanations for misleading content.	MH	US3.1, US3.2
		US3.4	Access shared repository of trusted sources.	CH	US3.1
E4	Translation	US4.1	Translate discussion content automatically.	MH	US19.1
		US4.2	Translate audio/video to sign language	WH	US4.1, US10.2, US10.3

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US4.3	Simplify language.	MH	
E5	Identifying Areas of Agreement	US5.1	Cluster similar arguments and identify consensus.	MH	US1.1
E6	Gamification	US6.1	Recognize meaningful contributions.	MH	US24.1
		US6.2	Include gamified incentives (e.g., badges).	MH	US6.1, US24.1
		US6.3	Gamified onboarding process to establish shared norms.	CH	US6.1, US24.1
E7	Suggesting Alternative Perspectives	US7.1	Suggest alternative viewpoints.	SH	
		US7.2	Provide credible sources for alternative views.	SH	US7.1
E8	User Feedback	US8.1	Analyze user feedback to identify improvements.	MH	
		US8.2	(Human) Flag inaccurate AI-generated summaries.	MH	US8.1, US22.2
		US8.3	(Human) Suggest better translations for content.	MH	US8.1, US22.2

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US8.4	Feedback on deliberation processes.	CH	US8.1
E9	Tracking Discussion Patterns	US9.1	Analyze discussion patterns.	CH	
		US9.2	Recommend topics based on interests.	CH	US9.1
		US9.3	Group content and contributions by themes.	CH	US9.1
E10	Participation Features	US10.1	Upload an avatar or a photo for the user's profile.	MH	
		US10.2	Join discussions using video.	MH	
		US10.3	Join discussions using audio.	MH	
		US10.4	Choose a pseudonym instead of the real name.	CH	
		US10.5	View content without logging in.	WH	
		US10.6	Support synchronous formats like live chats or video events.	MH	US10.2, US10.3

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US10.7	Support asynchronous formats for deeper deliberation.	MH	
		US10.8	Support various deliberative processes (e.g., debates, consultations, vote & justification, Q&A).	SH	US10.7
E11	AI Transparency & Accountability	US11.1	Explain AI actions to build trust.	MH	
		US11.2	Log and publish significant AI interventions.	MH	US11.1
		US11.3	Provide explanations when content is flagged.	MH	US11.1
		US11.4	Highlight user contributions in update notes.	CH	US8.1
		US11.5	Periodic updates on discussion impact on policies.	CH	US8.1
E12	Analysis & Visualization & Communication	US12.1	Generate reports and data visualizations from discussions.	MH	
		US12.2	Track metrics like civility and argument quality.	CH	
		US12.3	Submit content in multiple formats.	SH	

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US12.4	Track and analyze participation data using AI.	SH	
		US12.5	Interaction with a chatbot.	CH	
		US12.6	Offer demographic surveys.	CH	
E13	Support	US13.1	Send reminders and support scheduling.	CH	
		US13.2	Provide discussion topics and structured agendas.	CH	
		US13.3	Offer note-taking and follow-up summaries.	CH	
		US13.4	Provide AI reasoning tools to help users refine their arguments.	CH	
		US13.5	Upload training material.	MH	
E14	Registration & Authentication	US14.1	Email/username registration.	MH	
		US14.2	Register via government ID.	WH	US14.1
		US14.3	Enforce secure authentication.	CH	US14.1

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US14.4	Request explicit consent for access to their device's microphone and camera.	MH	US14.1
		US14.5	Prevent multiple account creation.	MH	US14.1
E15	Access Control & Permissions	US15.1	Create and assign user roles.	MH	US14.1
E16	Personalization	US16.1	Remember user accessibility settings.	SH	
		US16.2	Enable users to personalize profiles.	CH	US16.1
		US16.3	Provide advanced content discovery tools.	CH	US16.2
E17	Argument mining	US17.1	Extract and classify arguments from discussions.	MH	
E18	Security & Privacy	US18.1	Securely store and transmit user data.	MH	
		US18.2	Secure data of users who use pseudonyms and avatars.	MH	US18.1
		US18.3	Provide clear data collection policies.	MH	US18.1

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US18.4	Comply with regulations like GDPR and AI Act.	MH	US18.1
		US18.5	Ensure responsible AI training and evaluation.	MH	US18.1
		US18.6	Exclude data from political/statistical exploitation.	MH	US18.1
		US18.7	Keep commercial activities separate.	MH	US18.1
E19	Performance & Scalability & Adaptability	US19.1	AI tasks should work in real-time when needed.	MH	
		US19.2	The system must support large-scale participation without performance degradation.	MH	
		US19.3	Architecture should support updates.	MH	
		US19.4	Comply with interoperability standards (e.g., DCAT-AP, CPSV-AP).	CH	
		US19.5	Optimize for bandwidth and power efficiency.	SH	
		US19.6	Integrate with external tools.	SH	

Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
		US19.7	Support multicultural and regional adaptability.	CH	
E20	Operational & Accessibility	US20.1	Simple and intuitive interfaces.	MH	
		US20.2	Comply with accessibility standards.	MH	
		US20.3	Follow usability principles.	MH	
		US20.4	Work across various devices (smartphones, tablets, pc) and OS (windows, mac os, android, ios).	MH	
		US20.5	Use standard APIs and protocols.	MH	
		US20.6	Be open-source.	SH	
		US20.7	Simple and accessible authentication.	MH	
		US20.8	Be hosted on scalable cloud services.	SH	
		US20.9	Support outreach tools to include more people.	CH	

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	MoSCoW	Dependencies
E21	Transparency & Auditability	US21.1	Explain all AI actions in simple terms.	MH	US11.1
		US21.2	Disclose platform ownership and policies.	MH	
E22	Human Oversight	US22.1	Include human oversight of AI outputs.	MH	
		US22.2	Allow correction of AI errors.	MH	
E23	Support	US23.1	Provide training materials in various formats.	MH	US13.5
E24	Design	US24.1	Gamification to promote thoughtful participation.	MH	

4.3 Survey in Germany

In this section, we present the main findings of the survey that took place in Germany, using an external polling company. This study (Jung Herr & Rauchfleisch, 2025) investigates how citizens respond to the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in democratic deliberative processes. Through a survey that took place in Germany (n = 1,850), the authors assess how the involvement of AI in key deliberative tasks, such as moderation, summarization, and opinion aggregation, affects public willingness to participate and perceived deliberative quality.

4.3.1 Artificial Intelligence in Deliberation: Understanding Public Reception and Risks of a New Divide

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into democratic processes has been widely discussed in the context of improving efficiency, scalability, and fairness. However, until now, empirical knowledge about how the public perceives AI involvement in these processes is limited. This research provides groundbreaking empirical evidence on how AI is perceived in the context of democratic deliberation, using a representative survey experiment conducted in Germany. The study explores whether people are willing to participate in deliberative

formats facilitated by AI and how they assess the quality of such formats compared to traditional human-led ones. Its findings are of direct relevance to policymakers and public administrators considering the adoption of AI technologies in civic engagement initiatives.

Democratic deliberation is a cornerstone of participatory governance. Digital technologies have expanded the toolbox available for these deliberative practices, enabling broader participation through online town halls, citizen assemblies, and other virtual formats.

AI is increasingly seen as a way to further enhance these digital efforts by offering functionalities such as summarizing content, moderating discussions, detecting factual inaccuracies, or aggregating preferences.

However, deliberation is not merely a technical challenge; it is a deeply human process that offers recognition, inclusivity, and voice. This raises critical questions: Does the involvement of AI in democratic processes reduce citizens' willingness to participate? Does it alter their perception of fairness and quality?

To answer these questions, we conducted a preregistered survey experiment with a representative sample of 1,850 German adults. Participants were randomly presented with deliberative tasks—some facilitated by humans, others by AI—and asked to assess their willingness to participate and their perceived quality of the deliberative process.

4.3.2 The “AI Penalty”

The study's most striking result is the term “AI penalty.” On average, participants were less willing to take part in deliberative formats that were facilitated by AI compared to those led by human moderators. They also rated the quality of AI-led deliberations lower.

Quantitatively, this AI penalty manifested as a statistically significant negative effect on both dependent variables:

- **Willingness to participate:** Participants expressed a lower interest in participating when deliberative tasks were facilitated by AI ($b = -0.30$, 95% CI $[-0.34, -0.26]$, $p < .001$).
- **Assessment of deliberative quality:** AI-enabled formats received significantly lower quality ratings than human-led formats ($b = -0.29$, 95% CI $[-0.32, -0.26]$, $p < .001$).

This AI penalty was especially pronounced in areas where experts tend to believe AI can be most helpful—such as content summarization, argument structuring, and opinion aggregation. Ironically, tasks that AI may not technically handle well—like fact-checking—were viewed more neutrally by participants.

4.3.3 Who is Willing to Participate? The Role of Predispositions

To understand the drivers of this suspicion, individual characteristics and predispositions were examined by the researchers, based on the civic voluntarism model, a well-established framework in political science. They grouped potential explanatory factors into three broad categories:

a. Material Resources

Contrary to expectations, factors like income, education, and available time (measured via employment and parental responsibilities) did not significantly affect willingness to participate in either AI- or human-led formats. This might be due to the hypothetical nature of the questions asked. When people are only asked about their interest in participation, material constraints such as time and money might be less salient.

b. Political Engagement

As expected, higher levels of political interest were positively correlated with willingness to participate, while political efficacy and party identification strength did not show significant effects.

c. Cognitive Disposition

The most consistent predictor of willingness to participate in deliberation, regardless of whether it was AI or human facilitated, was the ‘need for cognition’. This psychological trait reflects a person’s enjoyment of complex thinking and problem solving. Participants who scored higher on this trait were more inclined to engage in deliberative processes.

4.3.4 The Role of Attitudes Toward AI

A major contribution of this study is its analysis of how general attitudes toward AI affect the AI penalty. The researchers assessed perceptions of AI's benefits and risks across various societal domains, including economic development, national security, and political communication.

Their results revealed a clear pattern:

- Positive attitudes toward AI (e.g., beliefs that AI can support state capacity or economic growth) mitigated the AI penalty. These individuals expressed greater willingness to participate in AI-enabled deliberation and rated its quality higher.
- Negative attitudes toward AI (e.g., concerns about job loss or existential risks) intensified the AI penalty. These individuals were significantly less likely to participate and rated the quality of AI-facilitated deliberation lower.

In addition, the study looked at:

- Direct experience with AI: People who used AI in their personal or professional life were more willing to participate in AI-enabled formats.
- Anthropomorphization of AI: People who attributed human-like characteristics to AI (e.g., having a sense of humor or morality) were more accepting of its role in deliberation.

These findings indicate that trust in AI, and, more broadly, familiarity with AI, plays a critical role in shaping public acceptance.

4.3.5 Implications for Democratic Innovation

The researchers stress a critical insight: AI introduces a ‘new deliberative divide’. Traditionally, differences in the level of political participation have been attributed to socio-demographic inequalities like education, income, age, etc. This study shows that attitudes toward technology, and AI in particular, now form an additional axis of inequality.

This divergence is especially concerning because it is not established by resource inequality but in perception and belief. If AI is increasingly used in public deliberation, those who are skeptical of or fearful toward AI may self-select out of participation. This could lead to:

- Reduced representativeness of deliberative forums
- Lower legitimacy of outcomes
- Increased societal polarization

As such, practitioners, public administrators and government bodies must approach the integration of AI into participatory processes with caution. Simply adding AI for reasons of efficiency or scale may inadvertently reduce public engagement and trust.

4.3.6 Differences Between Expert and Public Perceptions

Another key finding is the discrepancy between academic expectations and public perception regarding the strengths of AI in deliberation. For example, the potential function of AI to make large amounts of text and complex arguments digestible are presented by experts as one of its main strengths. However, these are the very features that participants in the study reacted most negatively to.

Conversely, AI applications like fact-checking, which experts view with skepticism due to current technological limitations, received more neutral or even favorable public responses.

This mismatch highlights the importance of incorporating public perceptions and preferences into the design and deployment of AI-enabled democratic tools. Overlooking such perceptions could undermine the intended goals of deliberative inclusivity and fairness.

4.4 Conclusions

Based on the input from task 1.1 (2.1-2.10), pilots’ citizens and employees, best practice case owners, and platform owners, we established a well-rounded and user-centered foundation for the development of the product. The detailed documentation of requirements, accompanied by the description of the corresponding epics and user stories, ensures that the project is aligned with all the important stakeholders’ opinions and needs. This approach concluded in the product backlog, which serves as a clear roadmap that leads to proper development and progress. Finally, the presentation of the process followed, enhances both transparency and traceability, as well as lays the foundation for a solution that is relevant and sustainable in practice.

Furthermore, in the framework of the same task, we conducted a survey in Germany in order to investigate how citizens respond to the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in democratic

deliberative processes. The findings suggest that while AI has the potential to improve democratic deliberation, its integration into public consultation processes must be treated with caution. Public skepticism rooted in general attitudes toward AI can reduce participation and perceived quality, thereby undermining the very goals that deliberation aims to achieve.

AI, in its current form, introduces not only new capabilities but also new inequalities. Policymakers must therefore treat technological integration in democratic processes as not only a technical issue, but a deeply political and social one.

Therefore, the design of future (digital) deliberative formats should prioritize inclusivity, legitimacy, and trust: principles that cannot be outsourced to algorithms. Thoughtful implementation, responsive design, and a clear understanding of public attitudes will be essential to ensuring that AI contributes to, rather than detracts from, democratic innovation.

Concluding some key points raised from the survey. People are significantly less willing to participate in AI-enabled deliberations and rate their quality lower compared to human-led formats. Also, AI introduces a novel form of participatory inequality, not based on socioeconomic factors, but on individuals' attitudes toward AI and technology. Political interest and need for cognition are strong predictors of willingness to participate, while material resources (e.g., income, education) play a limited role in hypothetical scenarios. Positive views of AI (e.g., belief in societal benefits) reduce the AI-penalty, while concerns about AI risks significantly intensify it and finally, the public is most skeptical of AI in tasks experts view as AI strengths (e.g., summarizing arguments), indicating a need to align AI deployment with public perceptions and trust. The KPIs of Task 1.3 are presented in the following table.

Table 17: Task1.3 KPIs (*some interviewees from the pilots also filled the questionnaires as citizens and one member of them was also a platform owner).

KPI	Aim	Achieved
#User Stories	≥ 30	95 (+24 Epics)
#persons asked	≥ 100	$\pm 303^*$
#countries	≥ 4	7

5. Global Conclusion

This report is the first deliverable, “D1.1 Demystify Digital Deliberative Processes” that presents the results of the WP1. The objectives of this WP was: O1.1 To analyse and synthesise the scientific literature and practice in the cross-section of the following fields: deliberation processes and platforms, AI and LLMs (including video LLMs), argumentation mining, evaluation models, O1.2 To map the future of multimodal AI deliberations using scenarios (Technology Foresight), and O1.3 To elicit stakeholders needs and considerations. These three objectives are achieved in tasks T1.1, T1.2, and T1.3 respectively.

More specifically, in T1.1, we have demystified the normative underpinnings of deliberation and examined how and to what extent these ideals can be translated into digital settings, while avoiding producing problems of scale. The analysis of existing platforms and emerging technologies, like AI functionalities and Argument Mining, provides a comprehensive overview of the tools and considerations necessary to enable meaningful, inclusive, and transparent digital deliberation.

In T1.2, we have conducted a Technology Foresight exercise exploring AI's role in deliberative democracy by 2030. We used multiple methodologies, including literature review, Delphi method and scenario planning. As a result four future scenarios were developed. One named "Utopia" where AI enhances democracy, a "Dystopia" where AI undermines democratic values, and two intermediate scenarios shaped by uncertainties in social trust and political factors. The outcomes of the Technology Foresight, aim to inform policymakers and guide future decisions, ensuring AI supports democratic deliberation rather than undermining it. The outcomes of the Technology Foresight are visually depicted using DebateGraph, which will stay live throughout the project, enabling the further refining and improvement of the outcomes as the project evolves.

In task 1.3, the main objective was to elicit stakeholders' needs and considerations on using AI in deliberations. Gathering the input and needs of different stakeholders is not just important, it is essential for success. Each of the stakeholders we heard and recorded their opinion using various methods brings unique perspectives and priorities that shape the overall vision and functionality of the under development solution. By listening to their needs and transforming them into requirements, we ensure that the tool is relevant, has the user as the main focus point, and has great potential to fulfil its goal. This process lays the foundation for delivering a solution that truly solves the problems, maximizes adoption, and has the ability to achieve great impact.

The work we did in this deliverable, concerns the first phase of the project. By combining insights extracted from the literature, with the technology foresight, and the opinions extracted directly from various stakeholders, we have established a solid foundation for the development of the AI toolkit. This approach allowed us to understand the current state of the art, anticipate future technological trends, and capture the real needs and considerations of those who will use the tool. This ensures that the development will be driven by

well-informed and evidence-based decisions, aligned both with present and future perspectives.

Table 18 : KPIs reached via throughout this Deliverable (*some interviewees from the pilots also filled the questionnaires as citizens and one member of them was also a platform owner)

	KPI	KPI reached
#Papers reviewed	≥ 200	320
#Platforms reviewed	≥ 50	50
#AI Features reviewed	≥ 50	92
#Deliberation Formats reviewed	≥ 10	20
#Conceptual Map	≥ 1	1
#Technology Foresight Scenarios	≥ 4	4
#User Stories	≥ 30	95 (+24 Epics)
#persons asked	≥ 100	$\pm 303^*$
#countries	≥ 4	7

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Appendices

A. Questionnaire – 1 of the Exploratory Survey

Proposing Key Uncertainties

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Demographics

* What is your primary area of expertise or role in the project?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Technical (e.g., Developer, Data Scientist)
- Policy/Governance (e.g., Government Official, Policy Analyst)
- Research/Academia
- Civil Society Representative
- Other (Please specify)

* Which sector or type of organization do you represent?

- Public
- Private
- Academia
- NGO
- Other (Please specify)

* What is your level of experience with AI?

- High
- Moderate
- Low

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B. Questionnaire – 2 of the Exploratory Survey

Ranking Key Uncertainties

Pages

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[Info](#)
[Ethical and Social](#)
[Technical](#)
[Organizational and Governance](#)
[AI Autonomy vs. Human Oversight](#)
[Citizen Engagement and Trust in AI](#)
[Design and Implementation](#)
[AI's Role in Democratic Values and Governance](#)

Demographics

* What is your primary area of expertise or role in the project?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Technical (e.g., Developer, Data Scientist)
- Policy/Governance (e.g., Government Official, Policy Analyst)
- Research/Academia
- Civil Society Representative
- Other (Please specify)

* Which sector or type of organization do you represent?

- Public
- Private
- Academia
- NGO
- Other (Please specify)

* What is your level of experience with AI?

- High
- Moderate
- Low

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Ranking Uncertainties

Thank you for participating in this critical exercise! This questionnaire asks you to rank the **10 categories of uncertainties** based on their **Likelihood** (how likely they are to occur) and their **Impact** (how significant their effects would be if they occur). Your input will help us identify the two most critical uncertainties to guide the Scenario Planning phase.

For each category, rate its **Likelihood** and **Impact** using the scale below:

- 1: Very Low
- 2: Low
- 3: Moderate
- 4: High
- 5: Very High

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Ethical and Social Concerns

How likely are ethical and social concerns (e.g., transparency and accountability, bias and discrimination) to significantly impact the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

If ethical and social concerns occur, how significant would their impact be on the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

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Technical Challenges

How likely are technical challenges (e.g., data quality and integration, system complexity, infrastructure limitations, algorithmic facilitation, data privacy and security) to arise in the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

If technical challenges occur, how significant would their impact be on the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

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Organizational and Governance Issues

How likely are organizational and governance issues (e.g., AI capability gaps, administrative culture, siloed structures, regulatory gaps, funding constraints) to affect the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

If organizational and governance issues occur, how significant would their impact be on the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

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AI Autonomy vs. Human Oversight

How likely are concerns regarding AI autonomy versus human oversight (e.g., appropriate use of AI, power shifts in governance, over-reliance on AI) to affect governance processes in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

If concerns regarding AI autonomy versus human oversight occur, how significant would their impact be on governance processes in deliberation platforms?

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Citizen Engagement and Trust in AI

How likely are challenges related to citizen engagement and trust (e.g., awareness and education, digital divide, personalization concerns) to affect the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

If challenges related to citizen engagement and trust occur, how significant would their impact be on the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

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Design and Implementation Challenges

How likely are design and implementation challenges (e.g., undemocratic design, lack of citizen input, explainability) to arise in the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

If design and implementation challenges occur, how significant would their impact be on the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

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AI's Role in Democratic Values

How likely are challenges related to democratic values and governance (e.g., inclusion, public scrutiny, fragmented regulation) to impact the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

[Reset to initial position](#)

If challenges related to democratic values and governance occur, how significant would their impact be on the adoption of AI in deliberation platforms?

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C. Questionnaire – Delphi round 1

Technology Foresight - Delphi survey: Round 1

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Introduction

This survey is conducted as part of a **Technology Foresight** exercise that engages domain experts to explore **future scenarios related to the use of AI in deliberative democracy*** by 2030.

Methodology: Technology Foresight follows a two-round Delphi method

- **Round 1 (this survey):** focuses on gathering insights mainly through open-ended questions
- Round 2: Will refine these insights into structured questions to assess consensus on key issues.

The objectives of this survey are:

- To assess the importance of various uncertainties (highly impactful but unpredictable factors) shaping the future.
- To collect expert's input on potential developments in the domain.

**Deliberative democracy suggests everyone is given the opportunity to express their opinion to ensure the legitimacy of decisions. It involves engaging citizens and stakeholders in discussions to reach consensus or informed opinions on complex societal issues.*

Your input is essential in shaping a forward-looking vision of AI's role in deliberative democracy. Thank you for your participation!

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Demographics

* Full name

* Areas of expertise

- Law & Ethics
- Social sciences
- Political sciences
- Technology
- Digital democracy
- Other (please specify)

* Years of relevant experience (approx.)

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Evaluation of Categories of Uncertainty

The following main categories of uncertainties have been identified in the literature:

- **Legal & Ethical:** Uncertainties regarding regulations, legal frameworks, ethical implications and accountability **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., AI transparency, privacy, AI autonomy vs human oversight, fragmented regulation, regulatory gaps).
- **Social & Trust:** Uncertainties regarding citizen acceptance, participation, trust and social cohesion **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., misinformation, levels of public engagements, digital divide, inclusion).
- **Organizational:** Uncertainties regarding institutional readiness, governance structures and coordination among stakeholders **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., inter-agency collaboration, resource allocation, change resistance, scalability of AI in public administration).
- **Technological:** Uncertainties regarding technology adoption, platform reliability, cybersecurity and data management **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., algorithm bias, security breaches, low data quality, infrastructure limitations, explainability).
- **Political:** Uncertainties regarding political support, commitment, stability and alignment with democratic values **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., political polarization, policy continuity, shifting in priorities, risk of AI misuse in political processes).

For each of the following categories of uncertainty, please indicate your evaluation of **Likelihood**.
Likelihood: "How likely is this uncertainty to materialize and affect deliberative democracy by 2030?"

Uncertainty	1 Very Unlikely	2 Unlikely	3 Neutral	4 Likely	5 Very Likely
• Legal & Ethical	<input type="radio"/>				
• Social & trust	<input type="radio"/>				
• Organizational	<input type="radio"/>				
• Technological	<input type="radio"/>				
• Political	<input type="radio"/>				

For each of the following categories of uncertainty, please indicate your evaluation of **Impact**.
Impact: "If this uncertainty materializes, how significant will its impact be on deliberative democracy by 2030?"

Uncertainty	1 Minimal Impact	2 Low Impact	3 Moderate Impact	4 High Impact	5 Very High Impact
• Legal & Ethical	<input type="radio"/>				
• Social & trust	<input type="radio"/>				
• Organizational	<input type="radio"/>				
• Technological	<input type="radio"/>				
• Political	<input type="radio"/>				

Are there any other categories of uncertainties not listed above? Please describe.

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Qualitative Input

For each uncertainty category below, please briefly share your insights on:

- **Positive and negative developments** related to the identified uncertainties.
- **Drivers of positive developments** and **causes of failure** for negative developments.
- **Mitigation strategies** to prevent or minimize negative developments.

Identified categories of uncertainty (the same as with the previous page):

- **Legal & Ethical:** Uncertainties regarding regulations, legal frameworks, ethical implications and accountability **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., AI transparency, privacy, AI autonomy vs human oversight, fragmented regulation, regulatory gaps).
- **Social & Trust:** Uncertainties regarding citizen acceptance, participation, trust and social cohesion **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., misinformation, levels of public engagements, digital divide, inclusion).
- **Organizational:** Uncertainties regarding institutional readiness, governance structures and coordination among stakeholders **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., inter-agency collaboration, resource allocation, change resistance, scalability of AI in public administration).
- **Technological:** Uncertainties regarding technology adoption, platform reliability, cybersecurity and data management **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., algorithm bias, security breaches, low data quality, infrastructure limitations, explainability).
- **Political:** Uncertainties regarding political support, commitment, stability and alignment with democratic values **arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes** (e.g., political polarization, policy continuity, shifting in priorities, risk of AI misuse in political processes).

Legal & Ethical:

- Positive and negative developments related to this uncertainty category.

- Drivers of positive developments and causes of failure for negative developments for this uncertainty category.

- Mitigation strategies to prevent or minimize negative developments.

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Social & Trust:

- * Positive and negative developments related to this uncertainty category.

- * Drivers of positive developments and causes of failure for negative developments for this uncertainty category.

- * Mitigation strategies to prevent or minimize negative developments.

Organizational:

- * Positive and negative developments related to this uncertainty category.

- * Drivers of positive developments and causes of failure for negative developments for this uncertainty category.

- * Mitigation strategies to prevent or minimize negative developments.

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Technological:

- * Positive and negative developments related to this uncertainty category.

- * Drivers of positive developments and causes of failure for negative developments for this uncertainty category.

- * Mitigation strategies to prevent or minimize negative developments.

Political:

- * Positive and negative developments related to this uncertainty category.

- * Drivers of positive developments and causes of failure for negative developments for this uncertainty category.

- * Mitigation strategies to prevent or minimize negative developments.

Other factors

Other factors

Are there other factors or potential events that could significantly influence Deliberative Democracy and have not been covered above? Please describe them briefly.

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D. Questionnaire – Delphi round 2

Technology Foresight - Delphi survey: Round 2

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Introduction

This survey is conducted as part of a **Technology Foresight** exercise that engages domain experts to explore **future scenarios related to the use of AI in deliberative democracy* by 2030**.

Methodology: Technology Foresight follows a two-round Delphi method

- Round 1 (completed): focuses on gathering insights mainly through open-ended questions
- **Round 2 (this survey):** Will refine these insights to assess consensus on key issues.

The objectives of this survey are:

- To present the results of Round 1 and gather feedback.
- To collect expert's opinion about the future of deliberative democracy.

**Deliberative democracy suggests everyone is given the opportunity to express their opinion to ensure the legitimacy of decisions. It involves engaging citizens and stakeholders in discussions to reach consensus or informed opinions on complex societal issues.*

Your input is essential in shaping a forward-looking vision of AI's role in deliberative democracy. Thank you for your participation!

* Full name

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Results of Round 1

The following main categories of uncertainties were evaluated and discussed in the first Delphi round:

- **Legal & Ethical:** Uncertainties regarding regulations, legal frameworks, ethical implications and accountability arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes
- **Social & Trust:** Uncertainties regarding citizen acceptance, participation, trust and social cohesion arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes.
- **Organizational:** Uncertainties regarding institutional readiness, governance structures and coordination among stakeholders arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes.
- **Technological:** Uncertainties regarding technology adoption, platform reliability, cybersecurity and data management arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes.
- **Political:** Uncertainties regarding political support, commitment, stability and alignment with democratic values arising from the use of AI in deliberative processes.

The following diagram presents the mean score for impact and likelihood from the first Delphi round.

Do you have any comment on the above results?

The qualitative results, collected through open-ended questions, are presented on the following pages by category.

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Legal & Ethical Factors

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during the first Delphi round for this category.

Positive Developments

- The AI Act and other emerging regulations represent progress in setting legal boundaries.
- Strengthened ethical oversight mechanisms (e.g. EU AI Act, UNESCO Ethics Rec).
- Widespread awareness on transparency, explainability, fairness and accountability including the implementation of relevant mechanisms.
- GDPR reinforces data protection in AI.

Negative Developments

- Laws lag behind AI evolution; fragmented regulation; legal loopholes.
- Lack of legal recognition for non-human (AI-generated) contributions in deliberative processes.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- Strong regulatory frameworks
- Alignment with democratic values
- Civic pressure

Causes of Failure

- Rapid AI pace vs. slow lawmaking
- Unclear ethical boundaries
- Failure to enforce legal norms or apply them across contexts.

Mitigation Strategies

- Monitor and adapt AI Act to be aligned with technological advancements.
- Establish multistakeholder governance bodies to oversee AI in public deliberations.
- Develop legal safeguards that protect the representation of marginalized groups in AI-mediated deliberations.
- Clarify the legal boundaries for the use of AI in public deliberations and embed ethical guidelines into policy, procurement etc.

* Are the above identified **positive/negative developments, drivers, and causes of failure** sufficient in this category? If not, please explain what you think is missing or should be changed.

* How effective are the proposed **mitigation strategies**?

- Not Effective
- Slightly Effective
- Moderately Effective
- Effective
- Very Effective

* Would you propose any additional **mitigation strategies** for this uncertainty? How feasible do you think it is to implement the mitigation strategies by 2030?

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Social & Trust Factors

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during the first Delphi round for this category.

Positive Developments

- Growing citizen engagement and public interest in AI's societal impact.
- New citizen deliberation platforms and co-creation models promoting participatory governance.
- AI is used to increase inclusivity, representativity, and reduce polarization - if deployed responsibly.
- Improved public technological (AI) literacy that leads to enhanced trust.

Negative Developments

- AI is used to increase polarization, disinformation, and public distrust.
- Declining Public Trust in AI due to negative narratives e.g. negative media coverage, misinformation, or lack of transparency.
- Misuse or unfair use of AI can trigger protests, resistance, or social tensions. Potentially leading to new forms of violence (e.g., human to machine violence).
- Concerns over lack of transparency, deepfakes, digital divide, and declining democratic participation.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- Investment in AI literacy and digital education.
- Broad public discourse and exposure to responsible AI implementations.
- Emphasis on deliberative principles (transparency, oversight, accountability).
- Responsible inclusion of AI in democratic debates to increase diversity of voices.

Causes of Failure

- Citizens feeling disempowered or excluded from deliberative democracy.
- Misuse of AI by Powerful Actors
- Spread of Misinformation
- Growing Digital Inequality
- Lack of understanding of AI's role in deliberative democracy.

Mitigation Strategies

- Roll out AI literacy programs and targeted public education.
- Develop transparent deliberative platforms with public review and oversight.
- Use AI to counter misinformation (e.g., fact-checking, trust metrics).
- Emphasize human-centered AI design with explainability and fairness.
- Highlight real-world success stories to build trust and legitimacy.
- Foster inclusive, diverse debate, potentially including unconventional contributors (e.g., AI voices).
- Promote balanced narratives, avoiding polarizing public discussions about the use of AI in deliberations.

* Are the above identified **positive/negative developments, drivers, and causes of failure** sufficient in this category? If not, please explain what you think is missing or should be changed.

* How effective are the proposed **mitigation strategies**?

- Not Effective
- Slightly Effective
- Moderately Effective
- Effective
- Very Effective

* Would you propose any additional **mitigation strategies** for this uncertainty? How feasible do you think it is to implement the mitigation strategies by 2030?

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Organizational Factors

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during the first Delphi round for this category.

Positive Developments

- Public organizations are investing in AI readiness and innovation.
- AI helps to streamline public sector workflows and reduce bureaucratic burdens.
- Technological advancements drive innovation in governance and decision-making processes.

Negative Developments

- Organizational resistance to change is widespread.
- Lack of learning/adaptation, and rigid hierarchies are major barriers.
- Implementation efforts are fragmented and uncoordinated, creating inefficiencies.
- Lack of mechanisms for incorporating public feedback into decision-making.
- A gap between policy rhetoric and practical implementation persists.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- Adoption of AI readiness strategies and innovation mandates within public administration.
- Active learning, experimentation, and internal innovation labs.
- Cross-sector and public-private collaborations are growing.
- Public pressure and international examples can inspire reform.
- Pursuit of efficiency, inclusion, and digital transformation as core motivators.

Causes of Failure

- Low digital literacy within public institutions, especially among senior officials.
- Cultural resistance, weak leadership, and unclear implementation guidance.
- Underfunding
- Lack of strategic planning, and copy-paste approaches from foreign models.

Mitigation Strategies

- Invest in capacity building.
- Support inter-agency collaboration and shared frameworks for AI governance.
- Promote exceptional leadership to guide AI transformation aligned with democratic values.
- Ensure clear accountability and role definitions for AI use.
- Design systems with human fallback mechanisms in critical processes.
- Involve younger generations and encourage digital-native leadership models.
- Implement robust communication and change management strategies.

* Are the above identified **positive/negative developments, drivers, and causes of failure** sufficient in this category? If not, please explain what you think is missing or should be changed.

* How effective are the proposed **mitigation strategies**?

- Not Effective
- Slightly Effective
- Moderately Effective
- Effective
- Very Effective

* Would you propose any additional **mitigation strategies** for this uncertainty? How feasible do you think it is to implement the mitigation strategies by 2030?

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Technological Factors

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during the first Delphi round for this category.

Positive Developments

- AI tools are becoming more affordable, efficient, and user-friendly, facilitating broader adoption.
- Growth in generative AI and large language models (LLMs) opens up new possibilities for civic use.
- Advancements in cybersecurity and data management improve institutional robustness.
- Development of explainable AI (xAI) and transparent AI frameworks is progressing.
- Community-led initiatives and open-source movements are gaining momentum.
- Emphasis on data quality in AI training is improving output reliability.

Negative Developments

- Dominance of US-based tech giants leads to dependency and geopolitical imbalance.
- AI models lack transparency and introduce algorithmic bias.
- Immature technologies may be deployed without sufficient safeguards.
- The machine-machine drift can reduce the space for meaningful human deliberation.
- Some tools are introduced without clear democratic purpose, risking misuse.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- Ongoing progress in xAI, open-source platforms, and human-aligned model development.
- Collaborative efforts between academia, public institutions, and civil society.
- Focus on AI for societal good, especially in democratic processes.
- Availability of flexible and adaptable AI models designed for inclusion.
- Sufficient time and institutional space for thoughtful integration.

Causes of Failure

- Overreliance on foreign technological ecosystems.
- Premature adoption of tools without clear governance.
- AI tools used to manipulate or bypass democratic deliberation.
- Insufficient governance capacity to monitor, regulate, or steer development responsibly.

Mitigation Strategies

- Invest in explainable AI, algorithmic fairness, and bias mitigation.
- Promote open-source development and public sector AI innovation.
- Adopt by-design robust security protocols.
- Design flexible, human-aligned systems that enhance participation and transparency.
- Provide context-specific guidance for appropriate AI deployment.
- Encourage multisector collaboration in technological development and planning.
- Caution against non-transparent, commercial deployments that ignore public interest.

* Are the above identified **positive/negative developments, drivers, and causes of failure** sufficient in this category? If not, please explain what you think is missing or should be changed.

* How effective are the proposed **mitigation strategies**?

- Not Effective
- Slightly Effective
- Moderately Effective
- Effective
- Very Effective

* Would you propose any additional **mitigation strategies** for this uncertainty? How feasible do you think it is to implement the mitigation strategies by 2030?

Political Factors

The following presents a summary of the qualitative results collected during the first Delphi round for this category.

Positive Developments

- Increased political awareness and leadership around AI's democratic impacts.
- AI seen as a tool to improve governance, public services, and decision-making.
- Political support for ethical frameworks, digital public goods, and commons infrastructure.
- Growing debate about transparency, accountability, and inclusion in AI policy.

Negative Developments

- AI is being used for manipulation, disinformation, and polarization in political discourse.
- Risk of technocracy and exclusion, where AI decisions override democratic debate.
- Lack of trust in political institutions, and growing fragmentation or resistance to change.

Drivers of Positive Developments

- Evidence-based policymaking, science-driven regulation, and public trust-building.
- Development of inclusive civic AI mechanisms.
- Cross-country learning and benchmarking.
- Politicians seeing public benefit and legitimacy from AI integration.
- Long-term, forward-looking AI governance visions.

Causes of Failure

- Resistance to change
- Lack of political safeguards enables abuse of AI for political advantage (e.g., electoral gain)
- Exclusionary use of AI in political processes (elitism or technocracy)
- Insufficient representation of vulnerable or marginalized populations in AI governance.
- Rapid adoption without safeguards could deepen conflict and institutional erosion.
- Overreliance on non-elected actors (e.g., tech companies) in shaping political processes.

Mitigation Strategies

- Launch small-scale experiments to test AI in deliberative democracy with safeguards.
- Build institutional capacity for AI governance, including oversight bodies.
- Foster cross-party dialogue on AI's role in democracy.
- Develop laws regulating AI in elections, policy formation, and civic dialogue.
- Guarantee inclusive, representative participation in AI-enhanced decision processes.
- Support transparency in AI-influenced decisions (e.g., showing how input was processed).
- Take a long-term policy view, avoiding reactive or fragmented regulation.

* Are the above identified **positive/negative developments, drivers, and causes of failure** sufficient in this category? If not, please explain what you think is missing or should be changed.

* How effective are the proposed **mitigation strategies**?

- Not Effective
- Slightly Effective
- Moderately Effective
- Effective
- Very Effective

* Would you propose any additional **mitigation strategies** for this uncertainty? How feasible do you think it is to implement the mitigation strategies by 2030?

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Exploring the Future of Deliberative Democracy

In this final section, we are gathering your insights to help shape future scenarios related to the use of AI in deliberative democracy by 2030.

Describe a Positive and a Negative Scenario

- Imagine and briefly describe a **positive - "Utopia" future** where AI improves deliberative democracy by 2030 (i.e., positive developments and mitigations strategies described in the previous pages are realized).

Consider for example aspects such as: How is democracy affected? How deliberations look like? Who takes part in the deliberation processes? What is the scale of deliberations? How do individual relationships influence or get influenced by the process? etc.

- Imagine and briefly describe a **negative - "Dystopia" future** where AI undermines deliberative democracy by 2030 (i.e., negative developments described in the previous pages are realized).

Consider for example aspects such as: How is democracy affected? How deliberations look like? Who takes part in the deliberation processes? What is the scale of deliberations? How do individual relationships influence or get influenced by the process? etc.

Stress-Test the Utopian Future: What If It's Disrupted?

- Now imagine that the "Utopia" future is disrupted by negative **"Social and Trust"** developments (e.g., declining public trust in AI, unfair use of AI triggers social tensions). Briefly describe how this changes the "Utopia" scenario.

- Now imagine that the "Utopia" future is disrupted by negative **Political** developments (e.g. AI is being used for manipulation, disinformation, and polarization in political discourse). Briefly describe how this changes the "Utopia" scenario.

Is there anything else you want to add?

Previous

Submit

E. Survey questionnaire

The survey questionnaire is available in four languages (German, Greek, Italian, and English), one for each pilot.

Table 19: English survey questionnaire

Gender

Male Female Other I do not wish to answer

Age

18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65+

I do not wish to answer

Education Level

No formal education Primary School Secondary school

Associate Degree or Vocational Training Bachelor's Degree

Master's Degree Professional Degree Doctorate (PhD)

I do not wish to answer

Country of residence

Germany Greece Italy United Kingdom Other (Free text)

I do not wish to answer

Introduction

In its ideal form, democracy is based on dialogue and deliberations between citizens, where everyone is given an equal opportunity to express their opinion (e.g., propose topics, share arguments, vote on alternatives). However, this process can be challenging to conduct and sustain at a large scale in modern societies. AI-enhanced tools might offer new ways to support dialogue at larger scales and move public deliberations closer to the democratic ideal.

Our goal is to understand how AI tools can be used to support public deliberation in democracies and, through this, to build a freely available AI toolkit that groups anywhere in the world can use to enhance their own deliberations. The answers you share in the questionnaire will help us identify and prioritise the initial features of the AI toolkit, which we will then test and refine in four deliberative projects – starting later this year – in Germany, Greece, Italy, and an international initiative based in the UK.

Estimated completion time: 20 minutes

1. Have you used Artificial Intelligence tools in any context, if yes was it helpful?
- Definitely not helpful
 - Probably not helpful
 - Not sure
 - Probably helpful
 - Definitely helpful
 - I have not used

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2. If yes, could you describe briefly the context and what you found helpful or not?
(open question/optional)

For each of the following platform functions, please indicate your preferred balance between AI support and human oversight.

1 = Fully human-led 2 = Mostly human-led with AI support 3 = Equal balance between human and AI involvement 4 = Mostly AI-led with human oversight 5 = Fully AI-led

	1	2	3	4	5
Discussion summarization	<input type="radio"/>				
Discussion moderation	<input type="radio"/>				
Fact-checking	<input type="radio"/>				
Translation services	<input type="radio"/>				
Identifying areas of agreement	<input type="radio"/>				
Suggesting alternative perspectives	<input type="radio"/>				
Processing user feedback	<input type="radio"/>				
Tracking discussion patterns	<input type="radio"/>				

Below, you will find a series of features and functionalities of an AI-enabled deliberation platform.

Please indicate how important each of the following features are, on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

1 = Definitely not Important, 2 = Probably not important, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Important, 5 = Very important

	1	2	3	4	5
Discussion summarization (Automatically generates summaries of discussions)	<input type="radio"/>				

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Discussion moderation (Automatically suggests guidelines and flags inappropriate content)	<input type="radio"/>				
Fact-checking (Identifies and addresses factuality, providing verified information to ensure that facts being used are correct during deliberations)	<input type="radio"/>				
Translation services (Offers automated translations)	<input type="radio"/>				
Identifying areas of agreement (Clusters similar points and identifies key categories in discussions)	<input type="radio"/>				
Suggesting alternative perspectives (Proposes diverse viewpoints to enrich discussions and encourage critical thinking)	<input type="radio"/>				
Processing user feedback (Analyzes feedback to prioritize improvements)	<input type="radio"/>				
Tracking discussion patterns (Monitors engagement trends and dynamics to optimize future deliberations)	<input type="radio"/>				

For each of the following questions, state which of the following functionalities an AI-enabled deliberation platform is important to have based on your own perspective:

	1	2	3	4	5
3. How important is it to enable participants to flag the AI-generated summaries of discussions for errors?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. How important is it for the AI to actively moderate (monitor, regulate, facilitate) discussions to ensure inclusiveness?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. How important is it to have AI to suggest relevant sources and evidence during discussions?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. How important is it for AI to flag potentially misleading information?	<input type="radio"/>				

7. How important is it for AI to provide clear explanations when content is identified as potentially misleading?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. How important is it to allow participants to suggest improvements to automatic translations?	<input type="radio"/>				
9. How important is it for the AI to suggest deliberations and topics based on your preferences and previous activity?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. How important is it to be connected with different perspectives on the topics being discussed?	<input type="radio"/>				

11. How important is it to provide evidence for the suggested different perspectives?	<input type="radio"/>				
12. How important is it for you to know how and why AI acts when contributing to discussions (e.g., content moderation, summarization, consensus building)?	<input type="radio"/>				
13. How important is it to save and make publicly available audit logs of significant AI interventions in discussions (e.g., content removal, fact-checking decisions, consensus summaries)?	<input type="radio"/>				
14. How important is it to allow participants to provide feedback on AI features and contribute to their improvement through structured feedback mechanisms?	<input type="radio"/>				
15. How important is it to encourage meaningful participation in public discussions through civic engagement incentives (such as deliberation expertise badges, consensus-building achievements, dialogue quality recognition, etc.)?	<input type="radio"/>				
16. How important is it to recognize meaningful contributions from participants through contextualized achievement signals that reflect the quality and impact of participation (e.g., bridging opposing viewpoints, elevating evidence-based discussion, and fostering inclusive dialogue, community-building karma)?	<input type="radio"/>				

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17. How important is it to have the option to upload an avatar instead of using your photo?	<input type="radio"/>				
18. How important is it to enable participation in discussions via video?	<input type="radio"/>				
19. How important is it to enable participation in discussions via audio?	<input type="radio"/>				
20. How important is it to offer an option of participating under a pseudonym instead of your real name?	<input type="radio"/>				

The following statements evaluate your perceptions of the platform's security and your readiness to use an AI-enabled deliberation platform. Please rate each statement on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

	1	2	3	4	5
21. I do not consider it safe to provide personal information on an AI-enabled deliberation platform.	<input type="radio"/>				
22. I worry that the information I make available over an AI-enabled deliberation platform may be misused by third parties.	<input type="radio"/>				
23. Whenever something gets automated using AI, it is important to check carefully that there are no mistakes.	<input type="radio"/>				
24. I feel uneasy about AI systems shaping important deliberations without human oversight.	<input type="radio"/>				
25. I worry that my input in the AI-enabled platform's deliberation process could be misinterpreted by the AI systems.	<input type="radio"/>				

The following statements assess your perceptions of an AI-enabled deliberation platform's usefulness. Please rate each statement on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

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	1	2	3	4	5
26. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would enhance the effectiveness of my participation in deliberations.	<input type="radio"/>				
27. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would make it easier for me to participate in deliberations.	<input type="radio"/>				
28. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would increase my ability to participate in more deliberations.	<input type="radio"/>				
29. Using an AI-enabled deliberation platform would enable me to contribute more meaningfully to shaping and improving deliberation processes.	<input type="radio"/>				

30. Do you have any other suggestions about how AI could be used to enhance deliberation processes? (Open question/optional)

31. Do you have any other specific concerns about the use of AI in deliberations? (Open question/optional)

Table 20: Greek survey questionnaire

Φύλο

Άνδρας Γυναίκα Άλλο Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Ηλικία

18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65+
 Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Επίπεδο Εκπαίδευσης

Χωρίς επίσημη εκπαίδευση Δημοτικό Σχολείο Γυμνάσιο
 Πτυχίο Μεταδευτεροβάθμιας ή Επαγγελματικής Κατάρτισης Πτυχίο ΑΕΙ
 Μεταπτυχιακό Πτυχίο Ειδικευσης Διδακτορικό (PhD)
 Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Χώρα διαμονής

Γερμανία Ελλάδα Ιταλία Ηνωμένο Βασίλειο Άλλο (Ελεύτερο κείμενο)
 Δεν θέλω να απαντήσω

Εισαγωγή

Στην ιδανική της μορφή, η δημοκρατία βασίζεται στο διάλογο και τις διαβουλεύσεις μεταξύ των πολιτών, όπου και δίνονται σε όλους ίσες ευκαιρίες να εκφράσουν τη γνώμη τους (π.χ. να προτείνουν θέματα, μοιράζονται επιχειρήματα, ψηφίζουν εναλλακτικές). Ωστόσο, αυτή η διαδικασία μπορεί να είναι δύσκολο να διεξαχθεί και να διατηρηθεί σε μεγάλη κλίμακα στις σύγχρονες κοινωνίες. Τα εργαλεία που θα είναι ενισχυμένα με τεχνητή νοημοσύνη ενδέχεται

να προσφέρουν νέους τρόπους υποστήριξης του διαλόγου σε μεγαλύτερη κλίμακα και να φέρουν τις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις πιο κοντά στα ιδανικά της δημοκρατίας.

Στόχος μας είναι να κατανοήσουμε πώς τα εργαλεία τεχνητής νοημοσύνης μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν για να υποστηρίξουν τις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις σε δημοκρατίες και, μέσω αυτού, να δημιουργήσουμε μια ελεύθερα διαθέσιμη εργαλειοθήκη τεχνητής νοημοσύνης που μπορούν να χρησιμοποιήσουν ομάδες οπουδήποτε στον κόσμο για να βελτιώσουν τις δικές τους διαβουλεύσεις. Οι απαντήσεις σας στο ερωτηματολόγιο θα μας βοηθήσουν να εντοπίσουμε και να δώσουμε προτεραιότητα στα αρχικά χαρακτηριστικά της εργαλειοθήκης TN, τα οποία στη συνέχεια θα δοκιμάσουμε και θα βελτιώσουμε σε τέσσερα έργα για διαβουλεύσεις – ξεκινώντας αργότερα φέτος – στη Γερμανία, την Ελλάδα, την Ιταλία και μια διεθνή πρωτοβουλία που βασίζεται στο HB.

Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος ολοκλήρωσης: 20 λεπτά

1. Έχετε χρησιμοποιήσει εργαλεία Τεχνητής Νοημοσύνης σε οποιοδήποτε πλαίσιο, και αν ναι, ήταν χρήσιμη;
 - Σίγουρα δεν ήταν χρήσιμη
 - Μάλλον δεν είναι χρήσιμη
 - Δεν είμαι σίγουρος
 - Μάλλον ήταν χρήσιμη
 - Σίγουρα ήταν χρήσιμη
 - Δεν έχω χρησιμοποιήσει
2. Εάν ναι, θα μπορούσατε να περιγράψετε εν συντομία το πλαίσιο και τι βρήκατε χρήσιμο ή όχι; (ανοιχτή ερώτηση/προαιρετικό)

Για καθεμία από τις ακόλουθες λειτουργίες της πλατφόρμας, υποδείξτε την προτιμώμενη ισορροπία μεταξύ της χρήσης τεχνητής νοημοσύνης και ανθρώπινης επίβλεψης.

1 = Εξ ολοκλήρου ανθρωποκεντρική 2 = Κυρίως ανθρωποκεντρική με υποστήριξη τεχνητής νοημοσύνης 3 = Ισορροπία μεταξύ ανθρώπινης εμπλοκής και τεχνητής νοημοσύνης 4 = Κυρίως καθοδηγούμενη από την τεχνητή νοημοσύνη και με υποστήριξη ανθρώπινης επίβλεψης 5 = Πλήρως καθοδηγούμενη από τεχνητή νοημοσύνη

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	1	2	3	4	5
Περίληψεις Συζητήσεων	<input type="radio"/>				
Εποπτεία συζήτησης	<input type="radio"/>				
Έλεγχος γεγονότων	<input type="radio"/>				
Μεταφραστικές υπηρεσίες	<input type="radio"/>				
Προσδιορισμός σημείων συμφωνίας	<input type="radio"/>				
Πρόταση εναλλακτικών προοπτικών	<input type="radio"/>				
Επεξεργασία ανάδρασης χρηστών	<input type="radio"/>				
Παρακολούθηση μοτίβων συζήτησης	<input type="radio"/>				

Παρακάτω, θα βρείτε μια σειρά από χαρακτηριστικά και λειτουργίες μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητες TN του έργου.

Υποδείξτε πόσο σημαντικό είναι καθένα από τα ακόλουθα χαρακτηριστικά, σε κλίμακα από το 1 έως το 5, όπου:

1 = Σίγουρα όχι σημαντικό, 2 = πιθανώς όχι σημαντικό, 3 = ουδέτερο, 4 = σημαντικό, 5 = πολύ σημαντικό

	1	2	3	4	5
Περίληψεις Συζητήσεων (Δημιουργεί αυτόματα περίληψεις των συζητήσεων)	<input type="radio"/>				
Εποπτεία συζήτησης (Προτείνει αυτόματα οδηγίες και επισημαίνει ακατάλληλο περιεχόμενο)	<input type="radio"/>				
Έλεγχος γεγονότων (Εντοπίζει πραγματικά γεγονότα, παρέχοντας επαληθευμένες πληροφορίες για να διασφαλίσει ότι τα επιχειρήματα που χρησιμοποιούνται είναι σωστά κατά τη διάρκεια των συζητήσεων)	<input type="radio"/>				
Μεταφραστικές υπηρεσίες (Προσφέρει αυτοματοποιημένες μεταφράσεις)	<input type="radio"/>				

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Προσδιορισμός σημείων συμφωνίας (Συγκεντρώνει παρόμοια σημεία και προσδιορίζει βασικές κατηγορίες στις συζητήσεις)	<input type="radio"/>				
Πρόταση εναλλακτικών προοπτικών (Προτείνει διαφορετικές απόψεις για να εμπλουτίσει τις συζητήσεις και να ενθαρρύνει την κριτική σκέψη)	<input type="radio"/>				
Επεξεργασία ανάδρασης χρηστών (Αναλύει τα σχόλια για να ιεραρχήσει τις βελτιώσεις)	<input type="radio"/>				
Παρακολούθηση μοτίβων συζήτησης (Παρακολουθεί τις τάσεις και τη δυναμική της συζήτησης για τη βελτιστοποίηση των μελλοντικών συζητήσεων)	<input type="radio"/>				

Για καθεμία από τις ακόλουθες ερωτήσεις και με βάση τη δική σας οπτική, αναφέρετε ποιες από τις ακόλουθες λειτουργίες είναι σημαντικό να έχει μια πλατφόρμα διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητες TN:

	1	2	3	4	5
3. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται στους συμμετέχοντες να επισημαίνουν σφάλματα στις περιλήψεις των συζητήσεων που δημιουργούνται από TN;	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι μεσολαβεί ενεργά η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη για να (παρακολουθεί, ρυθμίζει, διευκολύνει) τις συζητήσεις ώστε να διασφαλίσει τη συμπερίληψη;	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να προτείνει η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη σχετικές πηγές και στοιχεία κατά τη διάρκεια των συζητήσεων;	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επισημαίνει η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη δυνητικά παραπλανητικές πληροφορίες;	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να παρέχει σαφείς εξηγήσεις η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη όταν το περιεχόμενο προσδιορίζεται ως δυνητικά παραπλανητικό;	<input type="radio"/>				

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8. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται στους συμμετέχοντες να προτείνουν βελτιώσεις στις αυτόματες μεταφράσεις;	<input type="radio"/>				
9. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να μπορεί η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη να προτείνει συζητήσεις και θέματα με βάση τις προτιμήσεις και την προηγούμενη δραστηριότητά σας;	<input type="radio"/>				
10. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να συνδέεται με διαφορετικές οπτικές γωνίες για τα θέματα που συζητούνται;	<input type="radio"/>				
11. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να παρέχονται στοιχεία για τις προτεινόμενες διαφορετικές προοπτικές;	<input type="radio"/>				
12. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι για εσάς να γνωρίζετε πώς και γιατί η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη λειτουργεί όταν συμβάλλετε σε συζητήσεις (π.χ. εποπτεία περιεχομένου, σύνοψη, δημιουργία συναίνεσης);	<input type="radio"/>				
13. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να αποθηκεύουμε και να διαθέτουμε δημόσια αρχεία καταγραφής ελέγχου σημαντικών παρεμβάσεων τεχνητής νοημοσύνης σε συζητήσεις (π.χ. αφαίρεση περιεχομένου, αποφάσεις ελέγχου γεγονότων, περιλήψεις συναίνεσης);	<input type="radio"/>				
14. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται στους συμμετέχοντες να παρέχουν σχόλια σχετικά με τις λειτουργίες TN και να συμμετέχουν στη βελτίωση τους μέσω δομημένων μηχανισμών ανάδρασης;	<input type="radio"/>				
15. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να υπάρχουν κίνητρα συμμετοχής (όπως κονκάρδες εμπειρογνωμοσύνης σε διαβούλευση, επιτεύγματα οικοδόμησης συναίνεσης, αναγνώριση ποιότητας του διαλόγου κ.λπ.) για την ενθάρρυνση της ουσιαστικής συμμετοχής σε δημόσιες συζητήσεις;	<input type="radio"/>				
16. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να αναγνωρίζουμε τις ουσιαστικές συζητήσεις των συμμετεχόντων μέσω σημάτων επιτεύγματος με βάση τα συμφραζόμενα που αντικατοπτρίζουν την ποιότητα και τον αντίκτυπο της συμμετοχής (π.χ. γεφύρωση αντίθετων απόψεων, βελτίωση της συζήτησης που βασίζεται σε στοιχεία και	<input type="radio"/>				

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ενθάρρυνση του διαλόγου χωρίς αποκλεισμούς, κάρμα οικοδόμησης κοινότητας);					
17. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να έχετε την επιλογή να ανεβάσετε ένα avatar αντί να χρησιμοποιήσετε τη φωτογραφία σας;	<input type="radio"/>				
18. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται η συμμετοχή σε συζητήσεις μέσω βίντεο;	<input type="radio"/>				
19. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να επιτρέπεται η συμμετοχή σε συζητήσεις μέσω ήχου;	<input type="radio"/>				
20. Πόσο σημαντικό είναι να προσφέρεται η επιλογή συμμετοχής με ψευδώνυμο αντί για το πραγματικό σας όνομα;	<input type="radio"/>				

Οι παρακάτω προτάσεις αξιολογούν τις αντιλήψεις σας για την ασφάλεια της πλατφόρμας και την ειλικρίθειά σας να χρησιμοποιήσετε μια πλατφόρμα διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα TN. Βαθμολογήστε κάθε δήλωση σε μια κλίμακα από το 1 έως το 5, όπου:

1 = Διαφωνώ απόλυτα, 2 = Διαφωνώ, 3 = Ουδέτερος, 4 = Συμφωνώ, 5 = Συμφωνώ απόλυτα.

	1	2	3	4	5
21. Δεν θεωρώ ασφαλές να παρέχω προσωπικές πληροφορίες σε μια πλατφόρμα διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα TN.	<input type="radio"/>				
22. Ανησυχώ ότι οι πληροφορίες που διαθέτω μέσω μιας πλατφόρμας συσκέψεων με δυνατότητα TN μπορεί να χρησιμοποιηθούν καταχρηστικά από τρίτους.	<input type="radio"/>				
23. Κάθε φορά που αυτοματοποιείται κάτι χρησιμοποιώντας TN, είναι σημαντικό να ελέγχεται προσεκτικά ότι δεν υπάρχουν λάθη.	<input type="radio"/>				
24. Νιώθω άβολα για τα συστήματα τεχνητής νοημοσύνης που διαμορφώνουν σημαντικές συζητήσεις χωρίς ανθρώπινη επίβλεψη.	<input type="radio"/>				

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25. Ανησυχώ ότι η συνεισφορά μου στη διαδικασία συζήτησης της πλατφόρμας με δυνατότητα τεχνητής νοημοσύνης μπορεί να παρερμηνευθεί από τα συστήματα τεχνητής νοημοσύνης.	<input type="radio"/>				
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Οι ακόλουθες προτάσεις αξιολογούν τις αντιλήψεις σας για τη χρησιμότητα μιας πλατφόρμας διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα ΤΝ. Βοηθολογήστε κάθε δήλωση σε μια κλίμακα από το 1 έως το 5, όπου:

1 = Διαφωνώ απόλυτα, 2 = Διαφωνώ, 3 = Ουδέτερος, 4 = Συμφωνώ, 5 = Συμφωνώ απόλυτα.

	1	2	3	4	5
26. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα ΤΝ θα ενίσχυε την αποτελεσματικότητα της συμμετοχής μου σε διαβουλεύσεις.	<input type="radio"/>				
27. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα ΤΝ θα με διευκόλυε να συμμετάσχω σε διαβουλεύσεις.	<input type="radio"/>				
28. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα ΤΝ θα θα αυξήσει την ικανότητά μου να συμμετέχω σε περισσότερες διαβουλεύσεις.	<input type="radio"/>				
29. Η χρήση μιας πλατφόρμας διαβουλεύσεων με δυνατότητα ΤΝ θα μου επέτρεπε να συνεισφέρω πιο ουσιαστικά στη διαμόρφωση και τη βελτίωση των διαδικασιών διαβούλευσης.	<input type="radio"/>				

30. Έχετε άλλες προτάσεις σχετικά με το πώς θα μπορούσε να χρησιμοποιηθεί η τεχνητή νοημοσύνη για τη βελτίωση των διαδικασιών συζήτησης. (Αναιτή ερώτηση/προαιρετικό)

31. Έχετε άλλες συγκεκριμένες ανησυχίες σχετικά με τη χρήση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης στις διαβουλεύσεις. (Αναιτή ερώτηση/προαιρετικό)

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Table 21: German survey questionnaire

Geschlecht

Männlich Weiblich Andere Ich möchte nicht antworten

Alter

18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65+

Ich möchte nicht antworten

Bildungsstand

Keine formale Bildung Grundschule Sekundarschule

Associate Degree oder Berufsausbildung Bachelor-Abschluss

Master-Abschluss Professioneller Abschluss Doktorat (PhD)

Ich möchte nicht antworten

Land des Wohnsitzes

Deutschland Griechenland Italien Vereinigtes Königreich
Andere (Freier Text)

Ich möchte nicht antworten

(Dritte Seite)

Einführung

In ihrer idealen Form beruht die Demokratie auf dem Dialog und der Deliberation zwischen den Bürgern, bei denen jeder gleichberechtigt die Möglichkeit hat, seine Meinung zu äußern (z. B. Themen vorschlagen, Argumente austauschen, über Alternativen abstimmen). Allerdings kann es in modernen Gesellschaften schwierig sein, diesen Prozess in großem Maßstab durchzuführen und aufrechtzuerhalten. KI-gestützte Werkzeuge könnten neue Möglichkeiten bieten, den Dialog in größerem Maßstab zu unterstützen und öffentliche Deliberation näher an das demokratische Ideal heranzuführen.

Unser Ziel ist es, zu verstehen, wie KI-Werkzeuge zur Unterstützung öffentlicher Deliberationen in Demokratien eingesetzt werden können, und auf diese Weise ein frei verfügbares KI-Toolkit zu entwickeln, das Gruppen überall auf der Welt zur Verbesserung ihrer eigenen Beteiligungen nutzen können. Die Antworten, die Sie in dem Fragebogen geben, werden uns helfen, die ersten Merkmale des KI-Toolkits zu identifizieren und zu priorisieren, die wir dann in vier deliberativen Projekten - die im Laufe dieses Jahres beginnen - in Deutschland, Griechenland, Italien und einer internationalen Initiative im Vereinigten Königreich testen und verfeinern werden.

Geschätzte Bearbeitungszeit: 20 Minuten

PENDING APPROVAL

1. Haben Sie in irgendeinem Zusammenhang Werkzeuge der künstlichen Intelligenz eingesetzt, und wenn ja, waren sie hilfreich?

- Definitiv nicht hilfreich
- Wahrscheinlich nicht hilfreich
- Nicht sicher
- Wahrscheinlich hilfreich
- Definitiv hilfreich
- bisher nicht genutzt

2. Wenn ja, könnten Sie kurz den Kontext beschreiben und was Sie als hilfreich oder nicht hilfreich empfunden haben? (offene Frage/optional)

Bitte geben Sie für jede der folgenden Plattformfunktionen an, welches Verhältnis zwischen KI-Unterstützung und menschlicher Aufsicht Sie bevorzugen.

1 = Vollständig menschengeführt 2 = Überwiegend menschengeführt mit KI-Unterstützung 3 = Gleichgewicht zwischen menschlicher und KI-Beteiligung 4 = Überwiegend KI-geführt mit menschlicher Aufsicht 5 = Vollständig KI-geführt

	1	2	3	4	5
Diskussionszusammenfassung	<input type="radio"/>				
Diskussionsmoderation	<input type="radio"/>				

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Faktenüberprüfung	<input type="radio"/>				
Übersetzungsdienste	<input type="radio"/>				
Identifizierung von Übereinstimmungen	<input type="radio"/>				
Vorschlagen alternativer Perspektiven	<input type="radio"/>				
Verarbeitung von Benutzerfeedback	<input type="radio"/>				
Verfolgung von Diskussionsmustern	<input type="radio"/>				

Im Folgenden finden Sie eine Reihe von Merkmalen und Funktionen einer KI-gestützten Deliberationsplattform.

Bitte geben Sie auf einer Skala von 1 bis 5 an, wie wichtig jedes der folgenden Merkmale ist, wenn:

1 = Definitiv nicht wichtig, 2 = Wahrscheinlich nicht wichtig, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Wichtig, 5 = Sehr wichtig

	1	2	3	4	5
Diskussionszusammenfassung (Automatische Erstellung von Zusammenfassungen von Diskussionen)	<input type="radio"/>				

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Diskussionsmoderation (schlägt automatisch Richtlinien vor und kennzeichnet unangemessene Inhalte)	<input type="radio"/>				
Faktenüberprüfung (Identifizierung und Überprüfung der Faktenlage, Bereitstellung überprüfter Informationen, um sicherzustellen, dass die in den Beratungen verwendeten Fakten korrekt sind)	<input type="radio"/>				
Übersetzungsdienste (bietet automatisierte Übersetzungen an)	<input type="radio"/>				
Identifizierung von Übereinstimmungen (Bündelung ähnlicher Punkte und Identifizierung von Schlüsselkategorien in Diskussionen)	<input type="radio"/>				
Vorschlagen alternativer Perspektiven (Vorschlagen verschiedener Standpunkte, um Diskussionen zu bereichern und kritisches Denken zu fördern)	<input type="radio"/>				
Verarbeitung von Benutzerfeedback (Analyse des Feedbacks zur Festlegung von Prioritäten für Verbesserungen)	<input type="radio"/>				
Verfolgung von Diskussionsmustern (Überwachung von Trends und Dynamiken bei der Beteiligung, um zukünftige Beratungen zu optimieren)	<input type="radio"/>				

Geben Sie für jede der folgenden Fragen an, welche der folgenden Funktionalitäten eine KI-gestützte Deliberationsplattform aus Ihrer Sicht haben sollte:

	1	2	3	4	5
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PENDING EC APPROVAL

3. Wie wichtig ist es, den Teilnehmern die Möglichkeit zu geben, die von der KI erstellten Zusammenfassungen der Diskussionen auf Fehler zu überprüfen?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Wie wichtig ist es für die KI, Diskussionen aktiv zu moderieren (zu überwachen, zu regulieren, zu erleichtern), um die Einbeziehung aller zu gewährleisten?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Wie wichtig ist es, dass KI bei Diskussionen relevante Quellen und Belege vorschlägt?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Wie wichtig ist es für KI, potenziell irreführende Informationen zu erkennen?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Wie wichtig ist es für KI, klare Erklärungen zu liefern, wenn Inhalte als potenziell irreführend eingestuft werden?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. Wie wichtig ist es, dass die Teilnehmer Verbesserungsvorschläge für automatische Übersetzungen machen können?	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Wie wichtig ist es, dass die KI auf der Grundlage Ihrer Präferenzen und Ihrer bisherigen Aktivitäten Vorschläge für Beratungen und Themen macht?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. Wie wichtig ist es, mit verschiedenen Perspektiven zu den diskutierten Themen in Verbindung gebracht zu werden?	<input type="radio"/>				
11. Wie wichtig ist es, Belege für die vorgeschlagenen unterschiedlichen Perspektiven zu liefern?	<input type="radio"/>				

PENDING EC APPROVAL

12. Wie wichtig ist es für Sie zu wissen, wie und warum KI bei der Teilnahme an Diskussionen vorgeht (z. B. Moderation von Inhalten, Zusammenfassen, Konsensbildung)?	<input type="radio"/>				
13. Wie wichtig ist es, Audit-Protokolle von bedeutenden KI-Eingriffen in Diskussionen zu speichern und öffentlich zugänglich zu machen (z. B. Entfernung von Inhalten, Entscheidungen zur Überprüfung von Fakten, Konsenszusammenfassungen)?	<input type="radio"/>				
14. Wie wichtig ist es, den Teilnehmern die Möglichkeit zu geben, Feedback zu KI-Funktionen zu geben und durch strukturierte Feedback-Mechanismen zu deren Verbesserung beizutragen?	<input type="radio"/>				
15. Wie wichtig ist es, eine sinnvolle Beteiligung an öffentlichen Diskussionen durch Anreize für bürgerschaftliches Engagement zu fördern (z. B. Abzeichen für Beratungskompetenz, Erfolge bei der Konsensbildung, Anerkennung der Dialogqualität usw.)?	<input type="radio"/>				
16. Wie wichtig ist es, sinnvolle Beiträge von Teilnehmern durch kontextbezogene Leistungssignale anzuerkennen, die die Qualität und die Auswirkungen der Teilnahme widerspiegeln (z. B. Überbrückung gegensätzlicher Standpunkte, Förderung evidenzbasierter Diskussionen und eines integrativen Dialogs, gemeinschaftsbildendes Karma)?	<input type="radio"/>				
17. Wie wichtig ist es, die Möglichkeit zu haben, einen Avatar hochzuladen, anstatt Ihr Foto zu verwenden?	<input type="radio"/>				
18. Wie wichtig ist es, die Teilnahme an Diskussionen per Video zu ermöglichen?	<input type="radio"/>				
19. Wie wichtig ist es, die Teilnahme an Diskussionen über Audio zu ermöglichen?	<input type="radio"/>				
20. Wie wichtig ist es, die Möglichkeit zu bieten, unter einem Pseudonym anstelle Ihres echten Namens teilzunehmen?	<input type="radio"/>				

Die folgenden Aussagen bewerten die von Ihnen wahrgenommene Sicherheit der Plattform und Ihre Bereitschaft, eine KI-gestützte Deliberationsplattform zu nutzen. Bitte bewerten Sie jede Aussage auf einer Skala von 1 bis 5, wobei:

1 = stimme überhaupt nicht zu, 2 = stimme nicht zu, 3 = neutral, 4 = stimme zu, 5 = stimme voll und ganz zu.

	1	2	3	4	5
21. Ich halte es nicht für sicher, persönliche Informationen auf einer KI-gestützten Deliberationsplattform bereitzustellen.	<input type="radio"/>				
22. Ich befürchte, dass die Informationen, die ich über eine KI-gestützte Deliberationsplattform zur Verfügung stelle, von Dritten missbraucht werden könnten.	<input type="radio"/>				
23. Wann immer etwas mit Hilfe von KI automatisiert wird, ist es wichtig, sorgfältig zu prüfen, dass es keine Fehler gibt.	<input type="radio"/>				
24. Ich habe ein ungutes Gefühl, wenn KI-Systeme wichtige Entscheidungen ohne menschliche Aufsicht treffen.	<input type="radio"/>				
25. Ich befürchte, dass meine Eingaben in den Beratungsprozess der KI-gestützten Plattform von den KI-Systemen falsch interpretiert werden könnten.	<input type="radio"/>				

Mit den folgenden Aussagen bewerten Sie die Nützlichkeit einer KI-gestützten Deliberationsplattform. Bitte bewerten Sie jede Aussage auf einer Skala von 1 bis 5, wobei:

1 = stimme überhaupt nicht zu, 2 = stimme nicht zu, 3 = neutral, 4 = stimme zu, 5 = stimme voll und ganz zu.

	1	2	3	4	5
26. Der Einsatz einer KI-gestützten Deliberationsplattform würde die Effektivität meiner Teilnahme an Deliberationen erhöhen.	<input type="radio"/>				
27. Der Einsatz einer KI-gestützten Deliberationsplattform würde mir die Teilnahme an Deliberationen erleichtern.	<input type="radio"/>				
28. Der Einsatz einer KI-gestützten Deliberationsplattform würde es mir ermöglichen, an mehr Deliberationen teilzunehmen.	<input type="radio"/>				
29. Der Einsatz einer KI-gestützten Deliberationsplattform würde es mir ermöglichen, einen sinnvolleren Beitrag zur Gestaltung und Verbesserung von Deliberationsprozessen zu leisten.	<input type="radio"/>				

30. Haben Sie weitere Vorschläge, wie KI zur Verbesserung von Deliberationsprozessen eingesetzt werden könnte? (Offene Frage/optional)
31. Haben Sie weitere spezifische Bedenken gegen den Einsatz von künstlicher Intelligenz bei Beratungen? (Offene Frage/optional)

Table 22: Italian survey questionnaire

Introduzione

Nella sua forma ideale, la democrazia si basa sul dialogo e sulla deliberazione tra i cittadini, cioè a tutti viene data pari opportunità di esprimere la propria opinione (ad esempio, proporre argomenti, condividere argomentazioni, votare su alternative). Tuttavia, questo processo può essere difficile da condurre e sostenere su larga scala nelle società moderne. Gli strumenti di intelligenza artificiale potrebbero offrire nuovi modi per sostenere il dialogo su larga scala e avvicinare le deliberazioni pubbliche all'ideale democratico.

Il nostro obiettivo è capire come gli strumenti di IA possano essere utilizzati per sostenere la deliberazione pubblica in democrazia e, attraverso questo, costruire un kit di strumenti di IA liberamente disponibili che i gruppi di tutto il mondo possano utilizzare per migliorare i propri processi deliberativi. Le risposte fornite nel questionario ci aiuteranno a identificare e dare priorità alle caratteristiche iniziali del kit di strumenti di IA, che verranno poi testate e perfezionate in quattro progetti deliberativi - a partire dalla fine dell'anno - in Germania, Grecia, Italia e in un'iniziativa internazionale con sede nel Regno Unito.

Tempo di compilazione stimato: 20 minuti

1. Hai utilizzato strumenti di Intelligenza Artificiale in qualche contesto e, se sì, ti sono stati utili?
- Decisamente non utile
 - Probabilmente non di aiuto
 - Non sono sicuro
 - Probabilmente utile
 - Decisamente utile
 - Non ho utilizzato

2. Se sì, puoi descrivere brevemente il contesto in cui l'hai utilizzata e cosa hai trovato utile o meno? (domanda aperta/facoltativa)

Per ciascuna delle seguenti funzioni della piattaforma, indica quale bilanciamento preferisci tra il supporto dell'IA e la supervisione umana.

1 = Completamente guidato dall'essere umano; 2 = Principalmente guidato dall'essere umano con il supporto dell'IA; 3 = Equilibrio tra coinvolgimento dall'essere umano e dell'IA; 4 = Principalmente guidato dall'IA con supervisione umana; 5 = Completamente guidato dall'IA

	1	2	3	4	5
Riassunto delle discussioni	<input type="radio"/>				
Moderazione delle discussioni	<input type="radio"/>				
Fact-checking (controllo dei fatti)	<input type="radio"/>				
Servizi di traduzione	<input type="radio"/>				
Identificazione di aree di accordo	<input type="radio"/>				

Suggerimento di prospettive alternative	<input type="radio"/>				
Elaborazione del feedback degli utenti	<input type="radio"/>				
Tracciamento dei modelli di discussione	<input type="radio"/>				

Di seguito sono elencate una serie di caratteristiche e funzionalità di una piattaforma di deliberazione abilitata all'intelligenza artificiale.

Indica quanto è importante ciascuna delle seguenti caratteristiche, su una scala da 1 a 5, dove:

1 = Decisamente non importante; 2 = Probabilmente non importante; 3 = Neutro; 4 = Importante; 5 = Molto importante

	1	2	3	4	5
Riassunto delle discussioni (sintesi delle discussioni generate automaticamente)	<input type="radio"/>				
Moderazione delle discussioni (suggerisce automaticamente le linee guida per la discussione e segnala i contenuti inappropriati)	<input type="radio"/>				
Fact-checking (Verifica e organizza i fatti citati nella discussione fornendo informazioni verificate per garantire il loro corretto utilizzo nella deliberazione)	<input type="radio"/>				
Servizi di traduzione (offre traduzioni automatizzate)	<input type="radio"/>				
Identificare le aree di accordo (raggruppa i punti simili e identifica le categorie chiave nelle discussioni)	<input type="radio"/>				
Suggerire prospettive alternative (propone punti di vista diversi per arricchire le discussioni e incoraggiare il pensiero critico)	<input type="radio"/>				

Elaborazione del feedback degli utenti (analizza il feedback dell'utente per approntare miglioramenti alla piattaforma)	<input type="radio"/>				
Tracciare i modelli di discussione (monitorare le tendenze e le modalità di coinvolgimento per ottimizzare future deliberazioni).	<input type="radio"/>				

Per ciascuna delle seguenti domande, indicare quali delle seguenti funzionalità è importante che abbia una piattaforma di deliberazione abilitata all'IA, in base al proprio punto di vista:

	1	2	3	4	5
3. Quanto è importante consentire ai partecipanti di segnalare gli errori nelle sintesi delle discussioni generate dall'IA?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Quanto è importante per l'IA moderare attivamente (monitorare, regolare, facilitare) le discussioni per garantire l'inclusività?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Quanto è importante avere un'intelligenza artificiale che suggerisca fonti e prove rilevanti durante le discussioni?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Quanto è importante che l'IA segnali le informazioni potenzialmente fuorvianti?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Quanto è importante che l'IA fornisca spiegazioni chiare quando il contenuto viene identificato come potenzialmente fuorviante?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. Quanto è importante consentire ai partecipanti di suggerire miglioramenti alle traduzioni automatiche?	<input type="radio"/>				
9. Quanto è importante che l'IA suggerisca attività deliberative e argomenti di discussione in base alle sue preferenze e alle attività precedenti?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. Quanto è importante essere messi a conoscenza di diverse opinioni sugli argomenti in discussione?	<input type="radio"/>				
11. Quanto è importante fornire prove per le diverse opinioni suggerite?	<input type="radio"/>				
12. Quanto è importante per lei sapere come e perché l'AI agisce quando dà un contributo alle discussioni (ad esempio: moderazione dei contenuti, riassunto, creazione di consenso)?	<input type="radio"/>				

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13. Quanto è importante salvare e rendere pubblicamente disponibili i registri di audit degli interventi significativi dell'IA nelle discussioni (ad esempio: rimozione di contenuti, decisioni di fact-checking, sintesi del consenso)?	<input type="radio"/>				
14. Quanto è importante consentire ai partecipanti di fornire un riscontro sulle funzionalità dell'IA e di contribuire al loro miglioramento attraverso meccanismi di feedback strutturati?	<input type="radio"/>				
15. Quanto è importante incoraggiare una significativa partecipazione alle discussioni pubbliche attraverso incentivi verso l'impegno civico (come badge di competenza nella deliberazione, risultati nella costruzione del consenso, riconoscimento della qualità del dialogo, ecc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
16. Quanto è importante riconoscere i contributi significativi dei partecipanti attraverso segnali di risultato contestualizzati che riflettano la qualità e l'impatto della partecipazione (ad esempio, il superamento di punti di vista opposti, l'elevazione di discussioni basate su prove, la promozione di un dialogo inclusivo, la costruzione di un karma comunitario)?	<input type="radio"/>				
17. Quanto è importante avere la possibilità di caricare un avatar invece di utilizzare la sua foto?	<input type="radio"/>				
18. Quanto è importante consentire la partecipazione alle discussioni via video?	<input type="radio"/>				
19. Quanto è importante consentire la partecipazione alle discussioni via audio?	<input type="radio"/>				
20. Quanto è importante offrire la possibilità di partecipare con un pseudonimo invece che con il proprio nome reale?	<input type="radio"/>				

Le seguenti affermazioni valutano la tua percezione sulla sicurezza della piattaforma e la tua disponibilità a utilizzare una piattaforma di deliberazione abilitata dall'intelligenza artificiale. Si prega di valutare ogni affermazione su una scala da 1 a 5, dove:

1 = Fortemente in disaccordo, 2 = Disaccordo, 3 = Neutro, 4 = Accordo, 5 = Fortemente in accordo.

	1	2	3	4	5
21. Non ritengo sicuro fornire informazioni personali su una piattaforma di deliberazione dotata di IA.	<input type="radio"/>				

22. Mi preoccupa il fatto che le informazioni che rendo disponibili su una piattaforma di deliberazione dotata di IA possano essere utilizzate in modo improprio da terzi	<input type="radio"/>				
23. Ogni volta che qualcosa viene automatizzato utilizzando l'IA, è importante controllare attentamente che non ci siano errori	<input type="radio"/>				
24. Non mi sento a mio agio nell'utilizzare sistemi di intelligenza artificiale che danno forma a deliberazioni importanti senza la supervisione di un essere umano	<input type="radio"/>				
25. Temo che il mio contributo al processo di deliberazione della piattaforma dotata di IA possa essere interpretato in modo errato dai sistemi di IA.	<input type="radio"/>				

Le seguenti affermazioni valutano la tua percezione sull'utilità di una piattaforma di deliberazione abilitata all'intelligenza artificiale. Si prega di valutare ogni affermazione su una scala da 1 a 5, dove:

1 = Fortemente in disaccordo; 2 = In disaccordo; 3 = Neutrale; 4 = D'accordo; 5 = Fortemente d'accordo

	1	2	3	4	5
26. L'utilizzo di una piattaforma di deliberazione dotata di IA migliorerebbe l'efficacia della mia partecipazione a processi deliberativi	<input type="radio"/>				
27. L'utilizzo di una piattaforma di deliberazione dotata di IA mi renderebbe più facile partecipare a processi deliberativi	<input type="radio"/>				
28. L'uso di una piattaforma di deliberazione abilitata dall'intelligenza artificiale aumenterebbe la mia capacità di partecipare a un maggior numero di processi deliberativi	<input type="radio"/>				
29. L'utilizzo di una piattaforma di deliberazione dotata di IA mi permetterebbe di contribuire in modo più significativo a plasmare e migliorare i processi deliberativi.	<input type="radio"/>				

30. Hai altri suggerimenti su come l'IA potrebbe essere utilizzata per migliorare i processi deliberativi? (Domanda aperta/facoltativa)

31. Hai altre preoccupazioni specifiche sull'uso dell'IA nei processi deliberativi? (Domanda aperta/facoltativa)

F. Semi-structured interview with pilot employees

The semi-structured interview is available in four languages (German, Greek, Italian, and English), one for each pilot.

Table 23: Semi-Structured interview for pilot employees– English

Invitation

An **AI-enabled deliberation platform** uses AI to facilitate structured, inclusive, and effective discussions among large groups of people. By leveraging AI, these platforms could address challenges associated with large-scale deliberations, such as maintaining civility, ensuring inclusivity, and synthesizing diverse viewpoints. AI could help with the **moderation of conversations, validation of facts, summarizations of discussions, etc.**

This interview is conducted in the framework of the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. Our goal is to understand how AI tools can support public deliberation in democracies and, through this, build a freely available AI toolkit that groups anywhere in the world can use to enhance their own

deliberations.

The answers you share in the questionnaire will help us identify and prioritise the initial features of the AI toolkit, which we will then test and refine in four deliberative projects – starting later this year – in Germany, Greece, Italy, and an international initiative based in the UK.

The interview aims to gather pilots' needs with regard to the use of AI in deliberations. This is an effective way to capture diverse, real-time insights directly from you who engage with processes and tools daily.

Demographics

Ask the participants about their role in their organization (pilot). Do not mention the name of the organization in the answers you will send for analysis.

Strategic and Organizational Impact

1. Do you think your current deliberation processes/platforms need to change? If yes, why? *(existing platform)*
2. How do you believe an AI-enabled deliberation platform contributes to the organization's long-term strategic goals? *(AI-toolkit platform)*
3. Are you aware of national and international policies that may restrict the use of such a platform? *(AI-toolkit platform)*
4. How could this platform improve the institutionalization of public deliberation practices? (embedding structured, inclusive, and impactful public discussions into formal decision-making processes) *(AI-toolkit platform)*
5. What impact could this platform have on transparency and accountability in decision-making processes? *(AI-toolkit platform)*
6. Why, to you, is (large-scale inclusive) deliberation important to be done?

Platform Experience and User Interface (UI/UX) Expectations

7. What are the expectations for the user interface? (e.g., intuitive design, mobile-friendly, accessibility features) *(AI-toolkit platform)*
8. Are there any specific accessibility requirements? *(AI-toolkit platform)*

Change Management and Communication

9. What level of training and documentation need to be provided to users? *(AI-toolkit platform)*

Technical and Functional Requirements

10. How the platform's data should be organized, stored, and accessed? Are you aware of any (data) standards that already exist/are being created? *(interaction between the two platforms)*
11. What are the requirements for performance and scalability (e.g., expected traffic, number of users)? *(AI-toolkit platform)*
12. What security and compliance standards must be met? *(AI-toolkit platform)*
13. Are there any technical constraints (e.g., operating systems, browsers, devices)? *(interaction between the two platforms, AI-toolkit platform)*
14. What are the core functionalities the platform must provide? (e.g., user authentication, reporting, dashboards, data visualization, data management) *(AI-toolkit platform)*

General opinion

15. Is there anything else you would like to mention?

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Table 24: Semi-Structured interview for pilot employees– Italian

Invito

Una **piattaforma di deliberazione dotata di Intelligenza Artificiale** utilizza l'IA per facilitare discussioni strutturate, inclusive ed efficaci tra gruppi con un gran numero di persone. Sfruttando l'IA, su larga scala, queste piattaforme potrebbero affrontare le sfide derivanti dalle deliberazioni come: mantenere un dialogo civile, garantire l'inclusività e sintetizzare i diversi punti di vista. L'IA potrebbe aiutare nella **moderazione delle conversazioni**, nella **validazione dei fatti**, nelle **sintesi delle discussioni**, ecc.

Questa intervista è condotta nell'ambito del progetto, finanziato dall'Unione europea, AI4Deliberation (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu>). Il nostro obiettivo è capire come gli strumenti di IA possano essere utilizzati per supportare la deliberazione pubblica nelle democrazie e, attraverso questo, costruire degli strumenti IA liberamente disponibili che possano essere utilizzati da gruppi di persone per migliorare le proprie deliberazioni.

Le risposte condivise nel questionario ci aiuteranno a identificare e dare priorità alle caratteristiche iniziali degli strumenti IA, che verranno testati e perfezionati in quattro progetti deliberativi - a partire dalla fine dell'anno - in Germania, Grecia, Italia e in un'iniziativa internazionale con sede nel Regno Unito.

L'intervista mira a raccogliere le esigenze dei progetti pilota in merito all'uso dell'IA nel deliberare. Si tratta di un modo efficace per catturare intuizioni diverse e in tempo reale direttamente da voi che vi impegnate quotidianamente con i processi e gli strumenti.

Dati demografici

Ruolo del partecipante nella sua organizzazione.

Impatto strategico e organizzativo

1. Ritiene che i suoi attuali processi/piattaforme di deliberazione debbano cambiare? Se sì, perché? (*Piattaforma esistente*)
2. In che modo ritiene che una piattaforma di deliberazione dotata di IA contribuisca agli obiettivi strategici a lungo termine dell'organizzazione? (*Piattaforma AI-toolkit*)
3. È a conoscenza delle politiche nazionali e internazionali che potrebbero limitare l'uso di tale piattaforma? (*Piattaforma AI-toolkit*)
4. Come potrebbe questa piattaforma migliorare l'istituzionalizzazione delle pratiche di deliberazione pubblica? (*Piattaforma AI-toolkit*)
5. Quale impatto potrebbe avere questa piattaforma sulla trasparenza e sulla responsabilità nei processi decisionali? (*Piattaforma AI-toolkit*)
6. Perché, secondo lei, è importante fare una deliberazione (inclusiva su larga scala)?

Esperienza della piattaforma e aspettative dell'interfaccia utente (UI/UX)

7. Quali sono le aspettative per l'interfaccia utente? (ad esempio: design intuitivo, facilità d'uso per i dispositivi mobili, caratteristiche di accessibilità) (*Piattaforma AI-toolkit*)
8. Ci sono requisiti specifici di accessibilità? (*Piattaforma AI-toolkit*)

Gestione del cambiamento e comunicazione

9. Quale livello di formazione e documentazione deve essere fornito agli utenti? (*Piattaforma AI-toolkit*)

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Requisiti tecnici e funzionali

10. Come devono essere organizzati, archiviati e consultati i dati della piattaforma? È a conoscenza di standard (di dati) già esistenti o in fase di creazione? *(Interazione tra le due piattaforme)*
11. Quali sono i requisiti di performance e scalabilità (ad esempio, traffico previsto, numero di utenti)? *(Piattaforma AI-toolkit)*
12. Quali standard di sicurezza e conformità devono essere rispettati? *(Piattaforma AI-toolkit)*
13. Ci sono vincoli tecnici (ad esempio: sistemi operativi, browser, dispositivi)? *(Interazione tra le due piattaforme, piattaforma AI-toolkit)*
14. Quali sono le funzionalità principali che la piattaforma deve fornire? (ad esempio: autenticazione dell'utente, report, dashboard, visualizzazione dei dati, gestione dei dati) *(Piattaforma AI-toolkit)*

Opinione generale

15. C'è qualcos'altro che vorresti menzionare?

Table 25: Semi-Structured interview for pilot employees– Greek

Πρόσκληση

Μια Πλατφόρμα Διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητες TN χρησιμοποιεί την τεχνητή νοημοσύνη για να διευκολύνει δομημένες, περιεκτικές και αποτελεσματικές συζητήσεις μεταξύ μεγάλων ομάδων ανθρώπων. Με τη μόχλευση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης, αυτές οι πλατφόρμες θα μπορούσαν να αντιμετωπίσουν προκλήσεις που σχετίζονται με δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις μεγάλης κλίμακας, όπως η διατήρηση της ευγένειας, η διασφάλιση της συμπεριληψής και η σύνθεση διαφορετικών απόψεων. Η TN θα μπορούσε να βοηθήσει με την **επιτοπεία των συνμιλιών**, την **επικύρωση γεγονότων**, την **σύνοψηση συζητήσεων κ.λπ.**

Αυτή η συνέντευξη πραγματοποιείται στο πλαίσιο του έργου AI4Deliberation (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) που χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση. Στόχος μας είναι να κατανοήσουμε πώς τα εργαλεία τεχνητής νοημοσύνης μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν για να υποστηρίξουν τις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις σε δημοκρατίες και, μέσω αυτού, να δημιουργήσουμε μια ελεύθερα διαθέσιμη εργαλειοθήκη τεχνητής νοημοσύνης που μπορούν να χρησιμοποιήσουν ομάδες οπουδήποτε στον κόσμο για να βελτιώσουν τις δικές τους διαβουλεύσεις.

Οι απαντήσεις σας στο ερωτηματολόγιο θα μας βοηθήσουν να εντοπίσουμε και να δώσουμε προτεραιότητα στα αρχικά χαρακτηριστικά της εργαλειοθήκης TN, τα οποία στη συνέχεια θα δοκιμάσουμε και θα βελτιώσουμε σε τέσσερα έργα για διαβουλεύσεις – ξεκινώντας αργότερα φέτος – στη Γερμανία, την Ελλάδα, την Ιταλία και μια διεθνή πρωτοβουλία που βασίζεται στο ΗΒ.

Η συνέντευξη στοχεύει να συγκεντρώσει τις ανάγκες των πιλότων σχετικά με τη χρήση της τεχνητής νοημοσύνης στις δημόσιες διαβουλεύσεις. Αυτός είναι ένας αποτελεσματικός τρόπος για να συλλέξουμε ποικίλες πληροφορίες σε πραγματικό χρόνο απευθείας από εσάς που ασχολείστε καθημερινά με διαδικασίες και εργαλεία.

Δημογραφικά στοιχεία

Ο ρόλος του συμμετέχοντος στον φορέα/οργανισμό του.

Στρατηγικός και Οργανωτικός Αντίκτυπος

1. Πιστεύετε ότι οι τρέχουσες διαδικασίες/πλατφόρμες διαβούλευσης πρέπει να αλλάξουν; Αν ναι, γιατί; *(υπάρχουσα πλατφόρμα)*
2. Πώς πιστεύετε ότι μια πλατφόρμα διαβούλευσης με δυνατότητα TN συμβάλλει στους μακροπρόθεσμους στρατηγικούς στόχους του οργανισμού; *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
3. Γνωρίζετε εθνικές και διεθνείς πολιτικές που ενδέχεται να περιορίσουν τη χρήση μιας τέτοιας πλατφόρμας; *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
4. Πώς θα μπορούσε αυτή η πλατφόρμα να βελτιώσει τη θεσμοθέτηση των πρακτικών δημόσιας διαβούλευσης; *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
5. Τι αντίκτυπο θα μπορούσε να έχει αυτή η πλατφόρμα στη διαφάνεια και τη λογοδοσία στις διαδικασίες λήψης αποφάσεων; *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
6. Γιατί, για εσάς, είναι σημαντικό να γίνει (μεγάλης κλίμακας χωρίς αποκλεισμούς) διαβούλευση;

Προσδοκίες εμπειρίας πλατφόρμας και διεπαφής χρήστη (UI/UX).

7. Ποιες είναι οι προσδοκίες για τη διεπαφή χρήστη; (π.χ. διαισθητικός σχεδιασμός, φιλικός προς κινητά, δυνατότητες προσβασιμότητας) *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
8. Υπάρχουν συγκεκριμένες απαιτήσεις προσβασιμότητας; *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*

Διαχείριση Αλλαγών και Επικοινωνία

9. Τι επίπεδο εκπαίδευσης και τεκμηρίωσης πρέπει να παρέχεται στους χρήστες; *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*

Τεχνικές και Λειτουργικές Απαιτήσεις

10. Πώς πρέπει να οργανώνονται, να αποθηκεύονται και να έχουν πρόσβαση τα δεδομένα της πλατφόρμας; Γνωρίζετε κάποια πρότυπα (δεδομένων) που ήδη υπάρχουν/δημιουργούνται; *(αλληλεπίδραση μεταξύ των δύο πλατφορμών)*
11. Ποιες είναι οι απαιτήσεις για απόδοση και επεκτασιμότητα (π.χ. αναμενόμενη επισκεψιμότητα, αριθμός χρηστών); *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
12. Ποια πρότυπα ασφάλειας και συμμόρφωσης πρέπει να πληρούνται; *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
13. Υπάρχουν τεχνικοί περιορισμοί (π.χ. λειτουργικά συστήματα, προγράμματα περιήγησης, συσκευές); *(αλληλεπίδραση μεταξύ των δύο πλατφορμών, πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*
14. Ποιες είναι οι βασικές λειτουργίες που πρέπει να παρέχει η πλατφόρμα; (π.χ. έλεγχος ταυτότητας χρήστη, αναφορές, πίνακες εργαλείων, οπτικοποίηση δεδομένων, διαχείριση δεδομένων) *(πλατφόρμα AI-toolkit)*

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Table 26: Semi-Structured interview for pilot employees– German

Einladung

Eine **KI-gestützte Deliberationsplattform** nutzt KI, um strukturierte, integrative und effektive Diskussionen zwischen großen Gruppen von Menschen zu ermöglichen. Durch den Einsatz von KI könnten diese Plattformen die Herausforderungen bewältigen, die mit groß angelegten Beteiligungsverfahren verbunden sind, wie z. B. die Aufrechterhaltung des Anstands, die Gewährleistung der Inklusivität und die Synthese verschiedener Standpunkte. KI könnte bei der **Moderation von Gesprächen**, der **Validierung von Fakten**, der **Zusammenfassung von Diskussionen usw.** helfen.

Dieses Interview wird im Rahmen des von der Europäischen Union finanzierten Projekts AI4Deliberation (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) geführt. Unser Ziel ist es, zu verstehen, wie KI-Werkzeuge öffentliche Beratungen in Demokratien unterstützen können, und auf diese Weise ein frei verfügbares KI-Toolkit zu entwickeln, das Gruppen überall auf der Welt nutzen können, um ihre eigenen Beratungen zu verbessern.

Ihre Antworten auf den Fragebogen werden uns dabei helfen, die ersten Merkmale des KI-Toolkits zu ermitteln und zu priorisieren. Diese werden wir dann in vier Projekten in Deutschland, Griechenland, Italien und einer internationalen Initiative im Vereinigten Königreich testen und verfeinern, die noch in diesem Jahr beginnen.

Ziel der Befragung ist es, die Bedürfnisse der Piloten im Hinblick auf den Einsatz von KI in Beratungen zu erfassen. Dies ist ein effektiver Weg, um verschiedene Echtzeit-Einsichten direkt von Ihnen zu erhalten, die täglich mit Prozessen und Tools arbeiten.

Demografische Daten

Rolle des Teilnehmers in seiner Organisation. Erwähnen Sie nicht den Namen der Organisation.

Strategische und organisatorische Auswirkungen

1. Meinen Sie, dass Ihre derzeitigen Beteiligungsverfahren/-plattformen geändert werden müssen? Wenn ja, warum? (*bestehende Plattform*)
2. Wie trägt eine KI-gestützte Deliberationsplattform Ihrer Meinung nach zu den langfristigen strategischen Zielen der Organisation bei? (*KI-Toolkit-Plattform*)
3. Sind Sie sich der nationalen und internationalen Politik bewusst, die die Nutzung einer solchen Plattform einschränken könnte? (*KI-Toolkit-Plattform*)
4. Wie könnte diese Plattform die Institutionalisierung von öffentlichen Beteiligungs/Diskussionsprozessen verbessern? (*KI-Toolkit-Plattform*)
5. Welche Auswirkungen könnte diese Plattform auf die Transparenz und Rechenschaftspflicht in Entscheidungsprozessen haben? (*KI-Toolkit-Plattform*)
6. Warum ist es Ihrer Meinung nach wichtig, eine (umfassende) Beratung durchzuführen?

Erwartungen an die Plattform und die Benutzeroberfläche (UI/UX)

7. Welche Erwartungen werden an die Benutzeroberfläche gestellt (z. B. intuitives Design, Mobilfreundlichkeit, Zugänglichkeitsfunktionen) (*KI-Toolkit-Plattform*)
8. Gibt es besondere Anforderungen an die Zugänglichkeit? (*AI-toolkit Plattform*)

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Veränderungsmanagement und Kommunikation

9. Welches Maß an Schulung und Dokumentation muss den Nutzern zur Verfügung gestellt werden? *(KI-Toolkit-Plattform)*

Technische und funktionale Anforderungen

10. Wie sollen die Daten der Plattform organisiert, gespeichert und abgerufen werden? Sind Ihnen (Daten-)Standards bekannt, die bereits existieren/erstellt werden? *(Interaktion zwischen den beiden Plattformen)*
11. Welche Anforderungen gibt es an die Leistung und Skalierbarkeit (z. B. erwarteter Datenverkehr, Anzahl der Nutzer)? *(KI-Toolkit-Plattform)*
12. Welche Sicherheits- und Compliance-Standards müssen eingehalten werden? *(KI-Toolkit-Plattform)*
13. Gibt es technische Beschränkungen (z. B. Betriebssysteme, Browser, Geräte)? *(Interaktion zwischen den beiden Plattformen, KI-Toolkit-Plattform)*
14. Welche Kernfunktionalitäten muss die Plattform bieten? (z. B. Benutzerauthentifizierung, Berichterstattung, Dashboards, Datenvisualisierung, Datenverwaltung) *(KI-Toolkit-Plattform)*

G. Semi-structured interview with best practice case owners

The semi-structured interview for the best practice case owners is available in English.

Table 27: Semi-structured interview with best practice case owners

Invitation

An AI-enabled deliberation platform could facilitate structured, inclusive, and effective discussions among large groups of people. By leveraging artificial intelligence, these platforms could address challenges associated with large-scale deliberations, such as maintaining civility, ensuring inclusivity, and synthesizing diverse viewpoints. Through such platforms, citizens could propose topics, share arguments, vote on alternatives, and receive summaries of the discussions. AI tools could help moderate conversations fairly, validate

facts, and highlight consensus points, fostering productive and outcome-oriented discussions.

This interview is conducted within the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. Our goal is to understand how AI tools can be used to support public deliberation in democracies and, through this, to build a freely available AI toolkit that groups anywhere in the world can use to enhance their own deliberations.

The interview aims to obtain critical information (requirements) about deliberation processes and platforms with or without AI features, from people who have already successfully implemented similar platforms or processes.

Questions for the interview:

1. Some information about the platform (e.g. open-source, maintenance, owner, hosting)
2. What are the main features of the platform? (e.g. gamification, multimodal, video, massive deliberations, AI features);
3. Where and how has the platform been used?
4. What are the problems they face?
5. How do you see the role of artificial intelligence in your platform?
6. Are you planning to adopt AI? If so, what features?
7. What do you see as the advantages and what are the difficulties?
8. What would be your advice for the AI4Deliberation project? What AI features should we implement?

General opinion

9. Is there anything else you would like to mention?

H. Semi-structured interview with platform owners

The semi-structured interview for the platform owners is available in English.

Table 28: Semi-structured interview with platform owners

Invitation

An AI-enabled deliberation platform could facilitate structured, inclusive, and effective discussions among large groups of people. By leveraging artificial intelligence, these platforms could address challenges associated with large-scale deliberations, such as maintaining civility, ensuring inclusivity, and synthesizing diverse viewpoints. Through such platforms, citizens could propose topics, share arguments, vote on alternatives, and receive summaries of the discussions. AI tools could help moderate conversations fairly, validate

facts, and highlight consensus points, fostering productive and outcome-oriented discussions.

This interview is conducted within the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. Our goal is to understand how AI tools can be used to support public deliberation in democracies and, through this, to build a freely available AI toolkit that groups anywhere in the world can use to enhance their own deliberations.

The interview aims to obtain critical information (requirements) about deliberation processes and platforms with or without AI features, from people who have already successfully implemented similar platforms or processes.

Questions for the interview:

1. Some information about the platform (e.g. open-source, maintenance, owner, hosting)
2. What are the main features of the platform? (e.g. gamification, multimodal, video, massive deliberations, AI features).
3. Where and how has the platform been used?
4. What are the problems they face?
5. How do you see the role of artificial intelligence in your platform?
6. Are you planning to adopt AI? If so, what features?
7. What do you see as the advantages and what are the difficulties?
8. What would be your advice for the AI4Deliberation project? What AI features should we implement?

General opinion

9. Is there anything else you would like to mention?

I. Consent forms (only in English)

Table 29: Consent form of the survey

Consent form

Purpose of the Questionnaire: This survey is conducted as part of the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. The project aims to provide ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using, and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations.

The aim of this questionnaire is to understand: a) your opinion regarding some features and functionalities of an AI-enabled deliberation platform, b) your perceptions regarding this platform's security and your readiness to use it, and c) your perception regarding its usefulness. If you continue, there will be a short introduction to further facilitate your understanding.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in the survey is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate without any reason or justification. You may withdraw at any time while completing the questionnaire without any reason, justification, or consequences. **After the submission** of the questionnaire **you do not have** the option to withdraw.

Data collected: To participate in the survey, you will be asked to complete a questionnaire in which the information you will fill is **Gender, Age, Education Level, and Country of residence**. The above are optional, and you can complete and submit the questionnaire without sharing any of these.

We have selected the anonymous survey mode to prevent the saving of any personal data, including your IP address. The privacy statement on the protection of your personal data while using the EUSurvey tool can be found here:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/privacystatement>

However, the **IP** of every connection may be saved by the provider of EUSurvey for security reasons. For more information see:

https://surveys.acer.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/helpauthors#_Toc14

Please note, that [pilot's name] is not the provider of the EUSurvey tool and your IP address will not be shared with us.

Confidentiality: All responses will be kept confidential and stored securely. The provided information is anonymized. Only authorized research personnel from [pilot's name] will have access to the raw data.

If you have any questions about conducting the survey, you can contact us here [pilot's email or contact form].

Potential Risks: No risks from participating in the questionnaire are foreseen. However, if you feel uncomfortable at any point, you may choose to stop.

Benefits: Your participation contributes valuable insights for the project's AI tool kit. While there are no direct personal benefits to you, your support is greatly appreciated.

DECLARATION OF CONSENT - I declare that I have been fully informed about the terms of my participation in the survey.

By checking **Yes I consent**, I confirm that:

- I have read and understood the information provided above.
- I voluntarily agree to participate in this survey.

- I am at least 18 years old.
- Yes I Consent
- No, I do not Consent

Table 30: Consent form of the interviews with Best Practise Case Owners and Platform Owners

Consent form

Purpose of the interview: This interview is being conducted as part of the AI4Deliberation project (<https://www.ai4dproject.eu/>) funded by the European Union. The project aims to provide ethical AI tools and comprehensive guidance to assist governments in institutionalising, using, and evaluating multimodal, gamified, mass deliberations.

The interview aims to obtain critical information (requirements) about deliberation processes and platforms with or without AI features, from people who have already successfully implemented similar platforms or processes.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in the interview is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate without any reason or justification. You may withdraw at any time during the interview without any reason, justification, or consequences. After the submission of your answers you do not have the option to withdraw.

Data collected: In this interview, you will be asked only about your **role** in the organisation without mentioning the organisation's name.

In the interview, there will be a **voice recording** and it will be stored locally on the computer of the interviewer for a calendar week at max. After the transcription of your answers, the voice recording will be destroyed. The transcripts may also be shared with other entities who are part of the research project consortium and their employees, to which the controller entrusts the performance of specific activities in the scope of the research project.

Confidentiality: All responses will be kept confidential and stored securely. Only authorized research personnel will have access to the raw data. If you have any questions you can contact the data controller [data controller's name], here [email address or contact form].

The data will be processed based on consent to the processing of personal data and a statement of the purpose(es) for the processing (taking part in this research project). You may revoke your consent to the processing of personal data at any time before the data is aggregated. Such revocation does not affect processing which had already been completed upon consent before its revocation.

Data retention period: Your personal data collected for this research project shall be processed within the duration of the project and retained only as long as it is necessarily required to achieve the purpose of this project. Upon completion of the project, personal information will be deleted/anonymized.

Your rights are the following:

- to access data and to receive copies of the actual data;
- to correct (rectify) your personal data;
- to restrict processing of personal data;
- to erase personal data, subject to provisions of Art. 17 section 3 of the GDPR;
- to file a claim with the relevant authorities, if you believe data processing violates the law.

Consent:

By signing below, you confirm that:

- You have read and understood the information provided above.
- You voluntarily agree to participate in this interview.
- You consent to the voice recording of the interview.
- You understand that the recording will be stored locally for a maximum of one week and then deleted or earlier if the transcription is completed.
- You are at least 18 years old.

For the participant

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